

T.C.

SELÇUK ÜNİVERSİTESİ

SOSYAL BİLİMLER ENSTİTÜSÜ

İŞLETME ANABİLİM DALI

İŞLETME BİLİM DALI

**ISLAMIC FINANCE AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEADING ISLAMIC FINANCE
COUNTRIES**

Humayun HUMTA

DOKTORA TEZİ

Danışman

Doç. Dr. İbrahim Erem ŞAHİN

İkinci Danışman

Doç. Dr. Suna Akten ÇÜRÜK

Konya-2025

Bu çalışma, **16/01/2025** tarihinde ařağıdaki jüri tarafından **İřletme** Anabilim Dalı **İřletme** Bilim Dalı Programında Doktora Tezi olarak kabul edilmiřtir.

**Savunma
Tez Jürisi**

Doç. Dr. İbrahim Erem řahin
Selçuk Üniversitesi
İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi

Prof. Dr. Yunus CERAN
Selçuk Üniversitesi
İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi

Prof. Dr. Baki YILMAZ
Selçuk Üniversitesi
İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi

Prof. Dr. Halil AKMEŐE
Necmettin Erbakan Üniversitesi
Turizm Fakültesi

Doç. Dr. Suna Akten ÇÜRÜK
Necmettin Erbakan Üniversitesi
Siyasal Bilgiler Fakültesi

T. C.
SELÇUK ÜNİVERSİTESİ
Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Müdürlüğü

Öğrencinin	Adı Soyadı	Humayun Humta
	Numarası	184127001001
	Ana Bilim / Bilim Dalı	İşletme/ İşletme
	Programı	Tezli Yüksek Lisans <input type="checkbox"/> Doktora <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Tez Danışmanı	Doç. Dr. İbrahim Erem Şahin
	Tezin Adı	İslami Finans ve Ekonomik Kalkınma: Başlıca İslami Finans Ülkelerinde Karşılaştırmalı Bir Analiz

ÖZET

İslami finans, uluslararası finans alanında küresel büyüme görmüştür ve belirli ülkelere odaklanmıştır. İslami finansın son zamanlarda yılda yaklaşık %20 oranında büyümesi, kısmen adalet, katılım ve sahiplenme ilkeleri sayesinde, kalıcılığının ve geniş çekiciliğinin kanıtıdır. İslami finansın, risk paylaşımına verdiği önem, aşırı risk maruziyetine getirdiği kısıtlamalar ve somut ekonomik faaliyetlerle olan yakın bağlantısı nedeniyle teorik olarak şoklara karşı dirençli olduğu söylenebilir. Ekonomik kalkınma, bir ekonominin hayatta kalması için gerekli olan çok boyutlu bir süreçtir. Bir ekonominin gerçek ulusal gelirinin zamanla arttığı uzun vadeli, sürekli bir süreçtir. Yirmi birinci yüzyılda, gelişmekte olan ekonomilerin birincil hedefleri daha yüksek ekonomik kalkınmanın hayatta kalması ve sürdürülebilirliğidir. Bu çalışma, İslami finans ile ekonomik kalkınma arasındaki bağlantıyı inceler; burada İslami finans, İslami bankacılık, İslami sermaye piyasaları (kira sertifikası) ve İslami sigorta (takafül) ile ölçülür. Buna karşılık, ekonomik kalkınma, Birleşmiş Milletler Kalkınma Programı (UNDP) tarafından geliştirilen İnsani Kalkınma Endeksi ile ölçülür. Malezya, Endonezya, Kuveyt, Katar, Nijerya, Suudi Arabistan, Umman ve Türkiye gibi önde gelen İslami finans sektörü

lkeleri baęlamında 2015-2021 yılları arasında panel verileri kullanılarak, İslami finans ile ekonomik kalkınma arasında çeşitli göstergelerle ölçlen ilişki incelenmiş ve bu lkeler için sektör genişletmeye dair geçerli ve yenilikçi sonuçlar elde edilmiştir. Bu araştırma, her modelin sonuçlarını sonuçlandırmak için ç farklı Sıradan En Kçük Kareler Regresyon Modeli, En Kçük Kareler Kukla Deęişken Etki Modeli ve Rastgele Etki Modeli kullanmıştır:

a) Bir taraftan, sıradan en kçük kareler regresyon modelleri, doęrudan yabancı sermaye çıkışı ile İslami banka krlılıęı ve sukuk arasında negatif ve anlamlı bir ilişki göstermektedir. Dięer taraftan, doęrudan yabancı sermaye çıkışı, takafl ve krlılık ile sukuk arasındaki çarpan etkisiyle pozitif ve anlamlı bir şekilde ilişkilidir.

b) Rastgele etkili regresyon modeli, takafl ile insani gelişme endeksi (Ekonomik Kalkınma) arasında pozitif ve anlamlı bir baęlantı olduğunu göstermektedir. Sukuk, İslami bankaların krlılıęı yoluyla dzenleyici etki yoluyla insani gelişme endeksi ile pozitif ve anlamlı bir ilişkiye sahiptir. Giriş yapan doęrudan yabancı yatırım, hkmet verimlilięinin dzenleyici etkileri yoluyla ekonomik kalkınma ile pozitif ve önemli bir baęlantıya sahiptir.

c) En kçük kareler kukla deęişken regresyon modeli, İslami bankacılık ile Sukuk arasında gayri safi yurtiçi hasıla (GSYİH) zerinde pozitif ve anlamlı bir ilişki olduğunu göstermektedir. Aynı zamanda, takafl GSYİH ile anlamsız bir şekilde ilişkilidir. Dviz kuru ve enflasyon, siyasi istikrarın dzenleyici etkisi aracılıęıyla GSYİH ile pozitif ve önemli bir ilişkiye sahiptir. Malezya, Endonezya, Kuveyt, Katar, Nijerya, Suudi Arabistan ve Umman'da İslami bankacılıęın GSYİH'ye katkısı, Trkiye'den daha dşktr. Bu durum, dięer deęişkenler sabit tutulduğunda, İslami bankacılıęın Trkiye'nin GSYİH'sine katkısının dięer lkelerden daha fazla olduęu anlamına gelmektedir. Bu sonuçlar, belirtilen lkeler baęlamında İslami finans sektörn geliştirmeye yönelik geçerlidir.

T. C.
SELÇUK ÜNİVERSİTESİ
Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Müdürlüğü

Öğrencinin	Adı Soyadı	Humayun Humta	
	Numarası	184127001001	
	Ana Bilim / Bilim Dalı	İşletme/ İşletme	
	Programı	Tezli Yüksek Lisans <input type="checkbox"/>	Doktora <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
	Tez Danışmanı	Doç. Dr. İbrahim Erem Şahin	
	Tezin Adı	Islamic Finance And Economic Development: A Comparative Analysis of Leading Islamic Finance Countries	

ABSTRACT

Internationally, Islamic finance has expanded, focusing on specific nations. Islamic finance has recently experienced annual growth of around 20%, mainly attributable to the principles of equality, participation, and ownership. The principles of Islamic finance, which include a focus on risk sharing, limits on excessive risk exposure, and a solid link to actual economic activities, make it potentially immune to shocks. Economic development, a multi-dimensional process, is essential to the long-term viability of any economy—the rising, accurate national income results from a gradual but steady process over several decades. The main goal of emerging economies in the 21st century is to maintain and improve their economic development. This research examines how Islamic banking, Islamic capital markets (Sukuk), and Islamic insurance (Takaful) relate to economic development. On the other hand, we evaluate economic development using the UNDP-developed Human Development Index. We evaluate economic development using the Human Development Index (HDI) developed by the UNDP. To analyze the expansion of the Islamic finance industry, we utilized panel data spanning

2015–2021, focusing on prominent Islamic finance hubs, including Malaysia, Indonesia, Kuwait, Qatar, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, Oman, and Türkiye. Our goal was to investigate the correlation between Islamic finance and various proxies for economic development. To conclude each model, this study used three distinct regression models: ordinary least squares regression models, least squares dummy variable effect models, and random effect models.

a) On the one hand, ordinary least squares regression models show a negative and significant correlation between FDI outflow and Islamic bank profitability and Sukuk. On the other hand, the outflow of foreign direct investment is positively and significantly associated with takaful and the multiplication of profitability and Sukuk.

b) According to the random effect regression model, a positive and statistically significant correlation exists between takaful and the human development index (Economic Development). Islamic bank profitability moderates the association between the human development index and Sukuk, which has a positive and statistically significant relationship with the index. Government efficiency moderates incoming foreign direct investment and economic development, showing a positive and substantial relationship.

c) The least squares dummy variable regression model has found a favorable and statistically significant correlation between Islamic banking, Sukuk, and GDP. However, the correlation between Takaful and GDP is insignificant. Political stability moderates the relationship between inflation, the exchange rate, and GDP, resulting in a positive and statistically significant association. In Malaysia, Indonesia, Kuwait, Qatar, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, and Oman, Islamic banking contributes less to GDP than in Türkiye. This means that Islamic banking's contribution to Türkiye's GDP is greater than other countries by keeping other variables constant. These results are valid for enhancing the Islamic finance sector in the context of the mentioned countries.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Islamic finance describes the whole system of Islamic financial institutions that provide banking and other financial services under Islamic law and regulation. This system also encompasses Islamic capital markets (Sukuk), Islamic insurance (Takaful), Islamic mutual funds, and other similar institutions; it does not consider banks. According to the new Human Development Index (NHDI), economic development occurs when a country's income, education, and health all rise at the same time, and its value falls between ranges (0) and (1). Countries whose religion is based on the Noble Qur'an and the hadiths of Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) are more likely to have Islamic finance, which plays a significant role in economic development. Hence, Islamic financial legislation and execution are necessary for non-Islamic civilizations, especially in Islamic nations. This dissertation explores how Islamic banking, insurance, Takaful, and bonds contribute to economic growth, human development, and the outflow of foreign direct investment in leading countries such as Türkiye, Saudi Arabia, Oman, Kuwait, Nigeria, and Malaysia. After the study, we compared Türkiye's Islamic finance industry and economic development with those of other mentioned countries, and we emphasized the essential recommendations for this industry's expansion. This study stands out from others due to its utilization of three distinct impact models: the ordinary least squares regression model, the least squares dummy variable impact model, and the random effect model yielding unique and valid results. I express my profound gratitude for the collaboration and supervision of my supervisor, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Ibrahim Erem Sahin, the thesis monitoring committee members, Prof. Dr. Baki YILMAZ and Assoc. Prof. Dr. Suna Akten ÇÜRÜK, throughout the research process and its completion. I also express my heartfelt thanks to Prof. Dr. Yunus CERAN and Prof. Dr. Halil AKŞEME, whose perceptive inquiries and diligent assessment have significantly enhanced the accuracy and significance of my research. Sincerely thankful to all the professors and colleagues who have supported me considerably in completing this doctorate dissertation. It is worth mentioning that I am pleased with the material and spiritual support of my dear parents, family, and wife, especially my elder brother, Dr. Naqibullah Zaki, and I pray that God will be pleased with them.

Humayun HUMTA

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ÖZET	i
ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	v
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS.....	xiii
LIST OF TABLES.....	xvi
LIST OF FIGURES	xviii
INTRODUCTION.....	xxi
PART ONE: ISLAMIC FINANCE, TYPES, AND ITS MECHANISM OF APPLICATION	1
1.1. Introduction to Islamic Finance	1
1.2. Islamic Finance from Starts to Development.....	5
1.2.1. Are Islamic banks riskier compared to conventional banks?	14
1.2.2. Islamic Capital Markets.....	21
1.2.3. Nature of Sukuk and Its Development Across the History	21
1.2.3.1. Comparison of Sukuk and Bonds	23
1.2.3.2. Accounting For Sukuk.....	24
1.2.4. Takaful.....	25
1.2.4.1. Islamic Insurance vs Traditional Insurance	26
1.2.4.2. Types of Takaful.....	28
1.2.4.2.1. General Takaful.....	28
1.2.4.2.2. Family Takaful	28

1.2.4.2.3. Islamic Insurance Options For Families	28
1.2.4.3. Takaful Business Models.....	29
1.2.4.4. Accounting For Takaful.....	35
1.2.4.4.1. Accounting For Family Takaful.....	35
1.2.4.4.2. Accounting For General Takaful Business	36
1.2.4.4.3. Accounting For Shareholders Funds	37
1.2.5. Modes of Islamic Finance.....	39
1.2.5.1. Murabaha.....	40
1.2.5.2. Mudarabah.....	41
1.2.5.3. Musharakah	42
1.2.5.4. Muzare and Musakat	43
1.2.5.5. Salam.....	44
1.2.5.6. Istisna	45
1.2.5.7. Ijara	47
1.2.5.8. Tawarruq	48
1.2.5.9. Bai Al Wafa.....	48
1.2.3.3. Sukuk and Its Types	49
1.2.3.3.1 Sukuk Al- Modaraba	50
1.2.3.3.2. Sukuk Al Ijara.....	51
1.2.3.3.3. Sukuk Al Musharakah	52
1.2.3.3.4. Sukuk Al Murabaha.....	54
1.2.3.3.5. Salam Sukuk	54
1.2.3.3.6. Sukuk Istisna	55
1.2.5.10. Qard Al Hasan.....	57

1.2.6. International Organization For Islamic Finance	57
1.2.6.1. Accounting and Audit Organization For Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI).....	57
1.2.6.2. International Financial Service Board.....	57
1.2.6.3. Islamic Development Bank	58
1.2.6.4. SESRIC	59
1.2.6.5. International Islamic Rating Agency	59
1.2.6.6. Islamic Research and Training Institution	60
1.2.6.7. International Islamic Financial Market	60
1.2.6.8. International Islamic Liquidity Management Corporation (IILM)...	60
1.2.6.9. International Islamic Fiqh Academy	60
1.2.6.10. Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC)	61
1.3. Global Islamic Finance Landscape	61
PART TWO: ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	68
2.1. The Nature of Development Economics	68
2.2. What Do We Mean by Development	69
2.3. Traditional Economics Measures	70
2.4. The New Economic View of Development	70
2.5. The Three Objectives of Development	71
2.6. Three Core Values of Development.....	72
2.7. The Theories of Economic Development	73
2.7.1. Adam Smith’s Theory.....	73
2.7.2. Ricardian Economic Development Theory.....	74
2.7.3. Malthusian Theory.....	76

2.7.4. G.S. Mail Theory	78
2.7.5. Demographic Transition Theory of Population.....	79
2.7.6. Optimum Theory of Population.....	80
2.7.7. Karl Marx's Theory of Economic Development	81
2.7.8. Schumpeter's Theory of Economic Development	83
2.7.9. Keynesian Theory of Economic Development.....	84
2.7.10. Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth.....	85
2.7.11. Gerschenkron's Great Spurt Theory.....	86
2.7.12. Nurkse's Theory of Disguised Unemployment as A Saving Potential ..	87
2.7.13. Lewis Economic Development Model	87
2.7.14. FEI- Ranis Model of Economic Development	89
2.7.15. Jorgenson's Neo-Classical Model of a Dual Economy	90
2.7.16. Harris-Todaro Model of Migration and Unemployment.....	92
2.7.17. Leibenstein's Critical Minimum Effort Theory	94
2.7.18. Nelson's Low-Level Equilibrium Trap	95
2.7.19. Big Push Theory	97
2.7.20. Theory of Unbalanced Growth.....	98
2.7.21. Balanced Growth Theory	100
2.7.22. Dualism Theory of Economic Development.....	101
2.7.23. Dependent Theory of Underdevelopment	103
2.7.24. Limit to Growth Model	104
2.7.25. Gunnar Myrdal Theory of Circular Causation	106
2.8. Measurements of Economic Development	107

2.9. Systematic Literature Review	114
PART THREE: ISLAMIC FINANCE AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A COMPARATIVE INVESTIGATION OF THE LATEST INSIGHTS AND TRENDS FROM LEADING ISLAMIC FINANCE COUNTRIES, WITH A FOCUS ON TÜRKIYE	157
3.1. Significance and Objective of The Study.....	157
3.2. Limitation of Research.....	158
3.3. Data Set of The Research.....	159
3.4. Research Methodology.....	159
3.5. Panel Data	160
3.5.1. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Model.....	162
3.5.2. Fixed Effect Model.....	163
3.5.2.1. The First-Difference Method	164
3.5.2.2. The Time-Demeaning Method.....	164
3.5.2.3. Least Square Dummy Variable	165
3.5.3. Random Effects Model.....	166
3.6. Research Models	169
3.6.1. Effect Models of Islamic Banks on Foreign Direct Investment Outflow.....	169
3.6.1.1. Model Variables.....	170
3.6.1.2. Models Questions and Hypotheses	171
3.6.1.3. Models Analysis with Findings	171
3.6.1.4. Panel Data Line Plots.....	173
3.6.1.5. Questions and Hypotheses of Research	177
3.6.2. Random Effect Model of Takaful on Human Development	177
3.6.2.1. Models Variables	178

3.6.2.2. Models Questions and Hypotheses	179
3.6.2.3. Models Analysis with Findings	179
3.6.2.4. Remarks on Hypotheses of The Model.....	185
3.6.3. Least Square Dummy Variable Model.....	186
3.6.3.1. Models Variables	187
3.6.3.2. Models Questions and Hypotheses	188
3.6.3.3. Models Analysis with Findings	189
3.6.3.4. Remarks on Hypotheses of The Model.....	197
CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS	198
REFERENCES	205

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

NBFIs	: Non-Bank Financial Institutions
IFIs	: Islamic Financial Institutions
AAOIFI	: Accounting and Audit Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions
IFSB	: International Financial Service Board
IsDB	: Islamic Development Bank
IsDBI	: Islamic Development Bank Institute
ICIEC	: Islamic Corporation for The Insurance of Investment and Export Credit
ICD	: Islamic Corporation for The Development of The Private Sector
ISFD	: Islamic Solidarity Fund for Development
ITFC	: International Islamic Trade Finance Corporation
SESRIC	: Statistical, Economic, And Social Research and Training Center for Islamic Countries
IIRA	: International Islamic Rating Agency
IRTI	: Islamic Research and Training Institution
IIFM	: International Islamic Financial Market
IILM	: International Islamic Liquidity Management Corporation
IIFA	: International Islamic Fiqh Academy
OIC	: Organization of Islamic Cooperation
IFDI	: Islamic Finance Development Indicator

HDI	: Human Development Index
NHDI	: New Human Development Index
GDP	: Gross Domestic Product
PPP	: Power Purchasing Parity
LICs	: Low-Income Countries
LMCs	: Lower- Middle-Income Countries
UMCs	: Upper- Middle Countries
HICs	: High-Income Countries
OECD	: Organization For Economic Cooperation and Development
UN	: United Nation
UNDP	: United Nations Development Program
LDCs	: Least Developed Countries
LLDCs	: Landlocked and Small Island Countries
HIPCs	: Heavily Indebted Poor Countries
NICs	: Newly Industrializing Countries
PRISMA	: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
ARDL	: Autoregressive Distributed Lag
OLS	: Ordinary Least Squire
FE	: Fix Effect
RE	: Random Effect

- LSDV** : Least Square Dummy Variable
- FDI-Out** : Foreign Direct Investment Outflows
- FIG** : Figure
- ICFM** : Islamic Conference of Foreign Ministers
- SPV** : Special Purpose Vehicle
- PSA** : Participants Special Account
- PA** : Participants Account

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1. Islamic Banking History Timeline Events	13
Table 1.2. Existing Islamic Banking Products and Services.....	14
Table 1.3. Critical Issues Facing Islamic Financial Institutions Worldwide.....	18
Table 1.4. Differentiation Between Islamic and Conventional Bank	19
Table 1.5. Comparison of Islamic and Western Bank Financial Statements	20
Table 1.6. Differentiation of Islamic and Non-Islamic Insurances	27
Table 1.7. Islamic Finance Distribution (2021)	61
Table 1.8. Leading IFDI Nations And Global Average IFDI Rating For 2022.....	64
Table 1.9. Islamic Finance Development Indicators (Rank, Country and Indicators Scores)	66
Table 1.10. Islamic Finance Development Indicators.....	66
Table 1.11. Sub-Indicator of Financial Performance	66
Table 2.1. Search Databases.....	116
Table 2.2. Systematic Literature Review	150
Table 3.1 Description of the Variables Used in the Model.....	170
Table 3.2. Descriptive Statistics.....	172
Table 3.3. Correlation Matrix.....	172
Table 3.4. Regression Analysis.....	173
Table 3.5. Questions and Hypotheses of Research	177
Table 3.6. Description of the Variables Used in the Model.....	178
Table 3.7. Descriptive Statistics.....	180
Table 3.8. Correlation Matrix.....	180
Table 3.9. OLS Regression	180
Table 3.10. Fixed Effect Regression	181
Table 3.11. Random Effect Regression.....	181
Table 3.12. Model Selection	181
Table 3.13. Diagnostics Tests or Specification of The Selected Model.	182

Table 3.14. Robust Random Effect Model.....	182
Table 3.15. Remarks on Hypotheses of The Model.....	185
Table 3.16. Description of the Variables Used in The Model	187
Table 3.17. Descriptive Statistics.....	189
Table 3.18. Regression Analysis.....	190
Table 3.19. Correlation Matrix.....	192
Table 3.20. Remarks on Hypotheses of The Model.....	197

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1. Key Principles of Islamic Finance.....	4
Figure 1.2. Islam's Style Categorization	6
Figure 1.3. Progression of the Islamic Finance Industry	9
Figure 1.4. Risks in Islamic Banking.....	17
Figure 1.5. Modaraba Model	31
Figure 1.6. Wakala Model	32
Figure 1.7. Hybrid Model	33
Figure 1.8. Waqf Model.....	34
Figure 1.9. Modes of Islamic Financing	40
Figure 1.10. Financing Based on Murabaha	41
Figure 1.11. Financing Based on Modaraba	42
Figure 1.12. Musharakah Based Financing.....	43
Figure 1.13. Istisna Based Financing.....	44
Figure 1.14. Salam Based Financing	45
Figure 1.15. Parallel Istisna	46
Figure 1.16. Ijara-Based Financing.....	47
Figure 1.17. Tawarruq.....	48
Figure 1.18. Bai Al Wafa	49
Figure 1.19. Sukuk Al Modaraba.....	51
Figure 1.20. Sukuk Al Ijara.....	52
Figure 1.21. Sukuk Al Musharakah	53
Figure 1.22. Sukuk Al Murabaha.....	54
Figure 1.23. Salam Sukuk.....	55
Figure 1.24. Sukuk Al Istisna	56
Figure 1.25. Islamic Finance Assets	62
Figure 1.26. Growth of Islamic Finance	62
Figure 1.27. Islamic Finance Assets	63
Figure 1.28. Islamic Finance Development Indicator.....	64

Figure 2.1. Smith's Growth Theory	74
Figure 2.2. Ricardian Theory	75
Figure 2.3. Malthusian Theory.....	77
Figure 2.4. Population Transition Theory.....	79
Figure 2.5. Optimum Population	80
Figure 2.6. Optimum population.....	80
Figure 2.7. Karl Marx's Theory of Economic Development	83
Figure 2.8. Schumpeter's Theory of Economic Development	84
Figure 2.9. Keynesian Theory of Economic Development.....	85
Figure 2.10. Lewis Economic Development Model	88
Figure 2.11. FEI- Ranis Model of Economic Development	90
Figure 2.12. Harris-Todaro Model of Migration and Unemployment.....	92
Figure 2.13. Leibenstein's Critical Minimum Effort Theory	95
Figure 2.14. Nelson's Low-Level Equilibrium Trap	96
Figure 2.15. Big Push Theory	98
Figure 2.16. Theory of Unbalanced Growth.....	99
Figure 2.17. Vicious Cycle of Poverty.....	100
Figure 2.18. Vicious Cycle of Poverty.....	100
Figure 2.19. The Cycle of Poverty Turning to Balance Growth.....	101
Figure 2.20. Dualism Theory of Economic Development	102
Figure 2.21. Production Function	102
Figure 2.22. Dependent Theory of Underdevelopment	104
Figure 2.23. Limit to Growth Model	105
Figure 2.24. Circular Causation	107
Figure 2.25. LCDs Map	108
Figure 2.26. HDI Dimensions and Indicators	110
Figure 2.27. HDI- Value and Rank.....	112
Figure 2.28. Comparing The Ranking of HDI and GNI Per Capita (PPP, 2017)...	113
Figure 2.29. Comparing The HDI.....	113

Figure 2.30. GDP Per Capita Vs GDP Per Capita (PPP).....	114
Figure 2.31. PRISMA Statement	115
Figure 3.1. Diagram of Selecting Appropriate Models of Effects	168
Figure 3.2. Panel Data Line Plots	174
Figure 3.3. Panel Data Line Plots	175
Figure 3.4. Scatter Plot Matrix.....	175
Figure 3.5. Normal Probability Plot.....	176
Figure 3.6. Panel Data Line Plot.....	183
Figure 3.7. Panel Data Line Plot.....	183
Figure 3.8. Scatter Plot Matrix.....	184
Figure 3.9. Normal Probability Plot.....	184
Figure 3.10. Panel Data Line Plot.....	193
Figure 3.11. Panel Data Line Plot.....	193
Figure 3.12. Scatter Plot Matrix.....	194
Figure 3.13. Normal Probability Plot.....	195

INTRODUCTION

To grasp the development of Islamic economics completely, one must refer to both the Quran and Sunnah, as well as Usul-al-Fiqh (Islamic Legal Theory), which are the primary legal sources of Islam. Utilizing methods such as Ijma, Qiyas, Istishab, Maslahah Mursalah, and Sadd al-Dhar'ai, helps address contemporary struggles. Accounting, finance, business, and management courses must incorporate Islamic knowledge to keep Islamic economics relevant to modern society. Islamic knowledge incorporates classical sources like al-fiqh and Maqas id al-Sharah and more contemporary ideas that consider contemporary reality without secularist principles.

Over the past twenty years, there has been a worldwide boom in Islamic funds inside the corporate sector. Stock market investors have shown significant interest in the Islamic financial system within the international financial sector, and Islamic finance has seen exceptional expansion. Islamic banking has become more appealing to experts, monetary authorities, and academics seeking a stable and reliable alternative to conventional banking due to the current global financial crisis. Islamic finance tools are becoming more critical in businesses' financing decisions, which raises the issue of how much of an impact they have. Eliminating gambling components (maysir), limiting uncertainty (gharar), and eliminating riba are the three pillars of Islamic financial products. Based on these criteria, Islamic financial instruments fall into the overarching category of Sale-based, Profit-Loss Sharing (PLS), or Hybrid. For repayment structure, Sale-based instruments combine the initial payment with a pre-determined premium; these fixed-income securities are also known as loan instruments (Guizani & Ajmi, 2021, pp.763-766).

Public and private sectors worldwide have implemented several ideas and approaches to alleviate poverty and enhance the well-being of the impoverished. Islamic microfinance is becoming increasingly popular in countries with both Muslim and non-populations. Islamic finance has experienced significant growth and emerged as a prominent trend in finance. The primary reason is the increasing demand for Islamic

finance among Muslims, the remarkable success of Islamic banking worldwide, and its significant impact on the global gross domestic product (ZahidMahmood et al., 2017, p. 2).

Multiple findings from recent research demonstrate that Islamic finance is a practical approach to establishing a comprehensive financial system that fosters economic growth. Islamic financial assets grow from 15% to 20% annually in most of the world's top economies. These assets currently comprise three percent of the total assets of the world's banks. Research on development factors has received more attention as Islamic finance economics has grown internationally in the last few decades. As a result, savers and investors now have a better grasp of the need to consider ethical considerations while making financial decisions. Allah and his last messenger, Muhammad, peace be upon him, are the unwavering sources of guidance for an Islamic financial system's guiding principles, regulations, and procedures. The acceptance of financial transactions, contracts, or instruments is dependent on moral judgment. The economic principles outlined in the Quran, Hadith, and Sunnah provide a foundation for formulating the theories in Islamic economics. This method's ultimate objective is to facilitate the development of the Islamic economic system by establishing a procedure for revealing genuine and indisputable interpretations (Nawaz, 2019, p.2).

In the first part, we overview Islamic finance and its indicators and how to measure it in the context of some leading Islamic finance countries. Islamic finance is comprehensively explained in five different areas: Islamic banking, Islamic capital market, Islamic insurance, mutual funds, and non-bank Islamic financial institutions. World organizations and institutions are briefly discussed, along with the modes of Islamic finance. In part two, economic development and its measured skill are deeply explained. Some models and theories about economic growth and development are illustrated to compare the selected countries with one another. Furthermore, literature review and systematic literature review are discussed in the context of Islamic finance and economic development. In the third part, the application was conducted via Stata18

through three models, namely: ordinary least square model, random effect model, and least square dummy variable model. Some valid and new insights were concluded from the mentioned analyses to fill the existing gap in the literature review on the mentioned topic.

PART ONE

ISLAMIC FINANCE, TYPES, AND ITS MECHANISM OF APPLICATION

Foreign direct investment outflows, human development, and the gross domestic product (GDP) are three areas where Islamic finance plays a vital role for nations. Each component of Islamic Finance plays a crucial role in the national economy. Section one covers the essentials, including an overview of Islamic Finance, Islamic Mutual Funds, Islamic Banking, Takaful, Sukuk, and Islamic Finance Development Indicators (IFDIs) and a list of the top Islamic finance industries in the nation according to IFDIs. Several renowned worldwide organizations are actively involved in regulating, supervising, researching, and training both official personnel and individuals in this regard.

1.1. Introduction to Islamic Finance

The Islamic and capitalist economies differ in several ways, with the most significant distinction being that the Islamic economy strictly prohibits interest *riba* and speculation *gharar* while also enforcing shariah-compliant practices such as profit-loss sharing (*salam*, *murabaha*, *mudarabah*, etc.) and Wealth Redistribution (*zakat*, *waqf*, and *sadaqah*) (Kato, 2022, p. 1). In other words, Islamic financing is a financial service offered as a replacement to conventional financing to come across the specific requirements of Muslims. It operates by Islamic religious law (*shariah*), which prohibits uncertainty (*gharar*), gambling (*maysir*), and interest (*riba*) (Boubker et al., 2021, p. 2). Banking assets comprise 69.3% of the Islamic financial service industries (IFSI) portion, followed by *sukuk* at 29.8% and *takaful* contributions at 0.9% (IFSB, 2023, p. 220). Scholars from the International Council of Islamic Finance made significant strides in the field when they divided Islamic financial programs into six broad categories: Shariah-based, Islamic Economics, Islamic Finance, Islamic Management, Islamic Halal Management, and Islamic Accounting. Shariah transactions adhere to Shariah law and process, encompassing the fundamental contracts, legitimacy, and subject-to-matter of transactions, focusing on promoting social justice in Islamic economies. Islamic

economics is the field of study that examines micro- and macro-economic principles and practices based on Shariah teachings. This content explores the application of Islamic economic principles and investigates the permissibility or impermissibility of standard economic ideas and methods from an Islamic perspective. Islamic finance is a financial discipline that follows the principle of Shariah. The subject encompasses Islamic financial planning, risk management, takaful, wealth management, and Islamic banking and finance. Islamic management incorporates management ideas and practices derived from Islamic rule and Muamalat. It covers the four main facets of business administration: Management, Marketing, Finance, and Accounting. Halal management, deeply rooted in Islamic principles, primarily focuses on managing halal procedures within a halal firm. According to the halal management framework, there are three key areas: halal products and services, halal systems, and halal regulations. Islamic accounting refers to accounting and auditing practices grounded in Shariah law. Islamic Accounting Standards and Practices, Shariah Audits, Zakat Accounting, and Accounting for Social Responsibility are some of the topics covered in the modern day (Abd. Wahab et al., 2023, p. 814).

Obtaining money from banks, insurance companies, and the money and capital markets under suitable conditions and using this money efficiently can be known as the broad concept of Islamic finance. This entire operation should be done adhering to Islamic rules (Kahf, 2007, p. 277). When the term Islamic finance is utilized, the ban of riba is commonly associated with it. Zaher and Kabir Hassan (2001) argue that a comprehensive investigation and in-depth inquiry into Islamic finance is necessary. Reviewing contracts, risk allocation, consumer protection, and individual rights consider Islamic beliefs, prioritizing humanitarianism above traditional finance. Islamic economics is built on principles of social justice and resource allocation through partnership, fostering global brotherhood, promoting justice, assuring fair income distribution, and granting the private sector the flexibility to enhance human well-being.

The significant expansion of Islamic finance over the past four decades has been mainly powered by its unique ethical attributes, trailblazing elements, and the underlying

basis of trust rooted in faith (Ali, 2017, pp. 42-43). According to Islamic law, it is permissible to trade one good for another or one product for money. Riba, the practice of charging or paying interest, prohibits the exchange of one currency for another. Riba can be understood as a manifestation of Gharar, which refers to uncertainty. According to Shariah, interest and uncertainty are forbidden since their negative consequences outweigh the potential benefits. However, Gharar is permitted in cases where the benefits compensate for the damage.

To be in harmony with Shariah, transactions are permitted when both counter-values are exchanged simultaneously or when one counter-value is exchanged immediately and the other in the future. Although exchanging the two counter-values in the future might be possible, doing so would bring Gharar (uncertainty) into the deal. However, we may proceed if the advantages surpass the disadvantages. The Arabic root term gharra means to mislead, while the English word gharar means to cast doubt on or deceive. Gambling maysir, is an Arabic expression that comes from the words yasira (meaning simplicity) and yassara (meaning the chance to get something valuable without effort)(Paldi, 2014, P. 254).

Gharar, also known as uncertainty, can be defined in various ways:

- Pure speculation, in which the result is determined only by chance or gambling
- Unreliable result, in which the counter-value is either not reached or is unclear
- Unreliability of the item
- The object's uncertain future

Islamic finance is an investment technique that follows standards set by Shariah (Islamic Law). It emphasizes fairness and bans any unethical, speculative, or usurious activities. The two-tier shariah screening approach has been designed to evaluate the adherence of equities to shariah norms and principles, hence reflecting these values. A company's involvement in producing and selling pork products, alcohol, tobacco, deities, gambling, promoting immorality, and providing traditional interest- and derivatives-based financial services is one example of an activity that would trigger a more stringent

qualitative screening. Financial characteristics of liquidity banned revenue, and leverage are defined using quantitative screening criteria. Following these rules will place selected stocks in a particular conservative asset class. We expect the shares that meet the requirements to promote financial stability and lower risk. There is a need in the ethical investment market for strategies that consider social and environmental impacts, and two such approaches are Islamic finance and socially responsible investing (Widiastuti et al., 2022, p. 2).

Islam is a monotheistic religion with three fundamental components: faith, sharia, and morality. This concentration rests on internal and external matters, including the administration of internal affairs, the economy, and the conduct of elections that shape national legislatures. International relations pertain to the interactions between countries, while economics primarily concerns financial matters such as insurance, leasing, banking, housing capital, and venture capital. The chart (Fig 1. 2) below elucidates the need for the assertion above to be more critical, or in other terms, the categorization of a lifestyle based on Islam.

Fig 1.1. Key Principles of Islamic Finance

Source: (Errico et al., 2002, P.24; Abdullah & Chee,2013, p.7)

1.2. Islamic Finance from Starts to Development

Islam is a comprehensive living code. Islamic financial law is primarily derived from the Al-Quran and the Sunnah. Islam teaches us not just how to behave in society but also how to run a profitable business. Islamic law calls for establishing a fair, compassionate, and well-balanced community. Everyone must fulfil their responsibilities toward other people; by doing so, the rights of all individuals are safeguarded (Iqbal et al., 2014, p.122). Established in 1963, the Mith Ghamr Local Savings Bank is Egypt's first Islamic bank. Its primary objective is alleviating agricultural debts and providing alternative investment opportunities for Muslims. The Nasser Social Bank was an interest-free establishment in Egypt to be called a Bank founded in 1971. This was the first occasion that the government of a Muslim nation openly endorsed the creation of a financial organization that operates without charging interest. The involvement of a public authority in interest-free banking sent strong signals to wealthy Muslim business owners, even though the principal goals of the Nasser Social Banks were social, such as providing microcredits to small-scale enterprises, scholarships to students, and interest-free loans to the poor. Islamic financial law is primarily derived from the Al-Quran and the Sunnah. Islam teaches us not just how to behave in society but also how to run a profitable business. Islamic law calls for establishing a fair, compassionate, and well-balanced community. Islami is initially divided into three main parts: 1. Akhlaq 2. Aqedah 3. Shariah. As part of shariah, muamlaat is divided into public and private laws and internal affairs as part of public laws linked to banking through the economy. As shown below:

Fig 1.2. Islam's Style Categorization

Source: (Vicary Abdullah & Keon, 2010).

The Dubai Islamic Banks were formed in 1975 by a consortium of merchants. This bank was the first establishment of an Islamic Financial Institution in the private sector. Nevertheless, the UAE and Kuwait governments are vital because they provide funding assistance of 20% and 10% of the capital, respectively (Alharbi, 2015, p. 14).

The founding of the Islamic Development Bank in 1975 was a pivotal moment in the evolution of Islamic finance. The Islamic Development Bank (IDB) was established by the Organization of the Islamic Conference officials to ease international financial transactions. Promoting social and economic growth throughout the Muslim world has been the IDB's primary objective since its founding, by the Shariah philosophy. Numerous Islamic banking and finance initiatives have received substantial funding and support from the IDB. An alternative to traditional banking arose within the Islamic financial sector, which expanded from 1975 to 1990. During this period, a significant number of private Islamic financial institutions emerged. To exacerbate the situation, Pakistan, Iran, and

Sudan have publicly announced their intention to transition to Islamic-only banking systems and completely eradicate interest. As of 2014, Iran and Sudan have effectively accomplished these objectives. Furthermore, several global banks began providing Islamic financial products, which is essential. This unequivocally demonstrated the new model's feasibility and endorsement by worldwide stakeholders. The World Bank and the International Monetary Fund have recognized Islamic financial products as a possible means of intermediation (Errico & Sundararajan, 2002, p. 4). During the 1990s, the Islamic banking sector saw growth, and efforts were made to promote the growth of non-bank financial firms. In addition to banks, there has been a significant increase in Islamic financial institutions. These entities include insurance firms and investment. However, it is essential to mention that the banking sector holds most Islamic financial assets, accounting for 80% of the total. Organizations dedicated to infrastructure development emerged in the 1990s to bolster the Islamic financial industry. Initially, Islamic financial organizations had to operate inside the preexisting system that supported mainstream banking. The institutional architecture needed to accommodate the unique criteria of Islamic banking.

More and more nations, identifying as Muslim or not, are becoming members of international financial institutions (IFIs). Islamic financial institutions rose rapidly in response to the high demand for Islamic products and services among Muslims. These organizations currently offer a wide range of goods and services, including Islamic windows, Islamic investment funds and banks, Islamic mortgage businesses, takaful firms, and Mudarabah (Profit Sharing) companies.

During the nascent phase of the Islamic financial sector, endeavors were undertaken to develop a network of auxiliary institutions. There are now five different kinds of Islamic banking and finance available. 1. In countries where Muslims practice Islam, the government encourages the establishment of banks and other financial organizations. 2. Islamic financial institutions compete with more traditional ones in the commercial world. 3. Islamic windows, traditional Islamic Banks, and non-bank financial organizations are

how conventional commercial banks apply Islamic banking. 4. Shariah-compliant MNCs like the Islamic Development Bank in Jeddah; 5. Islamic capital market mechanisms like sukuk and mutual funds; and 6. the growing importance of Islamic insurance products like takaful. The five fundamental tenets of Islamic finance, which diverge from the concepts recognized in mainstream finance, are shown in Fig 1.1. The disparities distinguish Islamic financing from conventional finance. These steps have been taken in the progress of Islamic finance to launch the product in two generations. Islamic finance development steps in terms of product operation are illustrated below, but keep in mind that each forward step contains backward steps.

Step 1: Established in 1963, the Mith Ghamr Local Savings Bank is Egypt's first Islamic bank. Its primary objective is alleviating agricultural debts and providing alternative investment opportunities for Muslims. The establishment of the Islamic Development Bank in 1975 signaled the end of the commercial banking era that started in the 1960s and 1970s.

Step 2: In 1980, project financing began alongside commercial banking.

Step 3: The AAOIFI was founded in 1990, and in 1990, in addition to project financing and commercial banking, leasing, fund management, and equity topics were advanced.

Step 4: In 2000, the third stage of development included Islamic bonds, also known as sukuk, along with liquidity, the money market, alternative assets, and financial derivatives.

Fig 1.3. Progression of the Islamic Finance Industry

Source: (Abdullah & Chee, 2013, p.9)

A wide variety of Shariah-compliant financial products, including bonds, shares, and insurance, have emerged under Islamic finance. Some of the world's most prominent Islamic financial hubs, including Saudi Arabia, Malaysia, Bahrain, Qatar, Türkiye, and the UAE, heavily invest in Muslim-owned financial institutions. Universities worldwide have established several new Islamic Banks centers dedicated to studying Islamic banking. A crisis inside the Western system revealing its weaknesses and inefficiencies is necessary to complete this new system's development, now moving at a snail's pace. This issue has spread to other regions because of the financial arrangements that the United States and

Europe have set up. Therefore, since the 2007-2008 crisis, Islamic finance has gained more traction among economists seeking an alternative.

In contrast to other regions, the Islamic world has been unaffected by the recent default of the conventional system. A Muslim bank must adhere to Shariah law, prohibiting interest rates, speculations, and uncertainty. The divergence in ethical principles is the primary factor behind the distinctiveness of the Islamic financial model. Externally, an Islamic bank resembles a conventional bank. It functions as a financial manager, receiving client deposits via bank or investment accounts, generating income by lending these funds, and assuming a portion of the risk associated with financing projects. Islamic banks provide investment accounts that differ from interest-based banks in that depositors are not guaranteed against losses and do not receive fixed monthly amounts based on interest rates. This payout is contingent upon the bank's prosperity. Noninterest-bearing banking activities include:

- Half of the banking activities are exchange contracts.
- Eight percent are participation contracts.
- Two percent are leasing contracts.

Two types of financial management activities were established via Islamic approaches to adhere to the Islamic ban on *riba*. One approach is the use of profit and loss-sharing practices, which originate from traditional Islamic culture and are applied in the transactions involving stocks and bonds, property, and the establishment of agreements with financial institutions (Fianto et al., 2020, p. 1; Susilawati et al., 2023, p. 16).

- *Musharakah* contracts include forming partnerships with limitless liability, where members contribute varying capitals.
- *Mudarabah* agreements, characterized by the combined contribution of capital and labour, represent a joint stock corporation.

Furthermore, the non-profit and loss-sharing method is used when transferring usufruct and selling tangible personal property. The most notable legal agreement comprises:

- Salam contracts include selling goods when payment is made beforehand and delivery is postponed.
- Istisna's contracts are used to finance assets that are still in the process of completion, such as construction projects.
- Murabaha contracts include the bank purchasing tangible goods and selling them to customers at a higher price.

There is no guarantee that funds deposited or used via the Profit and Loss Sharing System will be fully refunded. The shortfall is deducted from the customer's account if the bank lacks sufficient funds to compensate for a potential loss. Within an Islamic bank, the Shariah board collaborates with the shareholders and directors to scrutinize its operations and ensure its compliance with Islamic law. A fatwa is given to convey authoritative rulings or opinions. Considering these attributes, Islamic banks meticulously evaluate all proposed business ventures, verifying their operational efficacy and financial investment by the regulatory capital requirements outlined in the pillars of the Basel 2 Accord.

Islamic Banks are required to adhere to the Basel Accords of 1988 and 2004 and be supervised by a Shariah board. These agreements pertain to prudential regulation and the maintenance of sufficient capital. The regulatory evaluation determines that financial institutions have sufficient capital to meet the risks associated with their unique business profiles and environments. Regulations and internal procedures encourage banks to determine and control their capital adequacy levels based on risk profiles, operations, and business plans. Supervisors monitor bank capital objectives and positions to ensure they align with the bank's risk profile and strategy.

For over a decade, the Islamic world has extensively examined the Western financial system to comprehend how to manage unforeseen circumstances and exploit every advancement to achieve worldwide expansion. Islamic finance must assure universal compliance with the established criteria across all institutions. uniform standards may facilitate the coordination of service and contract activities across several countries. The establishment of Islamic nations founded global financial institutions such as (AAOIFI), (IFSB), (IDB), (IIFM), and (IIRA) in 2002 ensured consistency in processes and management standards. Globalization, unrestricted money movement, and technological advancements have transformed the financial business (Mastrosimone, 2013, pp. 122-125).

Despite the positive changes brought about by globalization, the absence of laws and constant monitoring could lead to disastrous consequences. Due to the absence of globally accepted norms and rules, speculation has turned the actual economy into a financial system. Due to significant demand, Islamic Financial Institutions (IFIs) are consistently increasing in quantity and in the range of services they provide. However, as stated by Akram Laldin (2008), Islamic finance is unable to progress due to inadequate tax and regulatory structures. There have been two distinct epochs in Islamic banking and finance (IBF) history. The first starts with the arrival of the prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him). This marks the beginning of the first era. The Umayyad and Abbasid Epochs cover the orthodox caliphate, the recognized businesses, and the following generations. The second stage, which encompasses the present-day global financial and banking system, began in the nineteenth century.

The Muslim world saw the emergence of modern conventional banking in Egypt and India. In the 1890s, Barclays Bank established its first office in Cairo under the Ottoman Empire. This move immediately drew severe disapproval from Islamic clerics, primarily because of the interest-based nature of the financial transactions conducted by the bank. Consequently, Barclays shuttered the branch. In the 1940s, Islamic scholars in British India opposed financial transactions that included interest and issued a unified

fatwa, resulting in the establishment of the IBF. The Muslims of India opted for interest-free savings and lending organizations. Rejecting these banks, which had been operational in India before the partition. Following 1947, many cultural groups migrated to the recently established country of Pakistan. Regrettably, the expansion of IFIs was hindered by a slow pace, primarily due to a lack of trust and confidence from the public and government since no established regulatory body existed.

The evolution of Islamic financial institutions spans the first half of the twentieth century, and the present day is all about innovation and experimentation. The second stage, which encompasses the present-day global financial and banking system, began in the nineteenth century. Table 1.1 provides a detailed chronology of the second phase, which encompasses the operations of Islamic financial institutions and Islamic banking and finance from 1962 to 2016.

Table 1.1. Islamic Banking History Timeline Events

Year	Era
570 C. E	<p>Prophet Era</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A partnership that shares profits and losses (Musharakah or Shirkah) 2. The No-interest Benevolent Loan (Al Qard al Hasan) 3. The forward contract at Salaam 4. Swap (Exchange of money), whereby one party pays another in the same metal (gold for gold and silver for silver). 5. Ijarah (Leasing) 6. Caravans from Mekkah to larger Syria and returned were part of transregional trade. 7. Zakat, which is 2.5% of the required almsgiving to the destitute.
632 C. E	<p>Caliphs</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Abu Bakr Siddiq created the institution of mandatory zakat. 2. Omer ibn AL Khattab founded Bait at-mal, also known as the Federal Treasury House. 3. Uthman ibn Affan introduced the first Muslim coins. 4. Ali ibn Abi Talib strengthened the prophets' and the other caliphs' financial and economic policies.
661 C. E up to 1258 C. E	<p>Umayyad and Abbasid Eras</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The emergence of Islamic dinar and dirham coins 2. Treasury House Developments as the main Bait al-Mal 3. Throughout the Abbasid dynasty, the dinar and dirham continued to be used for trade, and the Treasury House played a significant role.

	4. The goal of founding the House of Wisdom was to advance science, engineering, finance, and new business innovation.
	5. The establishment of the Ijtihad institution aims to modernize Shariah laws.

Source: (Islahi, 2018, pp.404-406)

Trading contracts, participation contracts, and support contracts are the main pillars on which Islamic banking operations depend. Agreements involving participation utilize profit and loss-sharing contracts, while contracts involving trading and supporting use non-profit and loss-exchange contracts (Al Rahahleh et al., 2019, p. 6). Table 1.2 covers the contract types of Islamic financial institutions and banks.

Table 1.2. Existing Islamic Banking Products and Services

Trading Based Contract	Participation Based Contract	Supporting Based Contract
Istisna	Musharakah	Al- Rahn
Ijarah	Mudarabah	Al- Kafalah
Bai- Bithaman Ajil	Profit or Loss Sharing (PLS)	Qard al- Hasan
Bai- Inah	Hiwalah
Murabaha	Tabarruu
Salam- Forward	Hibah
Wadaih	Ibraa
Istisna	Al- Rahn

Source: (Al Rahahleh et al., 2019, p. 6)

1.2.1. Are Islamic Banks Riskier Than Conventional Banks?

Risk is defined by Oldfield and Santo Mero (1970) as the level of uncertainty inherent in a particular business endeavor, such as banking. Therefore, investment banks and commercial banks encounter risk in their regular activities. A good illustration is how interest rate changes affect capital expenditure and profit. According to Cihak and Hesse (2010), risk only quantifies uncertainty, representing the likelihood that an event will impact objectives. The inherent uncertainty of financial gain or loss in regular banking operations, such as deposit taking and lending, might pose a risk. The presence of risk might indicate the potential occurrence of a catastrophic catastrophe for any financial

organization, practically investment banks. Consequently, financial institutions must reliably identify and describe the risks associated with their operations.

Saunders and Cornett (2006) highlighted the hazards associated with credit, interest rates, liquidity, underwriting, and operations. Additional sources have indicated difficulties related to credit, market, and operational issues (Carey et al., 2005, p. 715; Apostolic et al., 2009).

Figure 1.4 indicates the risk profile of investment banks by classifying risk into two distinct categories: systematic risk and unsystematic risk. This paradigm has three unique risk categories: systematic risk, unsystematic risk, and hybrid risk, a blend of the two, including systematic and nonsystematic hazards. This new approach posits that business risk is the only systematic risk. Unsystematic risk includes governance risk, which comprises operational, reputational, and Shariah risks. Financial and Treasury risks are hybrid since they may be defined as systematic or unsystematic hazards.

Financial risk arises from both internal and external sources inside the firm. Credit, market, and equity may be categorized into three types. Therefore, it is unfeasible to classify financial risk as systematic or unsystematic (Al Rahahleh et al., 2009, p. 10).

Islamic banks can only accept current accounts as their primary deposit type. Investment or savings accounts give out returns based on profit rates, whereas non-interest-bearing liabilities force holders to request the principal when desired. The Islamic bank and the holders of investment accounts may adjust the rates according to the distribution of profits and losses. By reducing profit rates during economic downturns and boosting them during economic expansion, the profit-and-loss arrangement can provide pro-cyclical protection to banks in adverse conditions (Iqbal et al., 1998, p. 13). Investment deposits, which serve as a source of funding, may have a significant impact on the Islamic Banks' asset portfolio. In order to meet their obligations to depositors, also known as debtholders, conventional banks put aside a percentage of their funds in liquid assets. To meet their obligations to depositors, they also work to make loan

profits less volatile and unpredictable. Because they are able to treat investment depositors as equity holders, Islamic banks have more flexibility. With limited access to wholesale financing, Islamic banks may find it easier to be as flexible as they would want. Bahrain and Malaysia are home to an emerging Islamic money market to which only large institutions have access due to its restricted nature. The ability of Islamic banks to actively manage their obligations is more limited than that of conventional banks. The success of an Islamic bank and the devoutness of its customers determine the rate of return that customers may expect on their savings. An unknowable outcome might result from this: religious depositors could be more devoted and ready to accept lower returns, showing hesitation or open refusal to withdraw their money regardless of the bank's performance loss. On the other hand, religious depositors may exhibit a greater aversion to risk, thereby increasing their awareness of bank performance and their demand for higher returns. Therefore, Islamic banks should strictly adhere to laws to protect the funds in investment accounts, which might be more at risk than time deposits.

The influence of religious factors on investment account holders, leading to reduced withdrawal risk, may affect the lending practices of Islamic banks. Shifting credit risk to investment account holders in Islamic banks, who lack the rights of equity holders but assume equivalent risk, may diminish their incentive for comprehensive due diligence and lending oversight. In contrast to conventional banks, Islamic banks can be disciplined more effectively via the unique relationship since investment account holders have more motivation to monitor the performance of Islamic banks (Errico & Sundararajan, 2002, P. 20). Under such circumstances, Islamic depositors are inclined to transfer their funds from underperforming banks to others that provide greater returns or maybe even to conventional banks. Consequently, there is a higher likelihood of experiencing withdrawal danger (Khan & Ahmed, 2001, p. 49). This allows depositors to have more control over Islamic financial institutions. If Islamic financial institutions allow investors to share in the actual gain or loss, they may take on more risk. Bank shareholders may need to raise more equity capital to maintain capital ratios and prevent the loss of ownership rights if increased payments to investment account holders result in more substantial deposits. In

contrast, inadequate rewards incentivize the withdrawal of deposits, which can result in liquidity issues and, eventually, solvency concerns.

From a different angle, Islamic banking-related sources highlight that there are risks associated with global Islamic banking. These risks include cybersecurity risk, liquidity risk, rate of return risk, equity investment risk, transactions, process, Business Disruption and Delivery Risk, De-Risking Risk (Closing of Correspondent Banking Relationships), Climate Change Risks, Competences of People Risk, Credit Risk, Foreign Exchange Risk, Sharia Non-Compliance Risk, legal risk, tax risk, reputational risk, Enterprise/Managerial Risk, Technology Risk, and Strategic Risk (CIBAFI, 2023, pp. 42-45).

Fig 1.4. Risks in Islamic Banking

Source: (Al Rahahleh, 2019, p. 10).

These (Consumer attracting, relationship and continuation, macro- economic environment risk management, product supplying and creativity, information technology,

the owner's value and requirements, service effectiveness, human resource and capacity advancement landscape, application of anti-money laundering / combating financial terrorism related localized and abroad rules, business progress and enlargement, adherence, sharia norms, and authority framework, consumer safety, investment chances and competence, capital adequateness, corporate governing, political unpredictability, Islamic financial market structures, legislative support, financial broadening participation, MSME funding, detailed guidelines regarding Islamic finance, boosted management and monitoring, rivalry from other Islamic financial organizations, backwards workplace activities, battles since unique business models, margin pressure, and opposition from orthodox financial institutions) worries may slow or prohibit the advance of Islamic finance industry particularly participation banking. To know or manage these concerns, concerns are specified across the region. The details are shown in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3. Critical Issues Facing Islamic Financial Institutions Worldwide

Countries	Concerns of Islamic Banks
GCC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Managing risks, ➤ the state of the economy as a whole, ➤ and the production and distribution of goods
Southeast Asia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Computer systems ➤ Marketing and production of goods ➤ The governing structure, Islamic law, and compliance
Middle East ex-GCC West Central and South Asia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The landscape of human resources and talent development ➤ The application of local and global rules linked to anti-money laundering and counter-financing of terrorism ➤ Acquiring, maintaining, and satisfying customers ➤ Keeping customers safe ➤ Global economic climate ➤ Computer systems ➤ The ever-changing world of human resources and talent ➤ AML/CFT-related local and worldwide regulatory execution ➤ The state of IT
Europe and Türkiye	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The state of IT ➤ The state of the economy as a whole

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The state of human resources and the landscape for advancing talent ➤ Regulations about Islamic finance
North Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Consumer appeal, relationships, and retention ➤ IT ➤ Managing risks
Sub-Saharan Africa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ The state of the economy as a whole ➤ The worth and expectations of shareholders ➤ The effectiveness of IT ➤ Customer Satisfaction ➤ Activities including the introduction of products and innovation ➤ Financial and monetary tools that provide legal backing
Global	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Consumer appeal, relationships, and retention ➤ IT ➤ Global economic climate ➤ Managing risks ➤ Demonstrating the product and its innovation

Source: (CIBAFI, 2023, p. 54).

Some key differences are shown as follows:

Table 1.4. Differentiation Between Islamic and Conventional Bank

No	Items	Islamic Bank	Conventional Bank
1	Fundamental concept	Principles grounded in Shariah	Grounded on entirely artificial principles
2	Prohibited Components	Not containing any of these components: 1. Riba 2. Gharar 3. Maysir	Not Applicable
3	Distributed Risk Management	Islamic finance promotes a culture of shared risk-taking among investors and business owners.	As promised, the investment would earn interest at a specific rate.
4	Products	Shariah-compliant products	Not Applicable
5	Asset-Backed Financing	Does not specify currency as a commodity for sale.	Banks and financial institutions only make transactions with money and monetary papers.
6	Moral Dimension	Operates by Islamic moral standards, refrains from financing ventures that contradict Islam, and advocates for transparency.	Be more transparent and consider the ethical implications of the projects they fund.

7	Zakat (Religious Tax)	They need to pay zakat, which is obligatory.	Avoid engaging with Zakat.
8	Fine for Noncompliance	There is no extra charge for default payments.	When payments are not made on time, additional interest is assessed.
9	Client Engagement	The bank's status is to its customers as partners, investors, and entrepreneurs.	Establishment of a creditor-debtor relationship between a bank and its clients
10	Shariah Supervisory	Each Islamic bank establishes a necessary Shariah supervisory board to guarantee that the operation complies with Shariah law.	Not Applicable

Source:(Abasimel, 2023, p. 1925).

With a few notable exceptions, the financial statements of investment banks will seem dissimilar to those of commercial banks. The funds maintained in commercial banks typically include cash and other interest-bearing instruments, including Treasury bills. In contrast, the cash held at investment banks is only used for cash-related goods such as fixed assets and shareholder equity. Table 1.4 presents a comprehensive assessment of the many attributes provided by each of the institutions mentioned. Table 1.5 presents the discrepancies in financial statements between commercial and investment banks.

Table 1.5. Comparison of Islamic and Western Bank Financial Statements

Assets of Conventional Banks	Assets of Islamic Banks
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Investments and savings ➤ A variety of loans ➤ Liquid assets, including cash and government bills and notes ➤ Assets, both fixed and otherwise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Money and liquid assets ➤ Accounts receivable (including Murabaha and others) ➤ Assets related to Islamic finance, such as Musharakah, Ijara, Istisna, and Salam ➤ Assets, both fixed and otherwise
Capital and Liabilities of Conventional Banks	Capital and Liabilities of Islamic Banks

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Deposit (in checking and savings accounts) ➤ Promissory notes ➤ Minority interest ➤ Debt and other responsible parties ➤ Equity held by shareholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Accounts receivable (Salam and Istisna payables) ➤ current and savings accounts, ➤ liability and equity ➤ Other obligations, such as zakat and taxes that are due ➤ Return on investment for depositors
--	---

Source:(Al Rahahleh et al., 2019, p. 7)

The financial statements for Islamic Banks (IBs) differ from those of Commercial Banks, with just a few exceptions. For example, fixed assets and shareholder equity, cash in IBs is strictly for cash items only, whereas cash in Commercial Banks (CBs) usually consists of cash and other interest-bearing assets such as treasury bills.

1.2.2. Islamic Capital Markets

The Islamic capital market is a platform where Sharia-compliant financial assets may be traded. Investors are encouraged to search for opportunities that agree with Sharia law, and this strategy is in line with the conventional market. Conversely, a traditional capital market is an intermediary between investors and debtors. Islamic capital market products are built around asset-backed transactions, risk-sharing contracts, and profit-and-loss sharing. Some of the most common methods are commodities trading, equity-based investments, and Islamic bond offers. Many Islamic financial markets exist, including stocks, bonds, currency, and derivatives. Sukuk, or Islamic bonds, comprise 90% of the Islamic capital market, which will be briefly covered in future titles. Many other financial instruments also exist, each fulfilling specific needs (AIMS, 2024).

1.2.3. Nature of Sukuk and Its Development Across the History

A growing number of Muslim and non-Muslim nations see sukuk as a viable alternative to more traditional forms of capital raising. Many nations are contemplating or have already altered their regulations to permit the issuance of sukuk in their financial

markets. Though they are spread globally, these nations have a commonality: they are all African, European, Central Asian, Bruneian, or both. According to Thomson Reuters Zawya (2015), Sukuk is expanding in importance as a prominent Islamic financial tool in both Muslim and non-Muslim nations. One of the most common and effective ways to raise funds on international financial markets is via the sale of Sukuk, which has recently grown in popularity (Zawya, 2015, p. 88).

In February 1988, at the Fourth Session of the Council of the Islamic Fiqh Academy of the Organization of Islamic Conference in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, the issuance of sukuk gained prominence. When Muslim countries needed to raise capital compliant with Shariah law, issuing sukuk emerged as a viable alternative. In May 2003, the groups responsible for auditing and accounting for Islamic financial institutions published the regulations for investing sukuk. According to the standard, sukuk are identically valued certificates representing ownership shares in physical assets, usufructs, or services. Sukuk securities and other innovations in Islamic finance have changed how the Islamic capital market operates. It is well known that sukuk is a good way for Muslims to access funds on international markets. Consequently, sukuk has been used by both public and commercial entities at an alarming rate in the last several years (Kusuma & Silva, 2014, p. 2).

The Arabic term "Sakk" means bonds or securities that adhere to shariah standards, which is where the name sukuk comes from. According to these rules, Islamic issuers and investors are not allowed to engage in traditional securities investments. The Islamic financial instrument known as sukuk, which translates to Islamic Bonds or Investment Certificates, is based on Islamic financing arrangements and securitized leases. Murabaha, Musharakah, and Mudarabah are all types of such agreements (McMillen, 2007, p. 9; Obaidullah, 2007, pp. 194-197; Zulkhibri, 2015, pp. 237-239). The first issuance of sukuk took place in 1990, spearheaded by Shell MDS, a non-Islamic firm for foreign ownership. Subsequently, the sukuk market has thrived, although Islamic financial markets have challenges in achieving full development in most rising Muslim nations because of the

restricted availability of interest rate swaps and other conventional derivatives products in Islamic finance. Continued development and provision of shariah-compliant alternatives to traditional derivatives should be driven by the need to manage sukuk risk and maintain competitiveness (Zulkhibri, 2015, p. 240).

1.2.3.1. Comparison of Sukuk and Bonds

Sukuk enables the funding of commercial activities and investments in a manner that adheres to Shariah principles. Investors generate profit or rental income rather than earning interest. The distinction between bonds and sukuk lies in the distinction between lending with interest and trading or investing for profit. To generate lawful financial gain, investors or sukuk holders must assume accountability for the result of an investment, necessitating the acceptance of risk. There is no assurance of either earnings or money. Assuming responsibility for risk is a valid reason for obtaining profit. Sukuk holders own the securities and the underlying assets that support those securities. The return to sukuk holders is generated by the underlying assets. The productivity or efficiency of the underlying assets directly correlates with the dividend distributed to investors.

In contrast, selling ordinary bonds, which involves borrowing, does not require the transfer of any assets to investors. Investors purchase the bond, which represents a kind of debt. Buyers of collateralized bonds have little or no risk due to the assurance of interest payments and the principal amount. Failure by issuers to make timely payments of the agreed-upon instalments or the loan's principal amount will result in default. Upon default, creditors will have legal entitlement to seize any collateral offered as security for the debts. Therefore, collateralized lending at interest is inherently devoid of risk.

Although default is not considered a criminal offence in most nations, it grants creditors the right to pursue legal measures to retrieve any remaining balance of a loan. They may initiate proceedings to reclaim any assets possessed by debtors. In contracts designed to distribute profit and losses, such as Sukuk, Murabaha, and Musharakah, a default is impossible since these contracts are not based on loans but on agreements to

share earnings and losses. Unlike traditional bond issuers, profit and loss-sharing sukuk issuers are not legally obligated to provide dividends to investors without any profits. Consequently, investors will not be entitled to receive dividends in the event of financial losses. Investors have the potential to receive dividends whenever the underlying assets regain profitability (Abdullah & Terebessy, 2014, pp. 70-80). As in concluding points to be considered for the distinguishing of bonds and sukuk. Maintaining the differentiations between sukuk and bonds is crucial, both in theory and in reality. This difference is significant is how sukuk are designed since adherence to shariah law depends on whether the revenue received from issuers of financial instruments is classified as profit or interest. Sukuk must be structured as profit and loss-sharing instruments to ensure conformity with Shariah. The only way can ensure that investors gain legitimate profit rather than prohibited Riba. To ensure that sukuk represents the sharing of risk, they must be designed without any assurances of income or capital. Such guarantees would nullify the notion of risk sharing in the Sukuk structure.

1.2.3.2. Accounting For Sukuk

In Islam, accounting should serve not just as a service that delivers financial information to consumers and the public, but more significantly, accountants must fulfil their responsibilities by supplying knowledge that allows society to adhere to God's commands. According to Islamic accountability principles, management and capital providers are internally and externally accountable for their activities via accurate reporting and accounting. This means that Islamic views on societal accountability differ significantly from Western ones, which tend to focus on individual responsibility. All investments made by the institution, whether in sukuk (Islamic bonds), stocks, or tangible assets, are subject to the AAOIFI financial accounting standard No. 17. Since the standard is still in its infancy, it will only apply to fiscal years that start on January 1, 2003. Consequently, institutions which holdings in Islamic capital market products are most impacted by the need to address this criterion. Accurately recording complex instruments like Islamic bonds or Sukuk needs further scholarly work.

Investments in sukuk are subject to additional disclosure obligations imposed by AAOIFI's FAS 17. The issuer of sukuk is required to provide important information such as the face value of the sukuk, the proportion of sukuk purchased from each issuing party, and the kind of sukuk. It is also necessary to reveal who guarantees the sukuk and what kind of guarantee it is. The need to disclose the nature of the contractual connection between sukuk issuers, managers, and sukuk holders is another helpful disclosure requirement. The need to reveal the categorization of sukuk based on their maturities is the extra disclosure about sukuk investment. Islamic institutions should be more open about sharing financial details about their investments in assets, particularly sukuk, in light of all disclosures mentioned in earlier rules. The basic idea is to let people make educated decisions, particularly about the securities institutions invest in, by giving them access to relevant information. To meet the sharia requirements, users are expected to demand all the information mentioned above and disclosure, including details about the parties involved in contractual relationships and the risks and the potential returns of investments (Ahmed, 2011, p. 3).

1.2.4. Takaful

The Islamic view on mainstream insurance was deliberated at the 1965 Cairo Congress of Islamic Research. After eleven years, the first International Conference on Islamic Economics finally took place in Makkah, Saudi Arabia, in 1976. Almost two hundred Islamic economists and jurists were present at this significant gathering, and they all came to the same conclusion. Conventional insurance of any kind is illegal since it goes against the Sharia. In a 1985 meeting in Jeddah, the organization of Islamic Corporations (OIC) ratified this resolution, stating: Commercial insurance policies offered by modern insurance firms with periodic fixed premiums violate Sharia law and are null and invalid. Due to its ethical foundation in mutual help and cooperation for the sake of society, the OIC permitted the Takaful scheme—also called mutual insurance—to replace the insurance system (Nazarov & Dhiraj, 2019, p. 283).

In 1979, Sudan implemented the first takaful insurance. The rising demand for Sharia-compliant insurance among Muslims boosted the business. Using the terms of the Company's Act 1925, the Sharia board of Sudan's Faisal Islamic Bank issued a fatwa on the takaful plan, which led the bank to form the first takaful company. The firm later became publicly listed. As a result, takaful has spread to many parts of the Islamic world. Malaysia established the first takaful legislation in 1984 and incorporated the corporation as a limited liability company. Regardless of their Muslim allegiance, takaful operators may be found in many nations nowadays (Obaidullah, 2005, p. 196; Fadun, 2015, p. 12).

1.2.4.1. Islamic Insurance vs Traditional Insurance

When danger, hazard, or tragedy strikes, the members of any insurance plan should not have to worry about paying out of pocket. Despite this, traditional insurance and Takaful plans are different. To protect each other from potential losses or disasters, the Takaful system is based on the principle of mutual aid, solidarity, and indemnification. All parties involved commit to helping each other financially and overcoming the specified occurrence. The takaful operator oversees the management and investment of the funds collectively given funds, which are then used to reward the participants (Aziz, 2012, p. 63).

In a traditional insurance policy, the policyholder hands over responsibility for any losses to the insurance provider. Islamic law forbids certain aspects of traditional insurance policies, contradicting its fundamental principles rather than serving as an insurer. The Takaful company's primary responsibility is the management and investment of donated money. There is miscommunication between the operator and the participants over the purchase of risk coverage. In contrast to traditional insurance, the Takaful operator does not exchange the risk of paying out claims to participants for the money. Instead, the members share the risk. Conventional insurance, on the other hand, plays the role of the insurer and is designed on risk assumption; however, the amount it pays out may be lower or more than the property's actual worth (Şimşek & Pekkırızlı, 2021, p.

8). Table 1.6 summarizes the differentiation between Islamic and conventional insurance based on essential categories.

Table 1.6. Differentiation of Islamic and Non-Islamic Insurances

Categories	Islamic Insurance	Conventional Insurance
Contract Type	A hybrid agreement includes tabarru, agency, and profit-sharing terms.	Commercial agreement between an insurance company and its policyholders.
The Responsibility of the Operator/Insurer	It is beneficial for the takaful operator as well, as they are also in charge of the takaful money. If there isn't enough money, the takaful operator needs to provide interest-free loans (qard al-hasan).	The insurance company must use the money in the insurance and the shareholders' funds to pay the promised benefits.
The Obligation of Participants/Policyholders	Anyone who wants to be a part of the system must put money in, and if there is more than enough, everyone should split it.	The policyholder is responsible for paying the premium to the insurance company.
The Operator's or Insurer's Return	The takaful operator receives a mudarib remuneration from the Mudarabah profit-sharing plan and an agency fee from the wakalah contract in exchange for their services in handling the takaful money.	When there is a surplus in underwriting, the insurance company gets to pocket the money.
Counter Value	The effort and taking of risk are known as counter-value	Without any clear or legitimate counter-value, The profit comes from anticipating that the future will be favorable to them.
Investment Fund	Investing takaful funds in products that comply with Sharia law is mandatory.	You may invest as much money as you like.
Policyholder-Insurer Dynamic	A connection between an insurer and an insured party does not exist between the takaful operator and the participants. Everyone takes on the roles of policyholder and insurer at the same time.	The link between insurers and insureds is obvious.
Protection Feature	The foundation of the indemnification component is the principle of mutual contribution and participation.	Indemnification refers to the business connection between the insured and the insurance provider.

Source: (Nazarov & Dhiraj, 2019, pp. 294-295).

1.2.4.2. Types of Takaful

General Takaful and Family Takaful are the two most fundamental categories of takaful.

1.2.4.2.1. General Takaful

In the case of a significant loss or damage, general takaful policies are designed to meet the insurance needs of both people and companies. Implementing the Musharakah, Mudarabah, and Wakalah models is possible using this method. Homes, automobiles, and buildings are mostly protected, along with all other tangible assets. The following categories make up general takaful products, which provide coverage for non-life risks (AIMS, 2024):

- **Property:** If there is damage to your property due to a fire, lightning, or explosion, this coverage will pay you. Buildings, inventory, equipment, and similar items are also included.
- **Marine:** It covers damages or losses to goods on ships, planes, or highways.
- **Automobile:** This policy covers repairs to your car that may be necessary after an accident.
- **Miscellaneous:** This policy is customized to meet the business's specific needs.

1.2.4.2.2. Family Takaful

When family members enter a taburru contract, they commit to regularly contributing non-zakat items to the Waqf fund. Islamic insurance covers all potential risks to human life, such as demise, illness, and financial obligations, both now and in the future (AIMS, 2024).

1.2.4.2.3. Islamic Insurance Options For Families

- **Term life:** This kind of insurance only pays out the amount insured if the insured person dies within the stipulated time frame.
- **Whole life:** Theoretically, this policy will cover the insured for the rest of their lives, and the premium remains constant.

- Endowment: Endowment benefits are provided at retirement. Alternatively, in case of an earlier death of the insuree, they are paid to the dependents.
- Universal: It accommodates the insuree's evolving demands and goals while providing lifelong financial stability.
- Marriage plan: The purpose of a marriage plan is to meet the requirements of parents planning a marriage for their children.
- Educational plan: It focuses on providing for a child's educational expenses in the future (AIMS, 2024).

1.2.4.3. Takaful Business Models

Takaful has four types of business models, as follows (Marifa Academy, 2021):

- Mudaraba model
- Wakala model
- Hybrid or (Mudaraba+ Wakala) model
- Waqf model

In the mudaraba model, participants contribute to the takaful fund, and the manager manages the takaful fund into the special participant account and participant account. The relation between the participant and takaful fund, takaful fund, and operator of takaful is based on a mudaraba agreement where, in cases of profit, the profit will be shared between parties on the pre-agreed agreement, while in cases of loss, the participant or takaful holder will be responsible. The manager uses this takaful fund for the claim of the participants and invests in Sharia businesses for further earnings.

PSA= Total contribution of takaful participants- participant claims- total operation expenses= Profit/Loss

PA= Total investment amount- total operation cost = Profit/Loss

In both cases (Participants Special Account, Participant Account), if the profit is earned, this profit will be shared based on the mudaraba contract between Rabul Mal and Mudarib. In the case of a loss, the participants or takaful holders will be responsible. In the wakala and waqf models, the process is the same as in the mudaraba model; the difference is that the wakala model operator is the agent of the participant and receives the specific fee from the takaful fund, while in the waqf model, the relationship between parties is based on waqf. The profit will not go to takaful participants; the profit will go to the waqf fund and be reinvested for more earnings. In the hybrid model, the relationship between the parties is based on waqf and mudarba. Then, all the business processing is the same as other business takaful models. Figures show the summarized form of the Takaful business models.

Fig 1.5. Mudaraba Model

Source: (Marifa Academy, 2021)

In the Mudarabah model, the manager of the takaful fund manages the fund through two accounts (participant account and participant special account). If the fund makes a profit, it will be shared based on Mudarabah's pre-agreement between the participants, while if it makes a loss, the participant will be responsible.

Fig 1.6. Wakala Model

Source: (Marifa Academy, 2021)

In the Wakala model, the manager of the takaful fund manages the fund through two accounts (participant account and participant special account). The manager acts as an agent based on the fee where the agreement is made before the operation of the takaful fund.

Fig 1.7. Hybrid Model

Source: (Marifa Academy, 2021)

In the hybrid model of takaful, the relationship between participants is based on Wakala and Mudarabah. The managers could be agents who receive a fee for managing the takaful fund or agents who do not receive a fee.

Fig 1.8. Waqf Model

Source: (Marifa Academy, 2021)

In the Waqf model, the manager of the takaful fund manages the fund through two accounts (participant account and participant special account). If the fund makes a profit, it is not shared between the participants; the profit is reinvested for further earnings.

1.2.4.4. Accounting For Takaful

Takaful oversees and controls three distinct financial assets:

1. Family takaful fund
2. General takaful fund
3. Shareholder's fund

Interim and annual financial statements are generated for each category.

1.2.4.4.1. Accounting For Family Takaful

In family takaful, money comes in two ways: installment income, which is recorded when the money is collected or when it becomes effective, and investment income, which is recorded in cash. Bear in mind that the Balance Sheet treats all advance revenues as liabilities (Billah & Basodan, 2017, p. 14).

Expenses of family takaful are combined from refund contribution, death claims, re-takaful, depreciation, part withdrawal, maturity of the certificate, and certificate of surrender.

- All transactions are recorded on an accrual-based approach:
 - ✓ All transactions are recorded in an entry accounting system
 - ✓ A specified account date and the kind of company are used to enter all transactions into the general ledger.
 - ✓ Each participant has a particular account where they may record their mortgage and family installment payments.
 - ✓ The financial accounts also note the collected payments under the New Business and Renewal categories.
- Profit distribution

The fiscal or financial year should be used to create the takaful family's financial statement. Here are the most common kinds of revenue statements:

- ✓ In the distribution of profits and insurance activities in Malaysia, the proportion of participants to shareholders in family plans is 70:30 regarding investment returns. However, participants and shareholders split the excess in Saudi Arabia at 10:90.

- Trial balance
- Statement of family takaful operations and accumulated surplus of it
- Movement of fund
- Statement of group family towards operation and accumulated surplus
- Revenue account

1.2.4.4.2. Accounting for General Takaful Operations

- General ledger- the fund is managed under its general ledger. The subsidiary and records support this ledger (Billah & Basodan, 2017, p. 15):
 - ✓ Cashbook
 - ✓ Daily collection
 - ✓ Fixed asset register
 - ✓ Bank reconciliation
 - ✓ Investment listing
 - ✓ Re takaful register
- Typically, takaful income can be categorized into two forms: installment income, which is recognized upon collection or effective date, and refund contribution, which is paid out in cash and should be shown separately in the financial statement. Investment income is also paid out in cash, but remember that all advance receipts are considered liabilities in the balance sheet.

- Expenses of general takaful are combined from refund contribution, re-takaful outwards, claims admitted and paid, and Levy.
- The general ledger updates all company transactions via the double-entry system. The general ledger is organized according to the kind of company and account code for each transaction. A class of business information is also maintained for Islamic insurance (takaful), including fire, motor, miscellaneous, engineering, marine, and aviation.
- The general Islamic insurance company's earnings come from it is underwriting surplus, and the returns on investments are takaful funds.
- The general takaful fund's financial statements are produced following the conclusion of the financial year.
- Here are the several kinds of statements that may be found in Malaysia:
 - ✓ Trial balance
 - ✓ Profit and loss account
 - ✓ Revenue account
- International accounting standards produce statements in Saudi Arabia in the following ways:
 - ✓ Statement of financial position
 - ✓ Statement of insurance operations and accumulated surplus
 - ✓ Statement of insurance operations cash flows

1.2.4.4.3. Accounting For Shareholders Funds

- The general ledger keeps track of the shareholder's money independently of the takaful funds (Billah & Basodan, 2017, p. 16). Schedules and subsidiary ledgers back up all general ledgers, which consist of the following:
 - ✓ Cashbook

- ✓ Fixed asset register
 - ✓ Financing schedule
 - ✓ Investment Schedule
 - ✓ Register of shareholders fund
 - ✓ Bank reconciliation statement
- The sources of income for the shareholders fund are:
- ✓ The general ledger is updated monthly to reflect investment returns, namely the earnings from the family's Islamic insurance
 - ✓ The general ledger is updated monthly to reflect the share of earnings from the family's takaful fund.
- Three primary operational costs go into the shareholder's fund:
- ✓ Staff cost
 - ✓ Initial investment
 - ✓ Operational cost
- The accrual basis is used to account for the costs that were discussed before.
- ✓ The transaction entry system involves recording all company transactions using a double-entry technique. Financial transactions are entered into a general ledger, depending on the nature of the company and the account code.
 - ✓ As of the conclusion of each fiscal year, the following reports comprise the shareholder's funds financial statements:
 - ✓ Trial balance
 - ✓ Profit and loss account

- The international accounting standards in Saudi Arabia create the financial statements in this manner:
 - ✓ Statement of financial position
 - ✓ Statement of shareholders' comprehensive income
 - ✓ Statement of changes in shareholders' equity
 - ✓ Statement of shareholders' operations
 - ✓ Statement of shareholders' operations cash flows

1.2.5. Modes of Islamic Finance

The Islamic economic and financial paradigm lists mutual and shared benefits instead of the traditional interest-based approach that lines up individual welfare and disregards cooperative welfare. The Islamic economic structure differs from the modern capitalist model, prioritizing unbridled resource production and consumption over distribution and individual material interests.

Islamic financial instruments, including Musharakah, Mudarabah, Murabaha, Ijarah, Salam, and Istisna, facilitate risk sharing, a fundamental principle in Islamic finance. These resources, which draw on the Holy Quran and Sunnah of the Prophet (SAW), are designed to facilitate social commerce and business, leading to economic success and well-being (Ali, 2014, p. 1).

All kinds of trade contracts are permitted in Islam, based on Islamic law; Islamic finance can be categorized under four main headings (Partnership Model, Trade Model, Supported Application Model, and Other Financing Model) categories, and each heading is subdivided into different models of the Islamic finance. As fig 1.9 summarized:

Fig 1.9. Models of Islamic Financing

Source: (Dilber, 2022, p. 20)

1.2.5.1. Murabaha

In Arabic, Murabaha signifies profit or growth and is a derivative of the term riba. In technical terms, Murabaha refers to the practice of selling a product or service at a price that includes both the initial investment and any subsequent profit (Dar & Akram, 2013, p. 130).

Fig 1.10. Financing Based on Murabaha

Source: (Yanpar, 2015, p.154)

First, the client contacts the vendor and requests the necessary supplies. In order to go on with the supplier transaction, the client will appoint the bank as their agent. The bank will pay the vendor for the specified items on the client's behalf. Last but not least, the bank will charge more for the items to make a profit.

1.2.5.2. Mudarabah

In mudrabah, at least two different kinds of partners join for ongoing the business, in which Rabb-ul-mall or an investor supplies the initial funding for investment. At the same time, the mail or mudarib oversees daily operations and strategic planning (Aziz et al., 2013, p. 1238; Rahman, 2018, p. 34).

Investors and mudarib will share in the business's profits according to the ratio agreed upon at the beginning of the mudraba contract. If the business gets the damage due to any cause, the investor of the business would be responsible for the whole loss. Figure 1.11 below was taken to understand the mudarabh agreement better.

Fig 1.11. Financing Based on Mudaraba

Source: (Yanpar, 2015, p. 141)

1.2.5.3. Musharakah

In a musharakah, all parties involved put up money and work together to make a profit. Losses are proportional to the amount of capital contributed, while profits are split according to agreed-upon ratios. The conventional connection between a moneylender and borrower differs from the foundation of the musharakah financing model, which provides an alternate interaction between entrepreneurs. Musharakah does not demand a collateral guarantee since both partners are invested in the business with their cash and expertise. It eliminates the burden of debt and other obligations. It does not create a huge burden or require payments to offset damages (Ali & Hussain, 2017, p. 42; Farooq & Ahmed, 2013, p. 182; Iqbal et al., 2014, p. 76). Fig 1.12 shows the practical application of the musharakah financing model.

Fig 1.12. Musharakah Based Financing

Source: (Yanpar, 2015, p. 145)

1.2.5.4. Muzare and Musakat

These concepts are used in agricultural partnerships and are mainly used in agriculture. In Muzare agreements, one party allocates its land for agricultural activities while the other party uses it for labour and knowledge. In this agreement, the landowner uses his land for agricultural activities, provided that he receives a particular portion of the product. Another agricultural partnership model is Musakat, which, in the dictionary, means to give water to an animal or plant. It is a partnership model between the owner of the orchard or vineyard and the person who will work to share the product at a specific rate. Any fruit tree subject to Musakat should be of a type that can last more than a year (Dilber, 2022, p. 23).

1.2.5.5. Salam

Salam is multipurpose and may help all social classes of farmers, artisans, and traders- especially the underprivileged or those with little to no money; however, in Islamic banking, salam finance may be extended to legal entities and individuals. An Islamic bank may finance a farmer's product by analyzing its credibility and agreeing to provide the sale price for financing the production. Prices, quantities, quality, and delivery dates will all be worked out in a salam agreement with the bank. The transaction is finalized when the bank immediately pays the total purchase amount in cash. Once the farmer has delivered the goods, the salam contract is complete. After that, the bank makes a profit by selling the items to prospective customers at a separate price called the margin. On the other hand, extra expenses may arise if the bank cannot sell the items or if they need storage. There could not be somewhere to keep the products, or they might be perishable and spoil if left unattended. A special salam has been developed to protect against the possibility of not finding a buyer and all the hazards that come with it. In a parallel salam, an Islamic bank would strike a second selling deal with a buyer via WA'AD after completing a salam contract with a farmer, as seen below. WA'AD means the buyer is ready and eager to buy the goods when the farmer brings them to the bank. The bank avoids potential losses by parallel salam, resulting in eliminating the need for storage for the merchandise and immediately selling to a third contracted party without any storage costs (Al Zaabi, 2010, pp. 91-92; Kurniawansyah & Agustia, 2017, p. 2; Muneeza & Mustapha, 2020, p. 310).

Fig 1.13. Istisna Based Financing

Source: (Nasucha et al., 2019, p. 262)

Fig 1.14. Salam Based Financing

Source:(Muneeza & Mustapha, 2020, p. 312)

1.2.5.6. Istisna

An istisna, derived from the Arabic word sina'a, is a commercial arrangement wherein one party sells another an item that has not yet been manufactured or assembled as per the agreement's specifications. Delivery date and pricing are determined prior to contract signing. It is illegal for a vendor to sell an item that is not physically in their possession at the time of sale. In a standard Istisna, one party pays the other, and the seller agrees to deliver the products at the agreed-upon time (Habib, 2018, p. 155; Nasucha et al., 2019, p. 262). Fig 1.15 Illustrates the transactional relationship between the two in a simple Istisna.

However, according to modern Islamic banking, banks do not deal with purchasing and selling things; rather, they finance businesses that produce goods or provide services.

The parties to one Istisna contract may engage in a parallel Istisna contract with terms that are very close to, or even the same as, the terms of the original contract. The buyer and the bank enter into separate Istisna contracts, and the same is true for the bank and the builder. Islamic financiers facilitate the funding of construction projects by having the client and the contractor sign two Istisna contracts simultaneously. The connections between the parties to the contract are shown in Fig 1.15.

Fig 1.15. Parallel Istisna

Source: (Nasucha et al., 2019, p. 262).

Depending on what the agreement specifies, the buyer or consumer pays the bank, and the bank pays the builder. The builder subsequently fulfils the bank's order by delivering the finished product per the payback timeline. Contract payback terms may be flexible and agreed upon by the parties involved; payment can be provided in advance, in instalments during construction, upon completion, or after the project is finished. The final product specs are identical in both contracts, but the price and payment choices differ. This is due to the price difference, which the bank uses to represent its profit when financing a building project. Note that the two contracts are distinct and that the bank can not use the loss of one contract to affect the other. If the builder fails to deliver the asset on schedule, the bank might incur financial damages according to the structure of the Istisna contract.

Without buyer collateral and builder warranties, the bank faces a substantial risk of default from both the buyer and builder (Akkizidis & Khandelwal, 2008, p. 63; Hasmawati & Mohamad, 2019, p. 213).

1.2.5.7. Ijara

Islamic financial institutions offer several leasing arrangements. One of them is the Ijara, whereby one party, the lessor, transfers ownership of an object to another, the lessee, who agrees to pay rent to the lessor, the renter, for a certain period. As shown in Fig 1.16, the process begins with the bank paying the supplier for the asset, followed by the bank transferring ownership of the item to the client and collecting rent from the customer (Haron & Nursofiza Wan Azmi, 2009, p. 136 ; Noman et al., 2022, p. 3163 ; Yusuf & Isa, 2021, p. 50).

Fig 1.16. Ijara Based Financing

Source: (Noman et al., 2022, p. 3165).

1.2.5.8. Tawarruq

The term tawarruq originates from the word wariq, signifying minted or coined silver. Tawarruq is a sequence of successive sale agreements in which an individual acquires a product from a seller on credit and then sells it to a third party for cash to achieve liquidity. For instance, Fig 1.17 shows that the buyer purchases the goods from the seller [1] on a debt basis; the purchaser will be the seller of the same product as he/she purchased earlier on a third-party buyer to maintain the required cash (Ajija et al., 2010, p. 2 ; Ali & Hassan, 2020, p. 152).

Fig 1.17. Tawarruq

Source: (Ajija et al., 2010, p. 5)

1.2.5.9. Bai Al Wafa

The term bai al-wafa refers to a transaction in which the buyer and seller agree that the seller can repurchase the things they sold after a specific grace time has passed. Fig 1.18 shows that, in the first stage, the assets are sold to the buyer; after a specific agreed-upon time in the second stage, the seller will repurchase the asset that was sold in the first stage (Shoimah et al, 2021, p. 3; Asa'ari, 2013, p. 3).

Fig 1.18. Bai Al Wafa

Source: (Shoimah et al, 2021, p. 5)

1.2.3.3. Sukuk and Its Types

Sukuk is the plural form of the traditional Arabic word “Saak” when discussing terminology. Legal documents, known as Sakk, serve as evidence of commitments that adhere to Islamic law, also known as Shariah. In Islamic finance, sukuk as a security representing ownership of an asset is defined by the Islamic Financial Service Board (2009). A certificate of Islamic investment comprises both a claim on the asset's ownership and a claim on the cash flows or revenue that the asset produces. Sukuk holders share in the profits and risks of the company rather than getting a fixed interest rate. Islamic financial theory has centered on three main points: Islamic capital markets, Islamic insurance (Takaful), and Islamic banking. Sukuk, a significant financial instrument that accounts for about 90% of the market, dominates the Islamic capital market. While fourteen different kinds of sukuk exist, the seven most well-known and open-issued varieties are Murabaha, Ijara, Salam, Istisna, Mudaraba and Hybrid. Based on the features of the Sukuk, special-purpose vehicles supervise and manage all sukuk transactions; they also function as trustees and issue the sukuk. Each sukuk is designed to meet specific financial demands, and the principles of Islamic finance guide its construction (Haider & Azhar, 2011, p. 21).

Sukuk has a much shorter history than bonds. Malaysia issued its first sovereign sukuk in 1995. Malaysia has maintained its prominence in the Islamic capital market ever since. According to Ernst and Young, there are three distinct stages to the creation of Sukuk. Known as the Birth of Sukuk, the first phase began in 1996 and ended in 2001. During this time, concerns were mild. The largest number and quantity of Sukuk issuance occurred between 2002 and 2007. Since 2007, the sukuk market has been experiencing a downturn due to the global financial crisis and challenges related to Sharia compliance (Al-Sayed, 2013, pp. 67-68).

According to the theories, sukuk, conventional bonds, and shares are fundamentally different. Among the many distinctions between the three instruments, sukuk stands out as an improvement over traditional bonds due to its foundation in tangible, traceable economic transactions supported by actual assets or services; this, in turn, promotes long-term financial stability and societal well-being. The Sukuk structure's risk-sharing component ensures a fair and reasonable distribution of wealth throughout society (Nanaeva, 2010, pp. 10-11).

1.2.3.3.1. Sukuk Al-Modaraba

These certifications represent projects or activities handled under a modaraba (trust-based partnership) contract. The project manager is one of the partners or parties involved, and they are termed the Muda Rib. An additional partner known as rubble-mal, or the owner of capital, provides funding for the project alongside the Muda Rib. The managing partner, or Muda Rib, is the one issuing these certificates; the capital owners, or subscribers, are the ones putting up the money or modaraba capital. As agreed upon in the agreement, the certificate holders will own Modaraba's assets and participate in the earnings. In the event of a loss, they are also the ones to shoulder the financial burden. Fig. 2 shows the application of sukuk al modaraba, where, first, investors give the funds to the SPVs and hold the sukuk. Besides this, the SPVs and the company signed a contract with Modaraba, in which the SPVs provided the capital, and the company managed Modaraba's project. In the case of a loss, the SPVs will be responsible, while the profit

will be distributed based on Modaraba's agreement. Lastly, the specific proportionate of the profit for SPVs will be distributed to the investors based on the invested capital (El shazly & Tripathy, 2013, p. 7).

Fig 1.19. Sukuk Al Modaraba

Source: (Marifa Academy, 2015b).

1.2.3.3.2. Sukuk Al Ijara

An Ijara contract is a rental or lease agreement that details the duration and location of an item's use in return for payment. When they lease out an Ijara sukuk, the sukuk holders really own the asset. The ownership, rent collection, and disposition rights granted to the owners by an ijara sukuk do not impact on the lessee's entitlement, making these sukuk marketable. To comply with Ijara, the parties must specify the leased asset and rent in detail when the contract is issued. A transparent and condition-specific rental charge is required. While the owner is liable for the original outlay, the renter is responsible for maintenance costs. Fig 1.20 shows the application of sukuk al Ijara, where investors invest

in SPVs, hold the Sukuk, and pay SPVs; after that, the SPVs will make a contract to buy the asset and give it rewards to the company. In the case of purchasing, SPVs will be the owners of the asset, giving the same asset to the company and receiving the rent. SPVs will act as trustees for the investor and distribute the profit to the investor (Zulkhibri, 2015, p. 240).

Fig 1.20. Sukuk Al Ijara

Source: (Marifa Academy, 2015b)

1.2.3.3.3. Sukuk Al Musharakah

Before Islam came into the picture, there was a profit and sharing system known as Musharakah. Joint ventures include two or more people coming together under a written agreement to share the gains and losses of the business endeavor. The partners agree on a share of the profits. For Sharia law to recognize Musharakah, the contract must have been made with all parties' full knowledge and agreement, without any deceit or deception.

Each partner must put up money at a predetermined value, and the ownership of the venture's assets is proportional to the capital. Ideally, every partner is an active manager, but if there is any opt-out, the profit-to-share ratio cannot be higher than the initial investment. Any condition that contradicts this will cause the contract to be void since the loss is subject to the investment ratio. Figure 1.21 shows the application of sukuk al Musharakah, where first, the investors invest the money or funds in SPVs, and SPVs issue the sukuk. SPVs and the company have made a contract with Musharakah to perform Musharakah's business. In this business, the SPVs provide the capital while the company provides the physical asset, and both sides, in the case of profit, receive the profit based upon the agreed agreement. Then, the SPVs will distribute the profit to the investors based on the capital ratio. In the case of a loss, both parties will be equally responsible, and at the end of the Musharakah business, the asset will be sold on business by SPVs based on pre-agreement (Razak et al., 2019, pp. 24-25).

Fig 1.21. Sukuk Al Musharakah

Source: (Marifa Academy, 2015)

1.2.3.3.4. Sukuk Al Murabaha

In Sukuk al Murabaha, investors invest or provide funds to SPVs for the holding of Sukuk. In the letter, SPVs will purchase Islamic sharia commodities from a broker [1] and sell them to the company; the company will pay the (price+ profit) to SPVs on an agreed instalment basis. If the company has a liquidity problem, the company will sell the products to a broker [2] to pay the obligation of SPVs. When SPVs receive the profit, then it will be distributed between investors based on the capital ratio that they invested (Marifa Academy, 2015).

Fig 1.22. Sukuk Al Murabaha

Source: (Marifa Academy, 2015).

1.2.3.3.5. Salam Sukuk

The salami price is paid in full at the spot price, and the buyer agrees to receive an item's specified quantity and quality at a future date. It is possible to raise funds for Salam by issuing certificates of equivalent value, known as sukuk al-Salam, allowing holders to own the commodities that will eventually be provided via Salam. Certificate issuers are sellers of Salam commodities, subscribers are purchasers of those goods, and the subscription funds represent the purchase price of those items. Certificate holders have

the right to the selling price of their certificates or, if applicable, the sale price of the items sold via a parallel Salam, as they are the proprietors of the Salam. An SPV may issue securities based on the Salam principle, whereby the investor's money is given to the SPVs in advance in exchange for a commitment to supply a commodity at a later date. SPVs may also designate a third party to sell the pledged amount upon delivery at a premium. Sukuk holders and SPVs both benefit from the difference between the purchase and selling prices. Fig 1.23 shows the application process of the Salam Sukuk precisely (Dar, 2006, p. 15).

Fig 1.23. Salam Sukuk

Source: (Dar, 2006, p. 16)

1.2.3.3.6. Sukuk Istisna

Large infrastructure projects may benefit significantly from Istisna sukuk finance. The purpose of issuing sukuk al Istisna certificates of equal value is to raise the necessary finances for producing goods that the certificate holders would possess. The manufacturer,

supplier, or seller issuing the certificates is known as the issuer. The subscribers are the people who want to purchase the goods, and the money that is made from the subscription is equal to the product's cost. In the event of a sale, the holders of the certificates have the right to either the total purchase price of the product or the purchase price of the certificates based on a parallel Istisna, whichever is greater. Figure 1.24 shows the application of sukuk al Istisna, where investors hold the sukuk and provide funds to SPVs so that SPVs can make an Istisna contract with the contractor based on a specific date. The contractor will supply the promised goods, and the SPVs will pay. After receiving the goods, the SPVs will sell or lease them to the buyers and receive the instalment. Ultimately, the profit will be distributed to investors based on a capital ratio (Sa'ad et al., 2016, pp. 233-237).

Fig 1.24. Sukuk Al Istisna

Source: (Dar, 2006, pp. 28-29)

1.2.5.10. Qard al Hasan

In a beneficent loan, also known as Qard Hassan, the borrower must return only the principal amount and not any extra costs. This kind of loan is only made accessible in rare instances (Dilber, 2022, p. 31).

1.2.6. International Organization For Islamic Finance

Several international organizations have been established to promote Islamic finance globally, particularly in Islamic nations. The following organizations, academies, research institutions, and cooperatives are investigated:

1.2.6.1. Accounting and Audit Organization For Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI)

AAOIFI, founded in 1991 and located in Bahrain, is the leading international body in charge of developing and spreading Islamic financial industry standards. It deals with shariah, accounting, auditing, ethics, and governance and has set one hundred standards for use in global Islamic banking. It has the backing of several institutional members from over 45 countries, including regulatory agencies, law firms, accounting and auditing firms, and financial institutions. The guidelines of the Islamic Financial Institutions are now followed by all countries worldwide, resulting in a gradual standardization of Islamic finance practices worldwide (AAOIFI, 2023).

1.2.6.2. International Financial Service Board

The Islamic Financial Service Board was formally inaugurated in November 2002 and began operations in Kuala Lumpur on March 10, 2003. This organization is dedicated to establishing and maintaining high standards for the Islamic financial service sector, encompassing banking, capital markets, and insurance. The International Financial Service Board is an international organization aiming to advance Islamic financial services responsibly and openly by developing and advocating for new international standards that align with Sharia principles (IFSB, 2023).

1.2.6.3. Islamic Development Bank

The Islamic Development Bank was founded in 1975 in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, as stated by Çürük (2013). The Islamic Development Bank (IsDB) provides economic and social support to the 57 member states and Muslim populations outside those nations. Over time, the Islamic development banks have grown into a consortium of five distinct entities (IsDB, 2024):

IsDB-1975

As a multilateral development bank, it aims to enhance individuals' lives by promoting economic and social development.

IsDBI-1981

The Islamic Development Bank Institute is responsible for creating and sharing knowledge in Islamic economics and finance.

ICIEC-1994

Countries that follow Islamic law can obtain insurance for investment and export credit through the Islamic Corporation for the Insurance of Investment and Export Credit.

ICD-1999

The Islamic Corporation for the Development of the Private Sector backs private-sector projects to assist member states in progressing economically.

ISFD-2007

The Islamic Solidarity Fund for Development offers financial aid in the form of grants and loans to alleviate poverty and empower the underprivileged.

ITFC-2008

The mission of the International Islamic Trade Finance Corporation is to encourage the growth of commerce among the member states of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC).

1.2.6.4. SESRIC

A subsidiary organ of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), the Statistical, Economic, and Social Research and Training Center for Islamic Countries (SESRIC) was established in May 1977 in Tripoli by resolution no. 2/8-E, passed by the 8th Islamic Conference of Foreign Ministers (ICFM). This group's mission is threefold:

1. Collecting, analyzing, and disseminating social and economic data from member nations
2. Study and assess member countries' economic and social developments to develop ideas to encourage and improve cooperation among them.
3. To organize training programs in specific fields tailored to member countries' needs and the OIC's overall goals.

1.2.6.5. International Islamic Rating Agency

The Islamic International Rating Agency (IIRA) provides independent evaluations to ensure that issuers and issues adhere to Islamic financial standards. With its ratings, the International Islamic Rating Agency hopes to help local capital markets grow, especially in the OIC region and spread ethical finance worldwide. IsDB established IIRA to promote Islamic finance, an infrastructure organization similar to AAOIFI and IFSB. With a nomination on the board of directors, IsDB maintains its status as a key stakeholder. With it is headquartered in Bahrain, IIRA began operation in 2005 and introduced a suite of conceptually unique approaches in 2011. According to IIRA, Islamic finance's strength is its equity emphasis. This makes executing a transaction just as crucial as the transaction

itself. By adding the distinctive characteristics of Islamic finance and a particular emphasis on corporate governance and Sharia compliance, IIRA enhances the rating process and provides a broader view of quality. Gharar must not be present in any Islamic transaction to be considered legitimate. These ratings record economies while making markets more transparent and reducing information asymmetry. Grading would allow for more equitable trade by improving the quality of investment decisions (IIRA, 2021).

1.2.6.6. Islamic Research and Training Institution

Developed Islamic financial products, research, training, information, advisory, and technical assistance are all part of the Islamic Research and Training Institute's (IRTI) role as the principal organizational unit responsible for providing Islamic finance services to the Islamic Development Bank Group and its member countries (IsDBI, 2024).

1.2.6.7. International Islamic Financial Market

The International Islamic Financial Market (IIFM) standardizes Sharia-compliant financial transactions and product verifications. By Royal Decree No. 23 of the Kingdom of Bahrain, the IIFM is an independent, non-profit organization that develops Islamic infrastructure globally (IIFM, 2022).

1.2.6.8. International Islamic Liquidity Management Corporation (IILM)

Central banks and multilateral organizations established the International Islamic Liquidity Management Corporation (IILM) in 2010 to develop and market Sharia-compliant financial instruments to enable efficient Islamic liquidity management across international borders (IILM, 2021).

1.2.6.9. International Islamic Fiqh Academy

The mission of the International Islamic Fiqh Academy is to clarify Sharia's requirements and verdicts on matters that affect Muslims globally, both independently and by the Holy Quran and the Prophet's (PBUH) Noble Sunnah (IIFA, 2022).

1.2.6.10. Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC)

The Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) is the world's second-most prominent organization, behind the United Nations (UN), with 57 member nations across four continents. It is the channel by which Muslims throughout the world express themselves. Its goal is to promote international peace and harmony by protecting and advancing Muslim interests (OIC, 2024).

1.3. Global Islamic Finance Landscape

As of the year 2021, the total assets of Islamic finance are over 4 trillion USD. According to the previous year, this asset's growth was about 17%, and the number of institutions was 1679, as the table below summarizes.

Table 1.7. Islamic Finance Distribution (2021)

Sector/Asset Class	Total Assets	Share	Number of Organizations/ Means
Islamic Banking	276 5US Billion \$	70%	566
Islamic Bonds (Sukuk)	713 US Billion \$	18%	4426
Islamic Funds	238 US Billion \$	6%	1903
Other-Islamic Financial Institutions (OIFIs)	169 US Billion \$	4%	778
Islamic Insurance (Takaful)	73 US Billion \$	2%	335

Source: (IFDI, 2022, P. 24)

According to total assets, Islamic banking, sukuk, and Islamic funds are the top three subsectors of the Islamic financial business. A whopping 70% of Islamic wealth is held in Islamic banks. Meanwhile, as shown in Figure 1.25, Takaful constitutes a small subset of Islamic financing.

Fig 1.25. Islamic Finance Assets

Source: (Author's elaboration based on IFDI- Data)

Islamic finance's assets continuously grow from 2170 USD to 3958 billion United States dollars; by 2026, they are estimated to reach 5900 billion dollars. Fig 1.26 shows the continuous growth of Islamic finance assets from 2015 to 2021.

Fig 1.26. Growth of Islamic Finance

Source: Author completion

Iran, Saudi Arabia, Malaysia, the UAE, and Qatar ranked first and fifth in terms of Islamic financing assets. Figure 1.27 shows the numerical values of the assets.

Fig 1.27. Islamic Finance Assets

Source: ICD – Refinitiv Islamic Finance Development Report 2022: Embracing Change

1.3.1. Islamic Finance Development Indicator (IFDI)

The composite weighted index known as the IFDI measures the overall development of the Islamic finance industry. This general indicator has five sub-indicators, each with metrics, as shown in Fig 1.28.

Fig 1.28. Islamic Finance Development Indicator

Source: (IFDI, 2022, P. 11)

Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Bahrain, and Kuwait rank first through fifth in Islamic finance, according to the average score of the Islamic finance development indicator. The table below shows these rankings:

Table 1.8. Leading IFDI Nations and Global Average IFDI Ratings for 2022

Country	Ranking	IFDI 2022 score	Financial Performance	Governance	Sustainability	Knowledge	Awareness
Malaysia	1	113	98	94	117	147	172
Saudi Arabia	2	74	65	49	89	75	143
Indonesia	3	61	31	65	30	195	56
Bahrain	4	59	35	86	36	49	112
Kuwait	5	59	42	75	20	21	157

Source: (IFDI, 2022, P. 12)

1.3.1.1. Financial Performance

The Financial Performance Indicator is a weighted index that measures the number of Islamic financial institutions (IFIs) and capital markets in each country that produce Islamic financial services. In the Islamic finance development indicator's sub-indicator (Financial Performance indicator), Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Iran, Kuwait, and Bahrain ranked from 1 to 5, respectively.

1.3.1.2. Governance Indicator

GI is a weighted index that measures the standards of good practice in Shariah governance, corporate governance, and regulations. In the Islamic finance development indicator's sub-indicator (Governance indicator), Malaysia, Oman, Bahrain, Pakistan, and Kuwait ranked from 1 to 5, respectively.

1.3.1.3. Sustainability Indicator

A weighted index of CSR activities and ESG practices for all Islamic finance sectors and asset classes is known as SI. In the Islamic finance development indicator's sub-indicator (Sustainability indicator), Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, South Africa, and Jordan ranked from 1 to 5, respectively.

1.3.1.4. Knowledge Indicator

The knowledge index (KI), a weighted index of education and research, is the primary component of any knowledge-based industry. In the Islamic finance development indicator's sub-indicator (Knowledge indicator), Indonesia, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Pakistan, and Bahrain ranked from 1 to 5, respectively.

1.3.1.5. Awareness Indicator

The Islamic Finance Market Awareness Index (AI) is a weighted index that evaluates two components: news and events. In the Islamic finance development indicator's sub-

indicator (Governance indicator), Malaysia, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, UAE, and Bahrain ranked from 1 to 5, respectively.

The rank, country, and score of each IFDI are specified below tables:

Table 1.9. Islamic Finance Development Indicators (Rank, Country, and Indicators Scores)

Rank/Country	Financial Performance Score	Rank/ Country	Governance Score	Rank/ Country	Sustainability Score
1/Malaysia	98	1/Malaysia	94	1/Malaysia	117
2/Saudi Arabia	65	2/Oman	89	2/Saudi Arabia	90
3/Iran	47	3/Bahrain	86	3/Singapore	61
4/Kuwait	42	4/Pakistan	75	4/South Africa	47
5/Bahrain	35	5/Kuwait	75	5/Jordan	46

Table 1.10. Islamic Finance Development Indicators

Rank/Country	Knowledge Score	Rank/ Country	Awareness score
1/Indonesia	195	1/Malaysia	172
2/Malaysia	147	2/Kuwait	157
3/Saudi Arabia	75	3/Saudi Arabia	143
4/Pakistan	52	4/UAE	116
5/Bahrain	49	5/Bahrain	112

Source: (IFDI, 2022)

1.3.1.1.1. Top Countries by Sub-Indicator of Financial Performance

Based on the results of the sub-indicator of financial performance, Sudan is first in Islamic banking, Saudi Arabia is first in takaful, Kuwait is first in other Islamic financial institutions, and Malaysia was first in Sukuk in Islamic funds in 2021. For more details, the table is placed below:

Table 1.11. Sub-Indicator of Financial Performance

Rank	Islamic Banking	Takaful	OIFIs	Sukuk	Islamic Funds
1	Sudan 137	Saudi Arabia 69	Kuwait 91	Malaysia 182	Malaysia 125
2	Bahrain 92	Iran 62	Malaysia 76	Saudi Arabia 58	Saudi Arabia 54

3	Saudi Arabia 70	Bangladesh 54	Saudi Arabia 74	Indonesia 50	Iran 32
4	Iraq 64	Malaysia 44	Iran 68	Bangladesh 47	Luxembourg 34
5	Iran 63	Maldives 36	UAE 45	Kuwait 27	Mauritius 27

Source: (IFDI, 2022)

Countries in different parts of Islamic finance are ranked based on the financial performance sub-indicator of Islamic finance development indicator. Bahrain, Iran, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, and Saudi Arabia are ranked second in Islamic banking, takaful, OIFIs, sukuk, and Islamic funds, respectively. Saudi Arabia, Bangladesh, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, and Iran are ranked third in Islamic banking, takaful, OIFIs, sukuk, and Islamic funds, accordingly based on the financial performance score.

PART TWO

ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

The study of economic development is a relatively new, intriguing, and intricate branch within the vast economics and political economic studies. Only in the past half-century or so has there been an attempt to study the problems and solutions linked to economic development in Latin America, Africa, and Asia, despite the fact that Adam Smith may have been the first development economist and his treatise *Wealth of Nations* may have been the first work on economic development (1776). Economic development quickly develops its own unique analytical and methodological character. However, it relies on pertinent ideas and concepts from other areas of economics, and it is open in a modified or standard version (Todaro & Smith, 2020, pp. 6-7). In the second part, the study focuses on nature, mean, objectives, measurement, theories, and models of economic development and compares the progression of Islamic finance of leading countries to each other. Furthermore, a literature review is done based on variables of the study, years, and sources (search databases), along with a systematic literature review.

2.1. The Nature of Development Economics

Traditional economics mainly focuses on distributing limited productive resources most effectively and economically possible and maximizing the long-term expansion of these resources to create a wider variety of products and services. A fascinating and complex subfield within the enormous fields of economics and political economy, the study of economic development is a young and exciting area of research. Economic development in Latin America, Africa, and Asia has only been studied in the last fifty years or so, even though Adam Smith might have been the first development economist and *Wealth of Nations* (1776) might have been the first book on the subject. Therefore, the focus of political economy is on the interplay between the two fields, particularly the role of power in economic policymaking. The scope of development economics is significantly broader. Economic growth, social welfare, political stability, and the efficient

use of limited productive resources are crucial for improving living standards in Latin America, Africa, and Asia, as well as in countries that were once socialist but are now in transition. To achieve this, it must address both public and private institutional mechanisms. Because most commodity and resource markets are imperfect, information is scarce for both producers and consumers, society and the economy are experiencing massive structural changes, and there is a greater likelihood of multiple equilibria than a single equilibrium. The likelihood of disequilibrium situations is higher in the least developed countries compared to the middle-developed countries. Frequently, political and social concerns such as national unity, local decision-makers taking the place of foreign advisors, settling tribal or ethnic disputes, and maintaining religious and cultural traditions overcome economic considerations. Individual factors such as family, religion, clan, or tribe may be more important than utilitarian or profit-maximizing calculations or private, self-interested concerns (Todaro & Smith, 2020, p. 8)

For this reason, development economics- more so than the political economy or even conventional neoclassical economics- most focus on the cultural, political, and economic factors necessary to transform whole societies quickly to maximize the distribution of economic benefits. It has to zero in on the best ways to help people escape the cycle of poverty that begins with economic hardship and continues at the family, regional, and national levels. Therefore, development economics considers a more active role for the government and the level of coordinated economic decision-making required to change the economy. However, this must be accomplished, even if developing-world governments and markets are only sometimes the most effective. Over the last several years, there has been a meteoric rise in the visibility and impact of non-governmental organizations on a global scale (Todaro & Smith, 2020, p. 13).

2.2. What Do We Mean by Development

We must have a basic understanding of what the word development means, as many individuals may attach different meanings to it. To tell which countries were progressing

and which were not, we would need a viewpoint and some agreed-upon assessment standards (Kumar & Sharma, 2014, p. 94).

2.3. Traditional Economics Measures

In strict economies, when we talk about development in economic terms, we mean for a nation's gross domestic product per capita to rise at a rate that outpaces its population growth. It is possible to gauge a country's economic health by looking at its real gross national income growth rates and levels per capita. How much money is added to people's gross national income per capita less the inflation rate is what this is called. It shows how much money the typical person has available to spend or save on material things and services. Economic development used to be defined as a process wherein a country's focus shifted from agriculture to industry and services, leading to an increase in the employment rate. Thus, development programs have often emphasized rapid industrialization at the expense of fostering growth in rural regions and the agricultural sector. Prior to very recently, the common understanding of development was that it was an economic phenomenon that would lead to increased gross national product (GNI) and employment possibilities for the general populace. This view held sway in development policy circles in the 1970s and other similar contexts. As long as getting the growth job done was the top priority, issues like inequality in wealth, poverty, and prejudice could wait. The GDP indicates rising production, which is frequently the focus (Kumar & Sharma, 2014, p. 96).

2.4. The New Economic View of Development

In the 1950s and 1960s, when several developing nations accomplished their economic growth targets, this narrow view of developments needed to be revised. However, the living conditions of the majority of their citizens did not change, and an increasing number of people were calling on politicians and economists to be more aggressive in their fight against increasing unemployment, economic disparity, and widespread extreme poverty. In short, the focus of economic development efforts in the

1970s changed from just growing the economy to doing away with poverty, inequality, and unemployment altogether. The term redistribution from growth became popular very fast. Development, which encompasses rapid economic growth, less inequality, and the eradication of poverty, is best understood as an intricate process involving profound changes in societal norms, public perceptions, and governmental frameworks. The essence of development is transforming a social structure from one that is poorly perceived in terms of material and spiritual well-being to one that is commonly seen as better. All members of the system, regardless of their social status, have evolving fundamental requirements and aspirations, and this process must be accommodating to them. Traditional economics, especially in developing countries, assumes a more limited view of economics and monetary systems. Within the larger social context of a country and, more significantly, the global community, all of these factors must be taken into account. Here, social system means the complex network of monetary and non-monetary factors that interact with one another. In terms of the latter, many things come into play, including people's views on life, work, and authority, cultural norms, a system of land tenure, the legitimacy and influence of government agencies, the extent to which the public is involved in development decisions and activities, and the mobility of various socioeconomic groups (Jorgenson, 2018, p. 870).

These elements differ substantially between cultural contexts and geographic locations. When considering the global economy on a global scale, it is essential to consider its structure and regulations, including who created them, who controls them, and who reaps the most significant advantages. Modern market economies are indeed expanding due to the rapid globalization of trade, capital, company boundaries, technology, intellectual property, and labor migration (Todaro & Smith, 2020, p. 8).

2.5. The Three Objectives of Development

In a developed society, people's minds and bodies are in sync as they work to raise everyone's level of living via a series of linked economic, social, and institutional projects.

There are three minimum goals that any society's progress must strive towards, regardless of the details of this better life (Cypher, 2014, p. 18):

1. Improve access to and distribution of necessities for human survival, including food, housing, medical care, and safety nets.
2. To improve people's quality of life, we need to increase wages, create more employment, improve education, and pay more attention to cultural and human values. These things will boost people's material well-being and national pride.
3. To increase the variety of social and economic options accessible to people and countries, we must liberate them from reliance on other nations and individuals and forces of ignorance and human suffering.

2.6. Three Core Values of Development

Therefore, can development be defined as the progressive improvement of a society and its institutions for the benefit of all its members? This age-old philosophical topic of what it means to live a decent life has to be revisited and re-asked from time to time in light of the dynamic nature of global civilization. The correct response for poor countries now can seem quite different from what would have been best in earlier decades. On the other hand, at least three fundamental elements or principles may be used as a framework for thinking about and doing development. Pursuing these fundamental principles – subsistence, self-respect, and freedom- represents universal aspirations. They are associated with universally expressed, essential human wants that have persisted throughout all cultures and civilizations (Todaro & Smith, 2020, p. 2).

2.6.1. Subsistence: Food maintenance, including food, clothing, and a safe place to live, is what a typical person needs to survive on a subsistence level.

2.6.2. Self-esteem: When a society's economic, political, and social structures support human values like respect, dignity, autonomy, and self-determination, its members feel valued.

2.6.3. Freedom: a society where people may express their preferences by choice and where many options are available to meet societal needs.

2.7. The Theories of Economic Development

Living standards, educational attainment, and the percentage of the population that lives to a ripe old age all indicate a country's economic prosperity. All parts of a country's economy—farming, manufacturing, commerce, technology, services, etc.—are part of its economic development. The New Human Development Index measures economic development, and its value ranges between 0 and 1; nearing 1 means that the country has better social and economic welfare. Economic development is a problem in developing countries. To solve the problem and know the arts and features of economic development, the relevant theories and models of economic development are discussed as follows:

2.7.1. Adam Smith's Theory

The Wealth of Nations was written by Adam Smith in 1776. Smith was one of the first academics to study economic development. Although he did not come up with a comprehensive theory of development, he did clarify the key components that other economists would later put forth as theories. Adam Smith calls for an increase in the efficiency of workers and capital, which is a factor in the division of labour or specialization. He adds that the main reasons for the division of labour are gaining knowledge in a particular field and investing in information technology. The main factors affecting the division of labour or specialization are the growth of markets and the accumulation of capital, which have a constructive role in the factors of trust and good governance, open trade, and natural freedom. Generally, Adam Smith focuses on capital accumulation and the division of labour. Capital accumulation means that savings go up and investments are made to gain a high income and a high living standard. After certain

stationary states, the wages will go high and cause growth in the population for employment, resulting in a decline towards growth. In the case of developing nations, Smith's theory of economic growth is only somewhat applicable. The markets are smaller in these economies, and because of this, both the ability to save and the motivation to invest are minimal. In summary, the small market size, tiny production, and low income all cause less efficiency in labour and capital in developing countries. Along with the small market size, there is a loss of significance of liberty and a lack of good governance, which does not apply to Smith's theory in the context of underdeveloped nations (Jhingan, 2011, p.167; Kerr, 1993, p. 3; Ucak, 2015, p. 665).

In the graphs below, capital accumulation goes high for some time, and growth goes to its peak point, or $OT = \text{growth}$. After a specific time and peak point, growth continues to go down or is directed in a negative direction.

Fig 2.1. Smith's Growth Theory

Source: (Jhingan, 2011, p.167)

2.7.2. Ricardian Economic Development Theory

Ricardo does not explain the theory of development, but it explains the distribution theory, where this theory can be referenced in development. This theory indicates the distribution of total national income on factors of production (land, labour, and organization), or, in other words, the share of rent, wage, and profit in the total output of

income. Ricardo believes that the main growth factor is capital accumulation, of which profit is a vital indicator of it (Rise & Shine, 2021).

Further, he explained that growth has two stages:

- Progressive stage: if profit goes high, then capital accumulation, investment, employment, wages, and lastly, the profit will be increased more than the initial profit, which results in more growth in society. In the progressive stage of growth, the rate of profit will be positive or not 0.
- Stationary state: In this stage, when wages go high, the population grows and the demand for food products increases. To satisfy the basic needs of the population, inferior goods may be produced on inferior land with additional labour, where the wage goes up, and the efficiency of the product goes down. Finally, the growth may be harmful. In the stationary state, the profit rate will be equal to zero, and the graphs below first show progressive growth after a certain period that comes down because the rate of profit declines from 0 to negative.

Fig 2.2. Ricardian Theory

Source: (Rise & Shine, 2021)

Ricardian theory emphasizes the significance of increased capital accumulation via improved farming practices, diversification of savings, and a higher profit rate. Though it

may not be entirely relevant, the Ricardian theory does highlight the elements that slow down the economic development rate of developing nations. To understand the issues faced by overpopulated economies, it is necessary to examine the two prime hypotheses of Ricardian theory: the population principle and declining returns to land. The population is growing at a quicker rate than the food supply in developing nations. People are starving for land, yet there have been no technological advancements in this area. The law of diminishing returns leads to a decline in production. Rents are expensive because arable land is scarce compared to demand. Salaries are low, however, due to an oversupply of workers and a lack of interest in using capital instead of human workers. When these conditions prevail, the rate of capital formation is low, income is low, saving capacity is poor, and there is little incentive to invest.

2.7.3. Malthusian Theory

Malthus illustrates the correlation between food supply and population, asserting that population increases at a geometric pace while food supply expands at an arithmetic rate. This status complicates economics. Two factors for controlling such disaster conditions could be considered (Sethi, 2023; TheGeoecologist, 2021).

1. Preventive check: In this case, humans should control the population by marrying at a late age and planning family size by space between births.
2. Positive check: This control system works naturally. For example, suppose the population growth rate exceeds the food supply rate. In that case, the demand for food will increase, a war can be started to access food, or the lack of food can cause difficult situations in humans, which results in deaths to control the population.

Fig 2.3. Malthusian Theory

Source: (Sethi, 2023; TheGeoecologist, 2021).

When considering developing nations, Malthus's conception of an economy as having two distinct parts- agriculture and industrial- is remarkably accurate. Dualism characterizes the economies of developing nations, with agriculture playing a secondary role in industry. Even if technology is constantly improving, the law of diminishing returns applies to the latter sector. This other industry adheres to the principles of rising returns. So, the agricultural sector slows down the industrial sector's growth. All developing nations may benefit from the correlation that Malthus found between population growth and economic development. He claims that nations with rising populations have the slowest rate of economic growth. Countless nations in Africa and Asia have found this to be true.

All developing nations may benefit from Malthus's theories on what drives economic growth. The importance of production, optimal distribution, capital accumulation, soil fertility, and technical advancement, as well as non-economic factors like strong administration, significant laws, hard work, honesty of character, etc., in fostering growth in these nations cannot be denied. Furthermore, some of Malthus' proposed policy initiatives may benefit developing nations. He emphasized the need for land reforms, a public works program, equitable land and wealth distribution, balanced growth in agriculture and industry, increased trade both within and outside the country to

broaden the market, and structural changes to reduce agriculture's relative importance. Any strategy for economic growth in a developing nation will include these steps.

To be sure, developing countries cannot use all of Malthus's arguments:

1. Before everything else, these nations are completely unsuited to the Malthusian idea of underconsumption. In the Malthusian view, underconsumption means a surplus of unsalable products due to insufficient effective demand. This means that for developing nations, their low level of consumption is a direct result of their low level of production.
2. Malthus argued that capitalist parsimony caused the lack of effective demand. He proposed that capitalists and their unproductive consumption be the solution. Situations in developing nations do not call for any of these. Extremely low income, a strong consumption propensity, and no savings characterize an impoverished country. Raising effective demand via greater consumption is not an issue here since it will cause inflation. Instead, the problem lies in increasing development savings, revenue, and employment.

2.7.4. G.S. Mill Theory

This theory states that economic development is the function of production factors (land, labour and capital). Further, in this theory, Mill stated that land and labour are the original factors of production while capital is the former factor of labour. If the land and capital growth rates are fostered, then the labour rate and the wealth of the nation will increase. The labour can be divided into productive and non-productive labour; the non-productive labour cannot increase the wealth of a nation. G. S. Mill also states that control of population, capital accumulation and laissez-faire are important factors of economic development (UGCNET Economics, 2020; Rise & Shine, 2021b). Developing nations may benefit from Mill's ideas on population growth, declining returns, capital accumulation, and the limited role of the state.

2.7.5. Demographic Transition Theory of Population

Generally, this theory states that when transferring from an agricultural economy to an industrialized economy, the high birth and death rate should come to a lower birth and death rate for utilizing limited resources. The optimum population is the equation of birth rate and death rate. Suppose the birth or death rates are greater than one another, so the population cannot be satisfied by surplus and shortage of existing resources. The graph illustrates that, in the first stage, the birth rate is higher than the death rate because agriculture requires more labour than other sectors. In the second stage, the rate of death goes down because of the population's access to food, nutrition, and health care; the difference between the birth rate and death rate is called the natural growth rate in the population. In the third stage, when the economy is industrialized, the growing rate of birth and death will go low compared to the first stage (Sethi, 2023; The Geoecologist, 2021b).

Fig 2.4. Population Transition Theory

Source: (The Geoecologist, 2021b).

2.7.6. Optimum Theory of Population

Optimum theory indicates the comparison size of the population with existing resources; if the size of the population is larger than the resource, this status is called overpopulated; if the population is smaller than the resource, this condition can be named as populated while it might be occurring this condition that size of the population is equal to existing resources where it names or called the optimum population theory. Figures 2.5 and 2.6 below summarize the above-described theory (Sethi, 2023; Yasukawa, 1952, p. 113; Samuelson, 1975, p. 531).

Fig 2.5. Optimum Population

Note: (P) indicates Population, and (R) indicates resources.

Fig 2.6. Optimum population

Source: (Sethi, 2023)

in the optimum population case, the output per capita will be higher than in two other (underpopulated and overpopulated) statuses.

Summarization of Key points of classical theories, as stated by Smith, Malthus, Mill, and Ricardo in the context of economic development, can be counted as follows:

- **Free Market Approach** : Classical economists espouse the concept of an autonomous free market within a highly competitive economic system devoid of government intervention. The invisible hand is responsible for maximizing the gross domestic product.
- **Capital Accumulation is the Master Key to Advancement:** According to all classical economists, building wealth is the driving force behind economic development. They prioritize greater savings. They believe that only landowners and capitalists can save. Workers cannot put money aside because their income is only enough to cover basic living expenses. After deducting the rent costs to landlords and workers' subsistence salaries from total output, capitalists get the excess as profits.
- **Profit is The Motivation for Investing Money in A Business:** Investment leads to profit, and profit size has a positive correlation with capital accumulation and investment.
- **The Tendency of Profits to Decline:** There is no perpetual growth in profits. When capitalists are more competitive for larger capital accumulations, they tend to fall.
- **Static Condition or Stationary State:** Classical economics universally sees the stationary state as the point at which capital accumulation stops. This cycle is repeated as soon as the wage rate approaches the subsistence level, the population and capital accumulation levels drop, and profit drops to zero.

2.7.7. Karal Marx's Theory of Economic Development

Marx believed that society has five stages (primitive stage, slavery stage, federalism stage, capitalism, and socialism), where every society already achieved the first three

stages. Every society is in the capitalist stage, in which this stage, the exploitation of labour is maximized. That is why society must be transformed into socialism. Marx has two different processes of economic development: the growth of capitalism and the destruction of capitalism (Management Classes, 2022; SSD Educational Classes, 2020).

- 1. Growth of Capitalism:** In the case of increasing or high capital accumulation, the capitalists invest their capital to return more profit, and the country's GNP will increase, which contains the elements below:

$$\text{GNP} = C + V + S$$

C= Constant capital (advanced technology, planet, and equipment), V= Variable capital (labour), and S= Surplus values= (Total value- Wages).

Below is a basic explanation of Marx's method for calculating the rate of profit and surplus value:

$$\text{Rate of surplus value} = S/V * 100$$

$$\text{Rate of profit} = S/(V+C) * 100$$

$$OL_2 \ R_2 D_2 = \text{Production} \quad R_2 D_1 D_2 = \text{Surplus}$$

$$OL_2 = \text{Libor}$$

$$OW = \text{Wage}$$

- 2. Destruction of Capitalism:** Now, the demand for labour is going down, and the capitalists are investing in technology and machinery to increase the product and earn more profit than before. Labour will lose their jobs, and they will make the union get their rights. This will challenge the society to transmit from capitalism to socialism, where the rights of each member of society remain equal.

$$R_2 P = \text{Unemployment} = \text{Reserve army labour}$$

$$\text{Organic composition of capital} = C/V$$

$$OL_1 \ R_1 \ D_1 = \text{Production} \quad WR_1 D_1 = \text{Surplus}$$

$$OL_1 = \text{Libor} \quad OW = \text{Wage}$$

Generally, the above explanation of Karal Marx is shown in Fig 2.7.

Fig 2.7. Karl Marx's Theory of Economic Development

Source: (Management Classes, 2022)

2.7.8. Schumpeter's Theory of Economic Development

Schumpeter's view is about the business cycle and the process that businesses might face with economic development. Schumpeter is a great admirer of capitalism, and the concept of economic development is divided into two (entrepreneur and innovation) parts. His theory is based on three economic factors, as named below:

1. **Circular flow:** The economic condition where the income, expense, and living standard of the human being in the society are the same or constant over time, or generally, we can state that aggregate demand is equal to aggregate supply.
2. **Innovation:** Innovation is the change of production system in such ways:
 - ✓ Totally new production
 - ✓ New or different methods of production
 - ✓ New resources for raw material
 - ✓ New markets for production
 - ✓ Change in organizational structure
3. **Crisis:** After capitalism's stationary state, a crisis may occur because of falling innovation and profit.

Schumpeter believes that innovation can break the circular flow or equilibrium of the economy through innovation; after some time, the innovation will fall, and the system of capitalism will face a crisis because of the falling technology and profit. Further, Schumpeter stated that profit is the function of innovation, and innovation is created by entrepreneurs (Tripti Sangwan, 2020; Rise & Shine, 2022). The above explanation is shown in the below-summarized Fig 2.8.

Fig 2.8. Schumpeter's Theory of Economic Development

Source: (5 Minute Economics, 2023)

2.7.9. Keynesian Theory of Economic Development

John Menard Keynes states that effective demand in the case of economic development does not concern full employment.

The point where the aggregate demand function (ADF) and the aggregate supply function (ASF) meet is known as effective demand. ASF and ADF have three different equilibrium and non-equilibrium conditions (5 Minute Economics, 2022).

ASF = Supply/ Cost price

ADF = Demand/ Revenue price

ASF = ADF C = R Equally level of Output+ Employment (Effective Demand)

$ASF > ADF$ $C > R$ Output+ Employment tends to decrease

$ASF < ADF$ $C < R$ Output+ Employment tends to increase

The graphs below tell us how, before or without full employment, the equilibrium is made with output and employment.

Fig 2.9. Keynesian Theory of Economic Development

Source: (Mini Sethi, 2022)

2.7.10. Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth

Rostow's model is a very historical model of growth which has five stages (5 Minute Economics, 2021; ECOHOLICS - Largest Platform for Economics, 2022), as explained Below:

- 1. Traditional Society:** In this growth stage, the economy is in its simplest form or even primitive form. There is less than 5 % investment, industrial growth is limited, there is no political system, and a high proportion of the workforce is employed in the agriculture sector.

2. **Preconditions For Take-Off:** In this stage, economic progress occurs, investment rises to 5 to 10 %, infrastructure is developed, the birth rate decreases, or declines and credit institutions enter the scene to mobilize society's savings.
3. **Take-Off:** This stage is all about dynamic economic growth. Investment will increase above 10 %, urbanization and industrialization will increase, and technological breakthroughs will happen.
4. **Drive To Maturity:** In this stage of growth, investments increase between 10% and 20%, industrial sectors dominate, and the primary or agricultural sectors diminish. Dependence on another economy decreases, and the standard of living greatly improves. Reaching this stage of growth takes at least 40 to 60 years.
5. **Age of High Mass Consumption:** In this stage, people have much time for leisure as the income per capita increases, consumption or spending money on luxury goods increases, and investments are above 20%.

2.7.11. Gerschenkron's Great Spurt Theory

An economic historian, Alexander Gerschenkron, examined how Europe's traditional economy tried to become industrialized. He studied the rate of change in different nations and pointed to similarities and contrasts. As a result, he outlined a few standard steps that developing nations take to improve their economies. According to Gerschenkron, we were all economically backwards at one point. A radical departure from the past—a tremendous uptick in industrialization—was necessary to get from conventional measures of economic backwardness to a contemporary industrial economy. Reforms and partial industrialization occurred in several Western nations in the first half of the nineteenth century, including France, the UK, Germany, and the US (StJohnsPipeCasts, 2021; Nishant Mehra, 2017).

2.7.12. Nurkse's Theory of Disguised Unemployment as A Saving Potential

Rosenstein-Rodan notably introduced the concept of disguised unemployment in his work, *Problems of Industrialization in Eastern and South-Eastern Europe*. Ragnar Nurkse elaborated on the idea of underdevelopment. This statement means that in undeveloped countries with large population densities, the marginal productivity of agricultural labour is zero throughout a broad spectrum. Given the available methods and productive resources. So, reducing overall agricultural productivity is feasible while removing excess labour from agriculture. When more non-forming jobs are needed, a large portion of the population works in agriculture. For instance, not all seven workers are ultimately employed if seven people are working on a farm that could be farmed by five. Even with two workers removed and replaced. The farm's overall production will remain unchanged, with the remaining five workers doing the same tasks. When two workers add nothing to the farm's production, their marginal productivity is zero (Yasser Khan, 2022; Life Economics, 2023).

2.7.13. Lewis Economic Development Model

Lewis explained that every country has two sectors as follows below:

1. Primary sector
2. Modern sector

Lewis believes that the primary or agricultural sector has access to the supply of labour, which means that labour is more than required. High wages compared to the agricultural sector will be the motive for transferring access to labour to the modern sector. When inputs like labor are ramped up in agriculture, outputs like food and fuel will reach their maximum levels after a while; at that point, the marginal product will be zero. The agricultural sector employs more workers than is necessary, but the modern sector pays higher wages overall. As a result, the modern sector takes on more workers than the

agricultural sector, which boosts production and contributes to the country's GDP (Mini Sethi, 2021b; Robert Inklaar, 2020; Robert Inklaar, 2020b).

The Lewis model is discussed below briefly, as shown in Graph 2.10.

Fig 2.10. Lewis Economic Development Model

Source: (Mini Sethi, 2022)

Once the OE labour has been expended in agriculture, production will reach its maximum, and the marginal product will be zero. At this point, the workers will be transferred to the modern sector, where their wages will be W_1 and W , respectively. The surplus or profit from this transfer, known as W_1CK , will be used to invest in further machinery and increase the modern sector's production volume. This transformation or shifting goes up to where the wage rate is equal in both sectors.

OL_1 (Labors) = OW (Wages in agricultural sector); $OL_1 = OW_1$ (Wages in the modern sector); $WICK = \text{Profit} = \text{Surplus}$; Invest $WICK$ surplus in the modern sector to shift and increase the curve of total product in manufacturing (TPM).

1.7.14. FEI- Ranis Model of Economic Development

This model is an extension of Lewis's model, also known as the dualism model. It has three phases (Mini Sethi, 2021c; Economics Time, 2023; Mahavidya Economics School, 2020).

First Phase: In this phase, marginal product is equal to zero, which means labour does not contribute to the production amount in the agriculture sector. Labor must be transferred to the industrial sector.

Second Phase: In this stage of the model, labour's contribution to production exceeds the pay it receives, as the average product exceeds the marginal product. The focus will shift to the industrial sector from Labor.

Third Phase: There is no need to move workers from agriculture to industry since the former is more efficient than the other, and the marginal product is higher than the average product. The following graphics show all three stages of the concept.

$OXC = \text{Total Productivity of Labor}$

$XC = \text{Constant}$, $XC = \text{Total Production is Constant}$; So in this case, marginal product is zero or $OM = 0$, which means that labour does not contribute to the production. This much (OM) labour will be transferred to the industrial sector, and (OW) wages will be paid in the industrial sector against (OP) production, and as a result of such labour, the surplus (WPQ), will be achieved as profit. It will be invested to generate more and more production against increasing wages. The curves of marginal productivity of labour will shift upward because the transfer of labour continues for production in the industrial sector.

Agricultural production relies on land and human labour, while manufacturing relies on capital and human effort. Society constantly evolves, and technological progress is a continual part of it.

Further, he discussed the function of production in the agricultural sector. This function is called the Coob Douglass Production function.

$$Y = e^{\alpha t} L^{\beta} P^{1-\beta} \quad (2.1)$$

In this context, Y stands for agricultural production, $e^{\alpha t}$ is a technological change that occurs at a constant rate α in time t, and L is the fixed amount of accessible land in the economy. β represents the portion of the product that landlords own, which is expressed as rent.

According to Jorgenson, the following factors are considered when determining the industrial sector pay rate:

$$\frac{\Delta M}{\Delta X} = (1 - \alpha)X = W \quad (2.2)$$

The output per man (X), the relative share of labour in the total product (1- α), and the industrial wage rate (W) are all variables in this equation. To maximize profits, the industrial pay rate must equal the marginal output of labour.

The industrial wage rate is different and higher than the wage rate in the agricultural sector, which is why the labour is shifting to the industrial sector.

$$\omega M + \mu WA = (1 - \alpha)X + qY \quad (2.3)$$

Where, ωM industrial wage bill;

Here, μWA represents the overall income from agriculture in manufactured goods, $(1-\alpha)X$ denotes the overall consumption of manufactured goods by employees in both sectors, and qY is the value of agricultural production in manufactured goods. The variable q represents the trading term that occurs between the two sectors. Jorgenson illustrates his perspective on capital accumulation, defined as investment minus depreciation;

depreciation represents a fixed proportion of capital stocks. $\dot{K} = I - \eta K$ Let η represent the depreciation rate, I denote investment, and K signifies net capital accumulation.

When technical progress occurs, the population grows at its maximum level while capital and output grow faster than the population. $\frac{\lambda}{1-\sigma} + \epsilon$ where λ is the rate of technical progress and $1-\sigma$ is the labour share. This ratio is important for the sustained development of both sectors.

1.7.16. Harris-Todaro Model of Migration and Unemployment

Workers transitioning from rural to urban settings might use this model to see how their predicted urban pay rate is stacked against their rural wage rate. If rural regions' predicted pay rate is far higher than their actual rate, the labour will move to the industrial sector. The expected rate in urban areas equals the actual wage rate multiplied by the chance (%) hiring rate in urban areas (Mini Sethi, 2021d; Robert Inklaar, 2020a; Efficacy, 2020a). The models are clearly shown in the graphs below.

Fig 2.12. Harris-Todaro Model of Migration and Unemployment

Source: (Mini Sethi, 2021d)

In equilibrium point **E**, the wages are equal in both sectors where **OM-LA** work in the agriculture sector while **OA-LM** is hired in the manufacturing sector. This equilibrium can not occur because the wages are unequal in the mentioned sectors. If we assume that

it might be an equilibrium that the expected wage rate in the urban formal industry is equal to the actual wage rate in the rural sector, understanding the equilibrium below equation will help us.

$$WA = \frac{LE}{LUS} * WM \quad (2.4)$$

Where **WA** is the wage rate in the agriculture sector

WM is the wage rate in the manufacturing sector

LUS is the total number of job seekers in the urban sector

LE is the total number of jobs available in urban area

LE/ LUS is the chance to get a job in an urban area

In the equilibrium point E, (WR_{iA}=WR_{iM})= wage rate is equal in both sectors; OM-LA= labour force hired in the agriculture sector; OM-SS= wages rate in agriculture; OA-HH= wages rate in the manufacturing sector; A Curve is the demand curve of labour in the agriculture sector; M Curve is the demand curve of labour in the manufacturing sector; X axis the number of labour and left side of the Y axis is wages rate of manufacturing sector while the right side is explaining the wages rate in the agriculture sector.

Since the two sectors cannot achieve pay parity, the second equilibrium represents the proper equilibrium. There are two subsets within urban areas: the official and informal sectors. Workers in the official economy earn much money, whereas their informal sector counterparts earn far less.

Calculation of wage rates in the formal and informal sectors of the urban sector are summarized below:

$$WA = \frac{LF}{LF+LI} * \acute{W} + \frac{LI}{LF+LI} * WI \quad (2.5)$$

LF is the total number employed in the formal sector

LI is the total number employed in the informal sector

LF+ LI is job seekers in both sector

\dot{w} is the wage rate in the formal sector

W_I is the wage rate in the informal sector

W_A is agriculture wage rate

$LF/LF+LI$ is the chance (%) of hiring in the formal sector

$LI/LF+LI$ is the chance (%) of hiring in the informal sector

in the formal sector, high wages are given to those labourers who are hired in the formal sector in urban areas; in the case of hiring (LA-LM) labour in the informal sector, the wages continue to fall, or the labour force will be kept unemployed.

1.7.17. Leibenstein's Critical Minimum Effort Theory

This theory explains how an underdeveloped country can break a poverty cycle by using critical minimum effort. It means the minimum level of investment is essential for economic development to be invested. Two forces affect economic development, and income level will be affected positively and negatively by them; shocks can reduce the income level while stimulants will generate the income level to have a positive effect on economic development. Shocks reduce the income level and depress the economy, and stimulants generate income and encourage economic development. High technology is the sample of stimulants, while low technology can be counted as a shocking example (Mahavidya Economics School, 2020; Ekjyot Gujral, 2021; Sheenu Economics Classes, 2021).

In Fig 2.13, the H curve is the shocks curve, the N curve is the stimulants curve, the B straight line curve is the balanced growth line, E is the lower equilibrium, and Z is the critical minimum point. Suppose the country's invested amount is lower than the critical minimum effort point. In that case, this investment is not beneficial because the RB shock is greater than the RA stimulant, and the country's economy continues to fall to a lower equilibrium point. If the investment is more than the critical minimum effort point, in this

case, the QT stimulant is greater QG shocks or the stimulant is growing and shocking is decreasing; that is why the economy is getting better daily.

Fig 2.13. Leibenstein's Critical Minimum Effort Theory

Source: (Sheenu Economics Classes, 2021)

2.7.18. Nelson's Low-Level Equilibrium Trap

This theory elucidates the concept of a low-level equilibrium trap, which occurs in any nation when the population increase exceeds the income growth rate. A low level of national income results from low-income levels, savings, and investments in nations that have fallen into the trap. To address this issue, Nelson proposed that the increase in income would outpace the population (Mini Sethi, 2021e; Ecoholics - Largest Platform for Economics, 2022b; E.Z. Classes, 2018).

Fig 2.14. Nelson's Low-Level Equilibrium Trap

Source: (E.Z. Classes, 2018)

In panel A, the point of \dot{S} , the growth rate of the population is zero, where this point is equal to point X . Panel B shows 0 savings and investment, as in panel C, point S indicates the equation of the growth rate of population and total income.

In panel C, the low-level equilibrium is at point S , where the income level and population growth rate are both zero; a new stable equilibrium for the nation is at point N . Panel C in N shows that beyond that point, the population growth rate is greater than the income level. Hence, the government must step in to restore the country's economy to its previous stable equilibrium.

dp/p = growth rate of the population; $S = \dot{S} = X$; Y/P = per capita income level; dy/y = growth rate of income; dk/p = growth rate of investment.

2.7.19. Big Push Theory

This theory concentrates on pushing in the form of significant investments to remove the existing obstacle towards growth. Small investments waste resources; for growth, minimal investment is required. The minimum investment is the required level of investment for the country's growth (Mini Sethi, 2021c; TestPrep (AP, GATE, NET . . .), 2019; E.Z. Classes, 2018a). This theory focuses on three types of indivisibility named below:

1. **Indivisibility of Production:** Production should be large-scale, resulting in an economy. The theory's founder further mentioned that the economy arising from social overhead capital is more effective than the other forms. Social overhead capital includes transportation, communication, and power.
2. **Indivisibilities of Demand:** A single industry can not create demand. There must be so many industries to create demand for one another. Generally, interdependent industries in the economy are essential to creating demand.

For example, if there is one industry, in this case, output Q_1 is in price W , $AR < AC$, while increasing the industry in the economy, the output and the price will go higher along with profit and $AR(\text{Demand}) > AC$. The graph below gives the details;

Fig 2.15. Big Push Theory

Source: (TestPrep (AP, GATE, NET . . .))

A single industry in the economy

$OQ_1 = \text{Output}$; $Op_1 = \text{Cost}$; $OP_1 (AC) > OW(AR)$

Multiple industries in the economies

$OQ_2 = \text{Output}$; $Op_3 = \text{Cost}$; $ON (AR) > OP_3(AC)$

3. **Indivisibility of Supply Saving:** In developing nations, investment and savings could be more. A rise in national income will result in a higher marginal propensity to save, surpassing the marginal propensity to consume ($APS > APC$).

2.7.20. Theory of Unbalanced Growth

This theory explains that underdeveloped countries, due to the lack of resources, should invest these resources in the leading sector, which has an automatic effect on investment-increasing in other sectors of the economy (Mini Sethi, 2021b; E.Z. Classes, 2018b; EKOM Academy, 2021). This theory explains two types of series below;

1. **Divergent:** The resources of this kind of investment are related to the government, or this investment is called social overhead capital (SOC), as these investments include (roads, irrigation, power, communication, and transport).
2. **Convergent:** The resources of this type of investment are related to the private sector, as these investments include (the agriculture sector, manufacturing, trade and tourism). This investment is also named direct productive activities (DPA).

If SOC increases by the amount of RM, the DPA will increase to RK automatically, increasing both types of investment equalized in the straight line of R. In each point of the R line, the social overhead capital equals direct productive activity (SOC=DPA). a, b, and c curves are the ISO product line whereby increasing each type of investment, the mentioned curves are shifting upward. Remember that both types of investment affect one another until they are equal; after the equation, by increasing SOC, the DPA will be increased and affected more than the primary stage, and this effect can occur inversely. Linkage effects are also discussed in the theory; the forward linkage effect means that it affects a later stage of investment, while backward linkage has an early-stage effect. Increasing SOC will create increasing in the amount of DPA and vice versa; the below graph explains furthermore the above issue:

Fig 2.16. Theory of Unbalanced Growth

Source: (EKOM Academy, 2021)

2.7.21. Balanced Growth Theory

This theory explains that large amounts of investments are required in all factors of the economy for balanced growth simultaneously. Underdeveloped countries can not grow because of the vicious cycle of poverty. The founder of the theory believes that government intervention is essential for breaking the vicious cycle of poverty through large amounts of investment. The Vicious Cycle of Poverty operates on two sides: the demand side and the supply side; each side has its own stages that lead to other stages (Mini Sethi, 2021c; Chanakya Group of Economics, 2018; Anita Chandel Economics Classes, 2021).

Fig 2.17. Vicious Cycle of Poverty

Fig 2.18. Vicious Cycle of Poverty

Source: (Mini Sethi, 2021c)

In the non-profitable sector, the private sector can not invest; instead, the government invest and intervenes in the economy. The government should invest in large amounts for a balanced increase in production, which will lead to enlarging the size of the market. In this manner, the cycle of poverty will break; in all, the aggregate demand, investment, income, and productivity will increase one another, and the cycle of poverty will turn to the balanced growth of the whole industry.

Fig 2.19. The Cycle of Poverty Turning to Balance Growth

Source: (Anita Chandel Economics Classes, 2021)

2.7.22. Dualism Theory of Economic Development

Dualism's theory of economic development has many types. Where we explain the three main types as below:

1. **Technological Dualism:** Structural unemployment in manufacturing and hidden unemployment in agriculture are caused by the dualism of technology in emerging countries. Population increase causes disguised unemployment, whereas missed resource allocation causes structural unemployment. The theory's creator implies different production functions in the modern and traditional sectors. In the industrial sector, a fixed proportion of production factors (capital and labour) is used for production. There is no possible absorption in the labour amount instead of capital (See Fig 2.20), whereas, in the agriculture sector, the proportion of K/L is changeable for production (1 Minute Economics, 2021; JHINGAN, 2012, p. 340). The following graph shows four isoquants of output, denoted as IQ1, IQ2, IQ3, and IQ4. Each isoquant represents a distinct combination of capital and labour, and A, B, C, and D are the respective combinations of these two variables for each isoquant. A constant percentage component is represented by the slope of the route expansion in the industrial sector, abbreviated as OE.

market, debt is given by village lenders or landlords at a high rate of interest, while in an organized financial market, the rate of interest is low compared to non-organized financial markets. This dualism of financial affairs might cause problems in economic development for underdeveloped countries (Learn Oikonomia, 2024; 1 Minute Economics, 2021c; Anita Chandel Economics Classes, 2021b).

2. **Social Dualism:** The society can be homogenous and dual or plural society. This society can be represented by pre-capitalism and post-capitalism. Pre-capitalism mainly concentrates on the agricultural sector, which could also be named the Esteren sector. On the other hand, there is the Western sector, where the imported advanced social style is named. Both mentioned sectors have their characteristics (technology, innovation, capital, organization, risk-taking, and skillful labor) to differentiate from one another (1 Minute Economics, 2021a; Yasser Khan., 2023).

2.7.23. Dependent Theory of Underdevelopment

According to dependency theory, the wealthier "Core" states enrich themselves at the cost of the poorer, less developed "Periphery" nations (CSS World, 2020).

Core Country: Great and advanced power nations such as the UK, USA, Canada ..etc.

Semi-Peripheral Countries: Industrializing, mainly capitalist countries, took place between core and periphery countries.

Peripheral Countries: Less developed and weak nations such as Afghanistan, Somalia..etc.

In dependent underdevelopment theory, The Peripheral and Semi-Peripheral Countries depend on core countries because the peripheral and semi-peripheral countries export their source to core countries and import the manufactured goods at a high cost processed by core countries. By the cost of poor and underdeveloped countries, the core countries continue to develop and become stronger than previously (Allensens, 2012;

Samaaj Samjhein, 2022). The dependent theory of underdevelopment has three core hypotheses, as counted below:

1. International division of labour between countries
2. Class distinction
3. Global capitalism

Fig 2.22. Dependent Theory of Underdevelopment

Source: (Samaaj Samjhein, 2022)

2.7.24. Limit to Growth Model

According to this scenario, the future holds rapid global population, food production, and industrial output increases. Pollution, dwindling land supplies, and specialized technology that cannot provide an infinite supply of resources will trigger a collapse in resource availability by the century's conclusion. Therefore, considering the issue, it is necessary to use resources rationally. According to the limits to growth (LTG) model, Continued Growth Leads to Infinite Quantities That Just Do Not Fit Into a Finite World. This fundamental premise is the basis for the model's predictions or findings. In Figure 2.23 below, panels A, B, and C illustrate the limits of the growth model. The horizontal axis displays the passage of time in years, starting from 1900 and continuing until 2100. The R-curve, which slopes downward in panel A, represents resources measured along the vertical axis. Resources like oil, natural gas, copper, lead, etc., are finite and will continue to be exhausted from 1900 until at least 2100. Panel B displays the P and F curves, which indicate population growth and food supply as measured on the vertical axis. They are shown to rise at the same pace from 1900 to 2100 years, up to point

E. However, after 2000, the population curve P kept growing, but the food production curve F increased at a decreasing pace until 2100, when it began to decline. According to the PN curve, the pollution level in panel C is projected to keep increasing beyond 2010 and will have disastrous consequences if not managed promptly (UPSC 360, 2020; TheGeoecologist, 2021c; Jhingan, 2012).

Fig 2.23. Limit to Growth Model

Source: (UPSC 360, 2020)

2.7.25. Gunnar Myrdal Theory of Circular Causation

This theory explains that change in any sector of the economy will lead to change in other sectors of the mentioned economy. The focus point of this theory is regional inequality, where free market forces make the region more unequal than before. Regional inequality is the change in the standard of living, including health, wealth and education. Further in this theory, the two types of effects are explained below:

1. **Backwash Effect:** The adverse effect of the movement of wealth from a poor region to a rich region is called the backwash effect.
2. **Spread Effect:** The effect of one region's development will spread to nearby locations.

In the below graph, we have two regions: A is a developed region, and B is a developing region; in initial equilibrium in the point of E, the development level is the same, and because of that, the wage rates are all so the same as $W_A = W_B$. The labourers are migrating from developing regions to developed regions because of high wages, so in this case, the movement of the labour will continue until a new equilibrium occurs in the point of E1, where the wage rate is equal in both mentioned regions as $W_A = W_B$. Shifting the labour from a developing region to a developed region has an adverse effect on developing regions, such as decreasing demand for domestic goods, low investment, low employment, low capital formation, and finally, the region will go back or at least keep in the current (developing status) situation. On the other hand, the demand for labour in developed regions will get higher, and increasing investment, job opportunities and high wages will have a spread effect near the location to the developed regions (Mini Sethi, 2021i; Vision Economics, 2020; Mahavidya Economics School, 2021).

Fig 2.24. Circular Causation

Source: (Vision Economics, 2020)

2.8. Measurements of Economic Development

It is widely acknowledged that most of Asia, Latin America and the Caribbean, North Africa and the Middle East, Sub-Saharan Africa, Various Islands, and the Transition Nations of Eastern Europe constitute part of the developing world. It is often likened to the (OECD) area, which includes New Zealand and Australia but is occasionally called the North. This text focuses on the developing world and argues that there is just as much distinction between developing and developed nations as between the two (Todaro & Smith, 2020, p. 37).

GNI and GDP do not compare the Domestic Purchasing Power of various currencies; income levels are a good indicator of economic development. Several studies have attempted to overcome this issue by comparing relative GNIs and GDPs Using Purchasing Power Parity Instead of Exchange Rates or by converting the income level to buying power parity. Even more accurate than purchasing power parity (PPP), the composition index of HDI could be considered to measure economic development status. The World Bank sorted the nations of the globe into five groups according to their GDP

per capita: low-income countries (LICs), lower-middle-income countries (LMCs), upper-middle-income countries (UMCs), high-income OECD members, and other high-income countries (HICs). Inflation and other variables are considered when the cutoffs are revised annually. A per capita gross national product (GNI) of \$1,195 or less was used to classify LICs for 2023–2024. LMCs had incomes between \$1136 and \$4465, UMCs had incomes between \$4466 and \$13845, and HICs had incomes above \$13845 (World Bank, 2024).

Other Common Country Classifications

Other frequently used official international designations exist.

G7 and G20: two groups of nations have geographical importance: the G7, which consists of the seven biggest developed countries, and the G20, which includes the major middle-income countries.

Least Developed Countries (LDCs): At the end of 2023, 45 nations were included in this commonly used UN categorization; thirty-three were in Africa, eight were in Asia, three were in the (Pacific) Ocean, and one was in the Caribbean. To be included, a nation must have a low income, poor human capital (health and education), and a significant economic vulnerability (UN List of Least Developed Countries, 2023).

Least Developed Countries

Africa (33), Asia (8), Caribbean (1), Pacific (3)

Fig 2.25. LCDs Map

Source: (UN List of Least Developed Countries, 2023)

Landlocked and Small Island Countries: List of Landlocked Developing Countries (2023): Small Island Developing States (SIDS)—a group of 39 countries—and Landlocked Developing Countries (LLDCs)—a group of 32 countries—with 17 of these being the Least developed countries.

Heavily Indebted Poor Countries (HIPC): According to international agreements, this official categorization has been given particular attention for aid projects since the early 2000s. 37 HIPC countries exist as of 2019 (Heavily Indebted Poor Countries (HIPC) Initiative, 2024).

Newly industrializing countries (NICs): This is an informal way to describe economies that are just starting to see development in export-led manufacturing. In the 1970s and 1980s, South Korea, Taiwan, Thailand, and Indonesia were heavily tagged with the NIC mark. A nation like Vietnam today may be part of this category.

Emerging Market: The phrase frontier markets might be used for nations that investors see as less promising than developing markets. The term emerging market is used more casually and less stably in the financial press. Though it is no longer officially recognized, the phrase was first used by the private sector members of the World Bank Group, the International Finance Corporation (IFC). To ward off the then-standard phrase third world, which, according to the IFC, investors tended to connect with stagnation- the IFC coined the word to conjure up images of development.

Human Development Level: Using indicators like health care access and educational completion rates, the (UNDP) ranks nations as either low, medium, high or extremely high regarding human development.

Comparing Countries By Health and Education and the Human Development Index

To fully grasp a nation's economic progress, we must consider not just its average income but also its average health and educational accomplishments, which provide light on its basic capacities. Three essential measures of general health are the birth rate, the

mortality rate among children under five, and the prevalence of undernourishment. The proportion of the population with secondary education or above and the gross enrollment ratio for secondary school are two measures of average education. The UNDP produced the Human Development Index to compare nations' socioeconomic development status in 1990. This index was used up to 2009, and after that, in 2010, the traditional human development index was changed to a new or current human development index, where this index differed in the calculation process from the previous traditional development index (Todaro & Smith, 2020, pp. 46-47).

The current Human Development Index (HDI) formula ranks countries from 0 (Lowest Human Development) to 1 (Highest Human Development) according to three criteria: the average number of years lived at birth, the average number of years spent in school by adults, and the real per capita gross domestic income adjusted for differences in purchasing power parity of each country's currency to reflect cost of living and the assumption of diminishing marginal utility of income. Here are the key points and aspects of the human development index:

Fig 2.26

Source: (Human Development Index (HDI), 2024)

The Human Development Index (HDI) is calculated as $(HDI) = H^{1/3} E^{1/3} I^{1/3}$, where H represents the health index, E denotes the education index, and I signifies the income index.

Major Consistencies and Distinctions Among the Emerging Countries

Ten characteristics define the main points of convergence and divergence across emerging nations and the variety and intensity of the obstacles to economic development each nation faces. For each characteristic, highly significant disparities behind the averages should be recognized and considered in development policies.

1. Earnings and output levels
2. The success of human capital
3. Severe inequality and poverty
4. The composition of younger and older populations
5. Those living in rural areas and those moving from rural to urban areas
6. The splitting of society
7. The extent to which industrialization and manufactured goods exports
8. Legacies related to land and its resources
9. The magnitude of the economy's financial and other marketplace
10. The reliability of the institution and its dependence on external funding

Human Development and Türkiye

The Human Development Index values in 2022 for the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and Türkiye are 0.037 (ranked 17), 0.875 (ranked 40), 0.875 (ranked 40), and 0.855 (ranked 45), respectively.

Fig 2.27. HDI- Value and Rank

Source: (Human Development Report, 2023-2024)

The Human Development Index is a summary measure of essential aspects of human progress, such as life expectancy, level of education, and economic stability. Each HDI dimension consists of three indicators: Gross National Income (GNI) Per Capita measures a respectable living level; Life Expectancy at Birth measures a healthy and long life; and Expected and Mean Years of Schooling measures a good education (knowledge). The ranking of the Human Development Index (HDI) and Gross National Income (GNI) Per Capita (PPP) differs from one another. For example, as a rank, Türkiye's HDI value is a head-two rank compared to a ranking by GNI per Capita across the globe.

Fig 2.28. Comparing The Ranking of HDI and GNI Per Capita (PPP, 2017)

Source: (Human Development Report, 2023-2024)

Figure 3 compares the countries' Human Development Index rankings over two years. Türkiye ranked 48 and 45 in 2021 and 2022, respectively.

Fig 2.29. Comparing The HDI

Source: (Human Development Report, 2023-2024)

The comparative economic development of the countries can be measured, and the level of income is the very first traditional measurement that compares the economic situation of the countries. For a more accurate comparison, the income level is measured by power purchasing parity to know the real economic condition. Below, the fig shows how Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (PPP) differs from GDP Per Capita and shows the Real Purchasing Power. Based on the analysis, Türkiye's GDP per capita is 12760 \$, and its adjusted GDP per capita (PPP) is 43920 \$ in 2024, which shows the real purchasing power of the country.

Fig 2.30. GDP Per Capita Vs GDP Per Capita (PPP)

Source: (Kuwait Datasets, 2024; Nigeria Datasets, 2024; Indonesia Datasets, 2024; Malaysia Datasets, 2024; Türkiye Datasets, 2024; United Arab Emirate, 2024; Oman Datasets, 2024; Qatar Datasets, 2024; Saudi Arabia, 2024).

2.9. Systematic Literature Review

Within the framework of Islamic banking, sukuk, and takaful, the Prisma 2020 flow diagram serves as the basis for the methodical literature review on the linkages between

Islamic finance and economic growth in Muslim-led nations. Islamic finance and economic development words with critical synonyms are used in different search databases. One hundred seventy reports were achieved, consistent with 20 duplicates, and 25 records were not to the point of research. One hundred twenty-five reports were screened. Five did not match the research questions, and this amount is excluded. Five reports were inaccessible for different reasons to achieve the full text of the remaining 120 reports. One hundred fifteen reports are accessed in a full-text version based on an analysis of such reports. Due to the lack of clarity and quality, 23 reports are further excluded for consideration in research. In sum, 92 reports were analyzed for systematic literature on research titled Islamic Finance and Economic Development: Afghanistan and Türkiye Comparative Study. The PRISMA 2020 diagram below shows the systematic process of a systematic literature review and how to conduct it.

Fig 2.31. PRISMA Statement

Source: (PRISMA Statement, 2020)

Table 2.1 below lists the various search databases that specify the variables and sub-variables of the study on relevant reports of included studies for evaluation and analysis in a literature review. As seen below, a total of 92 access reports are discussed one by one:

Table 2.1. Search Databases

Variables and Sub-Variables of The Study	Databases	Number
Islamic Finance	Directory of Open Access Journal (DOAJ)	10
Islamic Banking (sub-variable of Islamic finance)	Dergi Park Akademik	12
Islamic Capital Markets (sub-variable of Islamic finance focusing on SUKUK)	Science Direct	11
Takaful(sub-variable of Islamic finance)	Google Akademik	10
Economic Development/ Economic Growth	IEEE Xplore Digital Library (1-2); EBSCO	14
Human Development Index (Measurement Scale of HDI)	IEEE Xplore Digital Library	10
Relationship Between Islamic Finance and Economic Development/ Growth	Web Science (1-23) and CINAHL (24-25)	25

Source: Developed by author

Common Law/Sharia Law, Civil Law/Common Law, and Common Law/Sharia Law are examples of the combinations of the three legal systems that Grassa and Gazdar (2014) looked at and how they affected economic growth. Researchers compared historical data for 30 nations studied between 2005 and 2010 and ran cross-country regressions. According to this study, nations with legal systems based on Sharia had the most advanced financial systems. The mixed legal system, which combines civil law and Sharia law, significantly hinders the growth of Islamic finance. The evolution of Islamic banking, on the other hand, is positively influenced by common law/Sharia law. Furthermore, the research assesses that those countries adopting mixed (Common Law/Civil Law) law based on weak infrastructure for the Islamic financial industry negatively affect Islamic banking growth. Concentrating on the Muslim population and income level also positively affects Islamic banking.

Hassan et al. (2019) examined Islamic financial principles from conception to evolution. The guidelines are derived from (AAOIFI), (IFSB), and (IIFM). The function of such bodies and the process of developing the standard are discussed, along with socioeconomic factors impacting the system. At the end of the research, the problems are

highlighted in the studied standards for future strengthening, and some suggestions are pointed out for upcoming conducting research.

To investigate the problems with Islamic financial regulation in Türkiye, Yaş (2023) used semi-structured interviews. Twelve people, including officials from Islamic financial institutions (IFIs), their boards of advisors, and members of the Central Advisory Board, filled out the survey. The findings highlight the persistent need to create a regulatory structure for the participation financing industry. This method seeks to reduce the risk of non-compliance with Shari'ah law, keep taxes from becoming too high, strengthen the hierarchy of norms, and stop imitators from making ordinary financial goods. According to the research, there has to be a solid organizational structure, more transparency and independence for regulatory bodies, better involvement of stakeholders, and defined responsibilities. For better regulatory results, better regulatory governance is needed. Finally, the research highlights the importance of participation in finance industry standards and the necessity of their voluntary application.

Saidu (2020) outlines two prerequisites for a perfect and workable Islamic finance system. he applies a diachronic approach and uses historical data, scriptural reasoning, and inductive logic for analysis. The study reveals several problems and possibilities regarding Islamic finance that must be addressed or pushed aside. Namely, Islamic financing cannot be implemented in the absence of Islamic Law; Islamic Man; Islamic Financing could be organized in the absence of Islamic law but with the help of an Islamic man; global Islamic finance can be accommodated within a workable legal framework in the modern world; and Islamic finance is not an international phenomenon, but it is workable legal microframework.

Calandra et al. (2022) used bibliometric and open coding techniques to sift through 170 Islamic banking and technology publications. The study analysis identifies the leading publications, authors, and nations that fund most of the research expenditures in this area. Thematic research also shows that technological applications to Takaful are one of the

specialized topics. The potential of technology to aid decision-making in Islamic banking is one of the driving themes. This research is the best reference for understanding the concept of Islamic finance and technology for practitioners before starting jobs in this field. At the end of the article, some suggestions for future research are guided.

Migdad (2021) explored the scope and concept of Corporate Social Responsibility(CSR) from an Islamic perspective. The factors of CSR in Islamic economic tradition, especially in Islamic Financial Institutions, are explained. The study found that CSR is the original concept in Islamic economics, and some views of famous scholars have been gathered about the idea. Fighting corruption and sensitivity to Sharia-compliant operations should occur in light of the corporation's social responsibility to prevent additional costs that the corporation directly spends on CSR. The corporation to do so is Islamic banks to broaden the CSR in anti-strategy of corruption and sharia-compliant operation.

Siswantoro (2022) studied the effects of Islamic social finance, Islamic commercial finance, and a combination of the two on poverty in Indonesia. This study used the Error Correction Model technique to examine time series data from 2002–2021. This approach will show how Islamic commercial finance, Islamic social finance, and their combination affect short- and long-term poverty. Research shows that Islamic commercial financing, social finance, or a combination may significantly lower poverty rates. Integrating Islamic social and commercial financing negatively links the poverty rate in the short term, although this correlation is not statistically significant. In contrast, Islamic social finance and Islamic commercial finance have a negative but insignificant effect on the poverty rate. Furthermore, research concludes that future rulemaking should focus on establishing guidelines for establishing joint ventures between Islamic financial institutions.

Tohirin and Ismail (2016) explained that Islamic finance can reduce imperfect capital market problems, namely asymmetric information, agency problems, and transaction costs. Financial constraints exist in capital markets located in Malaysia, where

this constraint can be reduced through Islamic financings, as in Musharakah and Mudarabah forms. The imperfection of capital markets can be reduced if not overcome by Islamic financing because of the sharing of information between financiers and borrowers, which could occur along with lowering the cost of capital for sharing the profit and loss between the two parties rather than being burdened only on one shoulder.

Mohammed et al (2022) explore that climate change is the most complex challenge against human beings, and there is a dearth of ways to eliminate or evenly reduce the adverse effects and continue the planet's sustainable development. The environmental, social, and government (ESG) sectors still have many unsolved issues about carbon credit trading, effect assessment, accountability, greenwashing, and traceability. Research further identifies the opportunity for Islamic finance by using The DCarbonX business model and a decentralized application where the application solves the mentioned problem by using non-fungible tokens on the blockchain platform through smart contracts. The explanation of DApps (DeFi¹, Web 3.0 and ESG) is part of the research, and comparatively, it has been investigated in blockchain platforms for decentralized applications development. The article found that the SDGs are aligned with Maqasid al-Shariah's main objectives. Decentralized applications (DApps) built on blockchain platforms can help address environmental, social, and governance (ESG) concerns, including the effects of climate change. By releasing decentralized applications (DApps) in the areas of capital markets such as green sukuk, embedded finance, takaful, non-fungible tokens (NFTs), RegTech, and SupTech, Islamic finance can take advantage of the unrealized potential in blockchain-based solutions for climate change.

Lone and Quadir (2017) investigated the rationale for using a profit-and-loss-sharing system in Islamic banking, explicitly focusing on the borrowers' net worth. A project's financing is a crucial component. Money, considered the lifeblood of the business, is essential for carrying out the endeavour. However, economists have offered

¹ DeFi denotes decentralized finance

an alternate method of project financing because of the predetermined interest rate. Additionally, the research contrasted an interest-based funding system with a Profit and Loss Sharing (PLS) program. They provide new theoretical justifications for the low frequency of PLS use in Islamic banking. The study delves into game theoretic solutions to address these moral hazard issues in PLS.

Bayram et al. (2023) researched soundness indicators of Turkish Islamic and conventional banks. The study employs financial ratios consistent with the Banko meter technique and covers 2017–2022. Ranking systems such as ARAS, CoCoSo, COPRAS, MABAC, and TOPSIS are utilized, and the results of such ranking are integrated into the Borda Count method. The results show that all the banks considered are financially stable, with private conventional banks consistently rating at the top. This research is significant because it shows that Türkiye's conventional and Islamic banking sectors are financially stable, even when tested using different methods, and that this stability persists even when faced with challenging global conditions like the COVID-19 pandemic.

Using performance indicators extracted from 22 Islamic banks' financial statements, Ada and Dalkiliç (2014) studied the relationship between scale efficiency, efficiency improvements, and total factor productivity change. Between 2009 and 2011, information was culled from 18 different Malaysian banks and 4 Turkish institutions. The research uses the Malmquist Total Factor Productivity Index to track changes in efficiency and total factor productivity and Data Envelopment Analysis to quantify efficiency. The average scale efficiency of Turkish banks was more significant in 2009 than that of Malaysian banks, but it was lower in 2010 and 2011, according to the researchers. When comparing the years 2009 and 2010, the overall factor productivities of Turkish banks fell in the latter half of that year. On the other hand, the banks in Malaysia had a rise in total factor productivity during the same period, except for three specific banks.

Okumus and Artar (2012) stated that continuous volatility in international financial markets emphasizes how crucial financial stability is to further economic development.

Some contend that Islamic banking can better handle macro-financial crises and promote economic development than conventional banking due to its inherent advantages. The GCC's financial stability is now a vital issue for the rest of the world, as well as the nations themselves, considering the recent political upheavals in the region. This study aims to gather information on the financial health of Islamic banks in the Gulf Council countries (GCC), including Türkiye, using data collected from both Islamic and commercial banks. According to the report, big commercial banks are more financially secure than big Islamic banks. Small Islamic banks are often better prepared for adverse financial storms than their smaller commercial banks.

Durmuş (2023) investigates how Islamic banking professionals understand internal communication channels. Additionally, it explores the culture of thankfulness in an Islamic bank to uncover the hidden aspects of organizational culture. It explores the gratitude culture of an Islamic bank by diving into an Islamic bank's culture of thankfulness. This research sought to add to the existing literature by examining a case study of Islamic banks, which has yet to be overlooked in the field. This study was conducted in Türkiye, and semi-structured, in-depth interviews were conducted in 2017. Thematic analyses were performed to catch the patterns, and two main themes were found in the topography of the data. These themes were no gratitude here and yes but not enough. The first theme explored the views of most of the participants, who reported that there is no culture of thankfulness in the context of Islamic banks. However, the other minority group of participants stated that there is a culture of gratitude for Islamic banks. Still, it is not enough to achieve the goals of the organization efficiently. Finally, a culture of no-thankfulness may adversely affect the psychology, motivation, and feelings of worthiness of employees.

Madni (2017) explained that Islamic finance is gaining significant attention in the thriving banking industry due to its distinctive features and popularity. The Islamic finance industry has now surpassed \$1 trillion US dollars and is experiencing an annual growth rate of approximately 20%. Not only are Islamic financial goods expanding within

Muslim civilizations, but they are also gaining popularity in non-Muslim countries. This article looks at a statistical sample of low- and middle-income nations to see how the expansion of Islamic banking has affected their economic growth. There is a favorable correlation between Islamic banking and economic growth, even if Islamic banking is relatively tiny compared to the size of the economy and the whole financial system. This correlation remains after accounting for other factors, such as the degree of financial depth. The findings are consistent when considering different factors, sample compositions, and periods. It argues that the government should make Islamic banking a top policy priority to boost economic growth.

According to Malek and Rao (2022), Islamic banking profitability has recently garnered much attention in the literature on bank profitability. Quantifying the influence of internal and external (macroeconomic) factors on Islamic banking profitability, this research examines data from a selection of Asian Islamic banks (Bahrain, Iran, Türkiye, and Malaysia) from 2011 to 2020. The empirical analysis makes use of the panel data method. Islamic banks' return on average equity (ROAE) and return on average assets (ROAA) demonstrate their profitability. They conducted descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression for the study's variables. According to the data, the operating expense ratio (OER) and liquidity ratio (LQR) are positively correlated. There is an inverse association between the age of a bank and the inflation growth rate. Moreover, for some Islamic banks, the data demonstrate that Bank Age (BA) negatively impacts profitability. On the other hand, a bank's profitability is positively and significantly affected by its equity ratio (ER) and bank size (BS). In contrast to conventional banks, Islamic financial institutions do not let macroeconomic factors like GDP growth, inflation, and banking system type influence their profitability.

Lajuni et al (2017) investigate factors influencing the intention to utilize Islamic banking products in a dynamic and growing market. Recognizing customers' intentions to use Islamic banking products is crucial, given that both Muslims and non-Muslims are adopting this practice. According to this line of thinking, based on theory and practice,

customers' perceptions of a product influence their intention to purchase it. The study distributed 200 questionnaires, among which 131 were received for using Structural equation modelling with partial least squares to examine the data. The results demonstrate that consumers' attitudes, levels of government support, and social influences can explain and predict whether they will utilize Islamic banking products or not. This research adds to the existing body of knowledge by shedding light on developing economies, where clients increasingly receive bank services tailored to their specific needs.

Abdullah (2017) compares Malaysia's and Indonesia's Islamic banking sectors and evaluates Islamic financial institutions based on five criteria: legal framework, court jurisdiction, capital growth, products offered, and Shariah governance. According to the research, neither country is far ahead of the other in the Islamic banking sector, even if they are both making great strides. In some categories, Malaysia ranks higher than Indonesia, but in others, Indonesia ranks higher than Malaysia. The study finds both benefits and drawbacks compared to other nations in the Islamic banking sector. Therefore, to achieve their goal of being a Centre for the Islamic banking business, both should improve their shortcomings while enhancing their strengths.

Aldoury (2020) stated that some principles of the Islamic financial ecosystem differ from the world's financial ecosystem, mainly in terms of interest (Riba). Islamic financial system is the best substitute or alternative to the world financial system, even in non-Muslim countries. The study focuses on the origins and functions of financial accounting, exploring differences between dividends and interest in Islamic banking, explains Islamic accounting's historical origins, inception, and practical applications, and examines the concept of banks in Islam. They thoroughly analyzed and discussed foreign trade financing, financial accounting standards (2-numbered standards), modaraba, and interest-free banking.

This study by Akin and Ozsoy (2021) looked at how Islamic banks in Türkiye may generate aggregate liquidity. Using the Berger and Bouwman paradigm to quantify

liquidity generation, the dataset covers 2010–2017. Based on research, the total amount of created liquidity tripled in the mentioned period, and this created liquidity is more by liabilities than assets. In addition, they discover that Islamic banks have generated liquidity outside of their records as well as on them. While Islamic banks' loan-to-asset and deposit-to-asset ratios have been falling, their overall liquidity has risen. The fact that these ratios have been falling indicates that an extensive margin (i.e., larger banks in actual terms) rather than an intense margin (i.e., banks better at providing liquidity) has been the driving force behind the current trend.

Islamic banking differs from traditional banking in two key aspects, according to Halis and Eltawil (2017). These are the prohibition of interest and the sharing of profit and loss. For banks that are considering Islamic banking, these distinctions are significant. According to the findings, Islamic banking is just as risky as Western banking; the main differences lie in the origins and methods of risk management. Islamic banking has some distinct risks, such as equity investment risk, displaced commercial risk, Sharia non-compliance risk, and rate of return risk. The empirical portion of the study analyzes the risk management strategies used by Libyan Islamic financial institutions and concludes that factors unrelated to money pose the greatest threat. The authors conclude by making suggestions to help Libyan Islamic Banks improve their risk management practices.

Zarrouk et al (2016) aim to determine if the factors driving conventional banking profitability in the MENA area also influence Islamic banks' profitability. Islamic banking differs from traditional banking based on Sharia principles, likely impacting profitability. The study used the Generalized Method of Moment Estimators system on a dynamic panel data model to find the variables and macroeconomic variables that affected the profitability of central Islamic banks in the Middle East and North Africa from 1994 to 2012. According to the findings, cost-effectiveness, asset quality, and capitalization level positively affect bank profitability. According to research, Islamic banks may enhance their income streams via non-financing businesses. Islamic and conventional banks are

very comparable regarding the elements determining a bank's profitability. Islamic banks are less profitable when inflation is high.

Data analysis from the Conventional Stock, Islamic Stock, Bonds, and Sukuk Markets in Malaysia from 2007 to 2017 allowed researchers Ahmed and Elsayed (2019) to evaluate the decoupling hypotheses between conventional and Islamic stock markets. According to the total spillover index, conventional and Islamic markets rely highly on each other. On average, spillovers affect four markets, accounting for one-third of the total variance in prediction errors. Conventional, Islamic, and bond markets delivered tiny return shocks to Sukuk during the data period. Conversely, most spillovers to other markets came from the more conventional stock and bond markets. Compared to other markets, the interconnections and spillovers between sukuk and conventional bonds are significant, although they change over time. The divergent spillovers shown by sukuk and conventional bond indexes might be attributable to external variables, including the ongoing financial crisis, changes in the regulatory framework, and political unpredictability. It is also possible that the various contractual arrangements of these instruments are influencing the situation.

Ledhem (2022) studied the impact of the sukuk market's expansion on the security of Islamic banks. The focus of this study was the possible consequences of Islamic banks' association with the expansion of Sukuk for financial stability. This paper analyzes how the growing sukuk market affects the financial stability of Islamic banks using a dynamic panel system with a generalized approach to moments. By substituting the total quantity of sukuk issued with a proxy, researchers can monitor the growth of the sukuk market and assess the soundness of Islamic banks' finances using the Z-score model. All five sampled countries—Borneo, Indonesia, Türkiye, and Saudi Arabia—have Islamic banks. According to the research, sukuk market expansion favours Islamic banks' financial soundness by increasing their degree of complementarity. As a result, they can maintain their stability.

Using data from 22 countries from 1995 to 2019, Jatmiko et al. (2023) investigated the correlation between sukuk development and income inequality. According to the analysis, issuing the Sukuk would lead to a rise in income disparity, which utilized a two-stage fractional regression model. Here, the Islamic legal framework for sukuk explained the link between sukuk and wealth inequality that sidestepped problems in the credit market. For Sukuk to play a more positive role in social and economic development, the research recommends minimizing the adverse effects of Gharar (over-risk-taking) and Riba (endemic agency debt costs) and strengthening property rights within an ethical framework.

Balli et al (2022) investigate measures of the two-way spillovers between the sukuk (Islamic bond) market and the Sharia-compliant stock market. Various countries, Islamic equities, and sukuk markets exhibit distinct spillover paths and magnitudes. They find, which is new to the literature that the size of the market, the profitability and liquidity of Islamic firms, and the nature of the spillovers between the two markets all play significant roles. Sukuk and stock market spillovers are fewer for companies in deeper markets (those with a larger market capitalization) and more vital liquidity positions (lower debt-to-asset ratios). It is worth noting that corporations with broader markets and better profitability ratios have more considerable spillovers from the stock market to the Sukuk market. They also constructed a matched sample for the 38 companies that have issued Islamic stocks and sukuk. They show that applying the same spillover models to the matched sample can't separate the size of the sukuk-equities spillover from firm profitability and liquidity.

Boukhatem (2022) conducted an empirical method to probe the difficulties Sukuk market development (SMD) faced in Saudi Arabia. They retrieved data from comprehensive databases maintained by the Saudi Central Bank and the International Country Risk Guide (ICRG), covering the period from 2012 Q1 to 2021 Q1. The ARDL method is used to examine how financial risk factors affect the development of the Saudi sukuk market. The research suggests that stable currency rates, foreign debt, and debt servicing stability are the primary factors propelling the SMD in Saudi Arabia. However,

international liquidity and current account stability do not significantly influence this growth. The policy implications include the need for Saudi authorities to improve financial stability to foster a robust sukuk market.

Ibrahim (2015) introduces the special issue *Islamic Banking and Finance II* and presents several studies about the rapidly expanding Islamic finance sector. The article includes explicit analyses of the Islamic capital market and Islamic banking. Furthermore, the research points out that academic studies on Islamic finance primarily focused on testing claims that it differs from conventional finance using empirical means. In the suggestion section, more work is required to identify the availability of Islamic finance; future works should place the industry's foundation and make a proper setting based on theoretical statements that differ from conventional financing methods. Islamic finance's theoretical and practical dimensions should be integrated into economic well-being and policies such as economic development, stabilized policies, economic stability, and financial inclusion.

The effect of the growth of the Sukuk market on Islamic banks' capital ratios is investigated by Smaoui et al. (2020). Data was collected between 2005 and 2014, and 230 Islamic banks were analyzed. The capital requirements for Islamic banks include capital adequacy, capital-to-total asset ratios, and Tier 1 capital. To address any problems with simultaneity, endogeneity, and omitted variable bias. In conjunction with the system GMM estimator, the Prais-Winston method is used and concluded that Islamic banks' capital ratios have declined because of the Sukuk market's development. Furthermore, they contend that Islamic banks may have fostered lower capital ratios due to increased competition spurred by the emergence of Sukuk markets. Study findings also reveal that capital ratios are positively and strongly correlated with trade openness and bank liquidity, as expected, and negatively and significantly correlated with bank size and loan loss reserve ratio.

Khan et al (2022) analyzed sukuk tokenization based on a case study. The use of blockchain technology may help reduce the costs associated with tokenizing sukuk, as shown in the study. The high fees associated with sukuk are one of the primary reasons why it does not meet the financial needs of small and medium-sized businesses. The study examines the primary issues surrounding sukuk issuance and explores how blockchain technology can potentially address these issues. In addition, they classify the uses of blockchain technology in the financial sector, with an emphasis on Islamic finance. To determine which blockchain architectures are suitable for tokenization, the article examines several designs. The implementation of a simple, smart contract for Sukuk al-Murabaha on Ethereum allows them to perform a fresh case study on Sukuk tokenization. Finally, the research investigates a conceptual examination of practical considerations by contrasting the tokenization process with the Cost-Benefit Analysis of traditional sukuk issuing.

According to global empirical data supplied by Mseddi (2023), Sukuk securitization enhances originator firms' systematic risk development. Using a market-based approach, the research analyzes 68 sukuk issuances between 2004 and 2020. Next, they divide the data based on the announcement dates and the transactions. This study displays the various model parameters of systematic risk before, during, and after the event periods to show how systematic risk changes in this setting over time. The main findings indicate a decrease in systematic risk within approximately +/- 5 days before the announcement dates and Sukuk issuance. Some have speculated that sukuk holders take on more risk than the original project backers when firms use them to finance new ventures. Companies often allocate liquidity to riskier assets, influencing changes in financial leverage and capital structure, partially explaining the post-event increase in systematic risk.

Fauzi et al. (2016) shed light on the current situation of Malaysia's takaful, or insurance market, which complies with Shariah guidelines. The study reveals Takaful's successes and failures in Malaysia and provides an analysis of the practice. According to findings, takaful's growth in Malaysia is relatively small compared to conventional

insurance. Additionally, the takaful industry must quickly address several challenges to provide a viable alternative to conventional insurance.

Hassan et al (2018) explain the references to publications that examined the development and introduction of Takaful (Islamic insurance). The study examines the notion of Takaful, an Islamic approach to risk coverage and a substitute for traditional insurance. The mentioned research also goes into detail on the structure, mechanisms, and ways in which takaful insurance differs from traditional insurance. Furthermore, it outlines the Takaful models and classifications currently in use in the Takaful market. The study finishes with an analysis of the worldwide Takaful market, including its present state, potential future development, and recommendations for future paths.

Akhter (2010) identifies the different kinds of risks associated with Takaful business that impact the investment and operational functions of Takaful operators worldwide. To effectively manage these risks, the Takaful operator establishes certain criteria. Although Takaful operators often have trouble managing market and credit risks, this is because Takaful contracts are Shariah-compliant, which means that Takaful businesses can't do things with interest rates and financial derivatives that all Islamic jurists agree are wrong. Further research investigates Islamic financial instruments such as cooperative hedging and bilateral mutual adjustment, which aim to provide mutual benefits to both parties through risk sharing and could serve as a substitute for conventional derivatives. The study lays out a plan for how Takaful operators might improve their risk management culture. The text also addresses the obstacles that Takaful operators must overcome to improve their risk management techniques.

Pasha et al (2013) reviewed the relevant literature and described and examined numerous Takaful business models. The study focuses on the Modaraba, Wakala, Ta'awun, and Wakala-Waqf models. Additionally, they conducted a quick comparison of various Takaful business models.

Poan et al. (2022) analyzes how trust relates to awareness, attitude, subjective norms, and religion in Indonesia and how this affects purchase intention for takaful. Using an online questionnaire, this quantitative research in Indonesia collected 322 valid replies from people who are presently insured, knowledgeable of takaful, and interested in risk hedging. Using the structural equation model, they evaluated the outcomes and tested the hypotheses. According to the research, there is a strong relationship between trust and the desire to buy Islamic insurance and between trust and awareness, religiosity, and subjective standards. Furthermore, they found no significant correlation with the attitude toward trust.

Shukor (2020) identifies the elements that contribute to the development of trust in takaful agents, as well as the resulting outcomes. They gathered the data through a questionnaire and conducted descriptive, exploratory factor, and structural equation modelling analyses. The findings suggest that takaful agents' communication skills, level of experience, and image of the takaful operator they represent all have an impact on consumers' trust in them. Additionally, consumers' level of trust in takaful agents influences their loyalty and desire to stick with the current agent.

Eldaia et al. (2023) investigate takaful companies licensed by the Central Bank of Malaysia and how their performance is correlated with the board of directors' effectiveness (BODE). Furthermore, it focuses on how Shariah Committee Quality (SCQ) influences the correlation between BODE and the company's performance. This research considers a sample of eleven Takaful firms in Malaysia from 2010 to 2017. Indexes quantify BDE and SCQ, whereas ROA and ROE are performance proxies. A panel fixed-effect regression analysis examines the relationship between the BDE and the financial performance of Takaful firms in Malaysia and the moderating influence of SCQ. The study's primary conclusion is that BDE is positively associated with performance. Malaysian Takaful firms perform better when their boards consist of several independent, Muslim, and female directors. Another notable finding is that SCQ has a positive moderating effect on the association between BDE and performance. The results suggest

that combining a high SCQ level with a high board effectiveness level may improve performance.

Hanif et al (2014) gave an overview of the insurance industry, which included Islamic insurance (Takaful), a comparison of traditional and Islamic insurance, information about the legal framework and accounting for Takaful, customer surveys to find out how they felt about the takaful business, and information about and documentation of the problems that come up when running Takaful. The study highlighted that Takaful has a quickly increasing rate but seems to have a low market share. The previous performance was very poor, but robust growth indicates significant promise. The findings of the article concluded that the perception and regulation of Takaful in Pakistan are excellent to adopt.

Almulhim (2019) determines the leading production stage after analyzing the Saudi Arabian insurance market's performance using a two-stage data envelopment analysis. Using data collected from 26 traditional insurance companies and 7 Takaful insurance companies between 2014 and 2017, the researchers found that both organizations had falling average efficiency ratings. Stated differently, new policies about foreign involvement and consolidation are necessary in the Saudi Arabian insurance sector to support the growth and development of companies. Furthermore, the study offers implications for executives, managers, and decision-makers who are involved in the insurance sector in Saudi Arabia and other developing insurance markets.

Ansari (2022) provided a summary of the indexed and existing Takaful-related articles in the Scopus database from 2000 to 2019, along with recommendations for future research directions. Researchers classify articles on topics such as consumer behaviour, takaful models, financial and non-financial performance, human resources, and governance based on their distinct themes. Researchers have extensively studied marketing, finance, human resources, governance, and the legal aspects of takaful. Different studies have employed both quantitative and qualitative approaches. This study

has identified research gaps across various domains. Studies that use behavioral theories to investigate the behavioral intention to use takaful services make up a significant portion of the existing amount of takaful research.

Hryhoruk et al (2019) assess the degree of economic development in different locations using composite index evaluation technology. They present a composite index constructed using block convolution of two sets of partial indicators. The first set of indicators is based on absolute values. A second set of metrics is based on relative dynamics. Each group proposed a data normalization procedure and a convolution method for the partial composite index. They provide a method for finding the boundaries of intervals on the composite index scale for each stage of economic development to categorize Ukraine's regions. Apart from creating a composite index and an initial set of indicators, different activities can utilize the presented methods for identifying the boundaries of data groupings within intervals. The estimated findings may be used in the decision-making system as primary data for further computations and as a benchmark for identifying the directions of socio-economic development.

Liu et al. (2014) evaluate intellectual capital at the regional level. In 2012, they assessed the RIC of seventeen Shandong Province cities to examine RIC's impact on regional economic growth impartially. RIC and the growth of local economies are complementary. However, the extent to which it has aided economic growth remains debated. Furthermore, the quantity of RIC differs throughout the nation. In the final section of the study, they provide some pertinent remarks and recommendations about the development of the regional economy in various parts of Shandong Province based on empirical findings.

Stehlíková (2024) examined the impact of a pandemic on the economic situation of the mining and construction sectors as primary and secondary sectors, respectively. The study used economic and financial indicators, which mostly affect future crisis companies. The study's results indicate that both sectors need to effectively manage the significant

decline and bankruptcy of certain companies within the industry. This result could be used to forecast and model the socio-economic development of regions and nations. The growth of the analyzed sectors contributes to the companies' efforts to ensure sustainable development in the country.

Santillán et al (2024) provide recommendations for workable approaches to Mexico's economic development via the nearshoring trend. It included examining the potential benefits of nearshoring to Mexico and determining, evaluating, and classifying the factors that led to the dispute over trade between China and the United States. Two study objects—the Sino-American rivalry over international trade and nearshoring to Mexico—were the basis for the use of qualitative research methodologies and documentary research techniques. The advantages of free trade agreements in terms of tariffs, cheap labour costs for industrial firms, and stable currency rates are some elements that propel nearshoring to Mexico. To capitalize on this trend, Mexico should build better ports, roads, and air infrastructure, establish a solid public security policy, provide tax incentives to entice Foreign Direct Investment and promote the construction of industrial parks.

Zdravković et al (2024) examine the connection between freshwater abstraction and economic development to see how it affects Europe. The research covers a total of 19 European nations between 2007 and 2018, including 18 EU members and 1 candidate. Per Capita GDP, the Human Development Index, Water Productivity, and the Volume of International Trade were among the several economic development variables tested in a panel dataset to determine their impact on freshwater abstraction. The research shows that all of the explanatory factors matter significantly, except international trade, when it comes to cross-country differences. To keep within its bounds, the research does not include climate change or the accessibility of water supplies; instead, it concentrates on measures of economic development.

Huang (2020) intends to resolve China's fundamental economic problems. Factor input, structural optimization, and institutional reform are the three lynchpins of China's economic development, keeping the country's potential growth rate within a sustainable range and ensuring the economy grows steadily over the long term. The essential elements of economic growth are the circumstances under which economic activity occurs, as characterized by the main parts of a country and their trend throughout time. These conditions are characterized by stability, internality, and persistence. An economy is considered stable when it operates steadily within an acceptable growth range at a specific stage of development. However, this does not exclude the possibility of extraordinary economic swings in specific years brought on by unforeseen short-term causes. For instance, a consistently high growth rate distinguished the Chinese economy's foundations during the post-reform and post-opening-up eras.

Rafindadi et al. (2023) set out to conduct an unbiased study of the impact of globalization, financial development, and capital accumulation on the GDP growth and energy consumption of Saudi Arabia (a prominent OPEC powerhouse and an Arab energy icon nation) between 1971 and 2015. According to the study, globalization and financial growth, rather than economic expansion, increase energy consumption. The country's energy consumption went up as a result of capital accumulation as well. The findings of the variance decomposition show that, during 15 years, energy consumption was considerably affected by inventive shocks in globalization (15.28 per cent) and by financial growth (28.98 per cent). In contrast, capital accumulation shocks had a relatively minor effect, contributing only about 1.24% of the changes in energy consumption. The impulse response function results also show that shocks to financial development had a big effect on globalization and economic development and that capital accumulation sped up financial development by a lot. This study's conclusions highlight implications for advancing sustainable energy systems that capitalize on the advantages of globalization, financial development, and capital accumulation.

Alhassan et al (2023) examine how information and communication technologies (ICT) and economic and sustainable development are related on a worldwide scale. They evaluate the capability approach-based research model using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling and archival data from 130 nations worldwide. The results indicate that the availability and use of ICT have a substantial impact on a country's achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). While access to ICT is essential for fostering economic development, its actual use does not have the same impact. Furthermore, the findings indicate that economic development plays a critical role in mediating the relationship between ICT access and SDGs, but not between ICT use and SDGs. Governments must ensure that affordable use fees accompany ICT access to realize the full benefits of economic and sustainable development.

Lal et al (2021) aim to examine how financial inclusion affects the economic development of underprivileged communities through socio-economic empowerment. They collected data from April to August of 2020. Data analysis and scale purification were carried out using multivariate statistical methods, including EFA, CFA, and SEM. The study's findings demonstrate that financial inclusion, which in turn influences social and economic empowerment, influences the economic growth of less fortunate communities. According to the research, even though the government has made efforts to increase access to financial services, many banks still refuse to lend to underserved areas. This is due to low levels of education, illiteracy, awareness, bankers' mindsets, and government policies that limit their ability to handle financial crises on their own.

Mohieldin et al. (2019) seek to examine significant advancements in Egypt's financial growth and the progression of the nation's banking sector. This research aims to empirically examine the relationship between Egypt's economic growth and financial development from 1980 to 2016. In this study, they compare Egypt to a few other developing economies and emerging markets using key financial metrics. The study applied bivariate regression modelling to the time series data, revealing a strong correlation between real growth per capita and financial development, as measured by the

money supply to GDP. Real per capita income does not correlate with access to or efficiency of banking services, and real GDP per capita is robustly associated with the financial market access index.

The authors Bruneckiend' et al. (2023) investigate patterns of smart economic development in Europe and explore their connection to competitiveness. The reevaluation of development policies aimed at increasing competitiveness and decreasing economic development disparities has been prompted by economic shocks such as the 2008 financial crisis, Brexit, the coronavirus pandemic, and global events such as the fourth industrial revolution and the shift to a low-carbon economy. The inquiry includes

- A comparison of the structure of intelligent economic development indicators,
- A study of self-organizing neural networks and
- An estimate of the Cumulative Index with the World Economic Forum's (WEF) Global Competitiveness Index.

Panel data for 30 European states covering the years 2000–2018 make up the dataset. In general, when looking at various countries, the results reveal that more competitive European countries are more likely to have higher estimates of innovative economic development. The primary factors that influence the outcome are legal equity, societal accountability, skill development, intellectual capacity, and gainful work to establish intelligent strategies for achieving more successful competitiveness.

Mahajan (2013) Explained that the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) presented the Human Development Index (HDI) in their first report on human development in 1990. The HDI ratings rank and categorize countries worldwide, revealing their human development profiles. Since then, there has been much interest in the HDI from development theorists, policymakers, and critics. The HDI's methodology has changed periodically in response to diverse opinions and viewpoints. This study made a modest attempt to shed light on such modifications.

Sheth et al. (2020) explain the community human development index, which is a multidimensional index that assesses human achievement in different dimensions throughout the country, state, city, and neighborhood levels to facilitate the advancement localization of United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (UNSDGs). Presently, the Human Development Index (HDI) is a frequently used indicator that combines income, education, and life expectancy to measure the development of a country. Nevertheless, national averages need to reveal significant discrepancies across states, cities, and smaller neighborhoods within major metropolitan centers. The CHDI model aims to enhance comprehension of variations in human development within urban areas and among different populations at a regional level. They conducted a comprehensive analysis by calculating the CHDI for almost every census tract in the state of Illinois in the United States. The investigation revealed notable discrepancies in the degrees of development at the municipal level in Illinois. Furthermore, it emphasized disparities among various populations residing inside cities, particularly the city of Chicago. The findings indicate that it is possible to break down, compute, evaluate, and compare multidimensional indices designed to monitor sustainable development on a national level, regardless of their size. Researchers and policymakers may use the CHDI model to discover, visualize, and solve local disparities. They also use the model to build and execute evidence-based, tailored solutions at the community level.

Germán et al (2021) study provides empirical evidence of the correlation between human capital and technology on the Human Development Index (HDI) of Latin America. To illustrate the current correlation, panel data from 12 Latin American nations was analyzed. The World Bank's Atlas method divided these nations into three groups based on their income levels. The high-income group consisted of Chile, Panama, Uruguay, and Mexico. The middle-income group included Argentina, Brazil, Colombia, and Ecuador. Lastly, the low-income group comprised Peru, Bolivia, Honduras, and Nicaragua. The findings supported the notion by showing that, in low- and middle-income countries, the technology variable had a positive influence on the HDI, with the impact being more substantial in these nations. Nonetheless, there is a negative correlation between

technology and HDI in high-income nations. To enhance people's quality of life, governments must prioritize the development of human capital and opportunities for personal technology access.

The elements that affect the West Java Province HDI are identified and analyzed by Franciscus et al. (2022). They use the Weighted Geographic Regression (GWR) model in conjunction with the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model to compare spatial versus non-spatial approaches. The researchers analyzed data from 27 districts in West Java province, sourced from the Indonesian Central Statistics Agency, using six quantitative indicators related to HDI: open unemployment, life expectancy, predicted length of schooling, the average length of education, per capita spending, and the number of public health centers. This study found that in West Java, four variables—life expectancy, average education level, length of education, and expenditure per capita—significantly affect HDI figures. Compared to OLS technology, GWR performs better, with R^2 and AIC values of 99.24% and 35.10, respectively. Additional studies are advanced by using robust regression to tackle outliers in several areas and include significant elements that impact local policies.

Malcom et al (2021) used the Kudumbashree model to investigate the relationship between microfinance institutions (MFIs) and the Human Development Index (HDI) in Kerala, India. This research examined the impact of Microfinance Institutions (MFIs) on income, education, and women's empowerment—the three main determinants of human development. Through a critical analysis of the Kudumbashree model, the researcher determined that microfinance institutions (MFIs) have a positive impact on human development indicators. In addition to increasing income and savings levels, MFIs empower female members and provide them with access to educational programs and skill-training schemes.

Khare and Kumar (2016). looked at the size optimization of hybrid systems using SP, WP, BEP, and DGP generating units (diesel generator power). In addition, the research looked at the Human Development Index and how to make the most of

employment growth. Since the Human Development Index (HDI) depends on electricity consumption, generating and distributing excess energy by a hybrid system may increase the HDI. Employment creation will depend on various configurations of generating units of hybrid system and varies accordingly. The system under consideration is optimized using Bare Bone Particle Swarm Optimization (BBPSO). A comparison has been made between three distinct solar panel technologies. A comparison of the findings with different technologies reveals that AP-120 performs the best.

Hijazi et al. (2018) explain the well-known and largely used Fisher and Relief scores for supervised feature selection. They propose using these scores to identify the human development indicators that have the most impact on the development classes in the various Middle Eastern nations. The experimental results demonstrate the importance of indicator selection. Furthermore, they shed light on the importance of certain indicators of women's involvement in the labor force for the development of these Middle Eastern nations.

Gubarev et al. (2017) analyzed quality-of-life indices with living standards at both macroeconomic and microeconomic levels. To measure living standards, they used different nations' HDI, GDP per capita, and regional unemployment rates. Their research outputs include nations' HDI growth predictions, the optimal trend for GDP per capita, and the regions' unemployment rate distributions.

Researchers Ochoa et al. (2019) looked at Mexico's plan to boost digitization, which included funding digital literacy programs and installing internet connection points in public places nationwide. An analysis of the correlation between the 32 Mexican states and the HDI was suggested in the research. The research findings reveal a positive correlation: an increase of 1% in internet access for the household number leads to a corresponding increase of 0.02% HDI. A 1% decrease in internet access will result in a 0.07% decrease in the HDI. The study highlights policy recommendations for digital inclusion strategies to support human development.

Costa et al (2017) conducted a multivariate analysis of the Human Development Index (HDI) data for the years 1991, 2000, and 2010 in 167 municipalities in the state of Rio Grande do Norte, located in northeast Brazil. The use of self-organizing maps (Kohonen or SOM) facilitated the execution of clustering and data visualization tasks. Following SOM training, the method employs map segmentation using the k-means algorithm. Based on transition analysis from municipalities across various analyzed years, they rank clusters according to the three primary HDI aspects. Each time, intragroup commonalities and intergroup dissimilarities led to five distinct groupings of municipalities. The segmented maps show comparable towns. After the data is clustered, thematic maps of the area are also shown.

Al fathan and Arundina (2019). aim to investigate the relationship between the expansion of Islamic financing and Indonesia's economic progress. They will specifically examine the Islamic stock market, the advancements in Islamic banking, and the sukuk market. A Vector Autoregressive (VAR) Model, including Granger Causality and an Impulse Response Function, examines the relationship between Islamic finance and economic development. The objective is to identify the connection between various domains of Islamic finance and the causal connections between them. The study determined that expanding Islamic stock markets and banking supports the neutrality theory. The expansion of the sukuk market supports the supply-leading argument. Furthermore, the study demonstrated that the expansion of Sukuk markets fosters the advancement of Islamic banking, which subsequently promotes the Islamic stock market.

Ben Jedidia Khoutem (2014) aims to analyze the potential of Islamic financing to stimulate economic growth in Tunisia after the 2011 revolution. This article specifically seeks to investigate the linkages between Islamic banks and Sukuk markets that are more favourable to economic development. The authors of this research conclude that marketable Islamic intermediation may help alleviate poverty and unemployment by facilitating the flow of capital into the economy. Furthermore, it shows that banks may play a more significant role in the Sukuk markets, which can increase Islamic

intermediation. This paves the way to solving several issues with long-term investment, risk-taking, bank liquidity management, and saving mobilization. In terms of economic policy, the author suggests that Tunisia implement stringent regulations to foster accountability, disclosure laws, and transparency.

Solo et al. (2024) aim to analyze the impact of financial development on the economic growth of regions that have significant Islamic finance systems. The primary method used by the authors was a variety of estimated methods, with the least squares dummy variable corrected (LSDVC) method being applied to 23 countries over a timeframe spanning from 2000 to 2019. The results indicate that the financial sector may not have a substantial impact on economic growth, or it may even have a negative effect, depending on the proxy used. These findings are consistent with current research and remain strong regardless of the various estimating parameters and methodologies used. Finance practitioners should reassess their everyday operations since their influence on economic development is diminishing. In a similar vein, policymakers need to consider other variables that can affect the contribution of financial development to economic growth. It may be important to examine how institutional development modifies the link between growth and finance, as well as how financial development might support economic growth. Studying how Islamic financing affects economic development using various data sources may also be beneficial.

A study conducted by Zarrouk et al. (2017) delves into the relationship between the expansion of Islamic financial institutions and the actual GDP in the United Arab Emirates. They looked at the relationship and possible causes of Financial Development, Islamic Finance, and Economic Growth using a Bivariate Vector Autoregressive Model with time series data from 1990 to 2012. The study also predicted future growth under various settings using this model. Instead of more conventional measures of economic growth, they developed a composite indicator using non-parametric data envelope analysis. As the results show, there is no negative link between Islamic financial development and actual gross domestic product (GDP); financial development propels

economic expansion. Another finding from the predictions is that the relationship between financial development and actual economic activity has served as a stand-in for both the past and the future. The growth of Islamic banking is not going away.

Gani et al (2021) investigate the dynamic assessment of Islamic finance's contribution to the real economy of Malaysia. This research examines cointegration using the autoregressive distributive lag bounds test on a 20-year quarterly data set. Findings reveal that Islamic banking indices and the actual economy do not have a meaningful link in the short run. Conversely, in the long run, the Malaysian economy's flourishing is positively correlated with Islamic banks' deposits and financing. The study concluded that Islamic banks have a strong bidirectional causal relationship with Malaysia's GDP, while the influence of Islamic banking financing on GDP is weak.

The purpose of Zafar et al. (2024) is to conduct a comprehensive literature assessment on Islamic banking and human capital. They used two popular academic databases, Scopus and Web of Science, to discover relevant papers for their systematic literature review. This study, in conjunction with previous research reviews, focuses on three main topics: human capital measurement techniques, human capital determinants, and the relationship between human capital and the performance of Islamic banks. Study findings indicate that ground-breaking research has focused only on human capital in Islamic banking; others have included it in the more general concept of intellectual capital. Some have used disclosure and survey approaches, but accounting-based methods continue to be the most popular for assessing human capital. While several studies have investigated the connection between human capital and financial performance, very few have investigated the factors that influence human capital, with an emphasis on corporate governance.

Ledhem et al. (2021) empirically investigated the relationship between Islamic financing and economic development in Southeast Asia using the Endogenous Growth Model. With an emphasis on Southeast Asian nations, including Brunei Darussalam,

Indonesia, and Malaysia, The Study applied the Dynamic Panel One-Step System GMM Model to a data set covering six years, from 2013 to 2019. According to the results, Islamic money is a massive boon to the economies of Southeast Asian nations and helps them expand.

To investigate the connection between Islamic finance and Türkiye's economic development, Ledhem et al. (2022) used the endogenous growth model. The association between variables is discovered by combining data from several Turkish bank databases that have committed to serving the nation using the Markov Chain Marginal Bootstrap Resampling Technique. Islamic finance contributes to the expansion of the Turkish economy, according to the New Turkish Economy Program (2019–2021). This research aims to increase the share of Islamic finance in Türkiye's banking sector and international markets, which aims to spur economic growth.

The effect of interest rates and Murabaha on the financial crisis of 2008 was studied by Almsafir et al. (2014). With time series data spanning 1984–2012, this research used six variables: interest rates, GDP, unemployment, inflation, and the Murabaha rate. This study's findings suggest that changes in macroeconomic factors have a more rapid influence on Murabaha than on interest rates. The study's conclusions provide further evidence of Islamic finance's value as an alternative to traditional financing.

Ghroubi (2023) intends to study the connection between GDP growth, bank lending, and capital regulation within the context of a dual market. During the study's 20 years, participants came from 13 Muslim nations in Southeast Asia and the Middle East, representing 46 Islamic and 113 conventional banks. The study examines and proves that an increase in loan growth positively influences economic development within the context of Islamic banking using an unrelated regression technique. A slowdown in loan growth is inevitable when the capital ratio is raised, but economic development is still boosted. The results of Stewart et al. (2021), who argue that capital regulation boosts GDP growth and decreases credit volatility, are supported by this study. However, the effect of

increased loan growth (LOANG) on GDP per capita growth (GDPCG) is still being determined when it comes to conventional banks. However, the capital ratio boosts GDPCG and promotes LOANG, leading to an increase in risk.

Islamic banks (IBs) and macroeconomic factors are the focus of Kismawadi's (2023) research, which seeks to analyze their effects on the economic growth of Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, Malaysia, Qatar, Bahrain, and Bangladesh. The findings reveal that 24 Islamic financial institutions in the nations above use variance decomposition, impulse response functions (IRFs), and time series data. According to the results, Islamic banking helps boost economies, especially in the UAE, Bahrain, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and Qatar. In terms of Islamic banking, the results of the VDC test impact the economy's growth in the long run.

Pratiwi (2016) uses the Tawhidi String Relation (TSR) technique to build a micro-macro circular causal model and looks for potential barriers to sustainable economic development. According to the study's findings, Indonesia's economic goal and the current state of Islamic banking are entirely unrelated. The Islamic banking contracts Musharakah and Mudarabah showed a good correlation with the financial performance indicator of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. So, these two forms of UMKM partnership finance arrangements should get greater attention from Islamic banks. In addition, increasing its volume and value is essential for laying a long-term socioeconomic foundation in Indonesia. After that, GDP growth will be positive and achievable.

Hattar (2016) examined how the top leadership at a successful American bank managed the efficiency changes that came with the 2008 financial crisis. Data is gathered through semi-structured interviews, annual fiscal reports, and proxy statements and analyzed using Yin's method. The study constructs three themes that emerge in management strategies: the application of digital technology, growth maximization, and risk elimination. The study implies that governments do not support failed banks in accessing a more robust economy.

Ibrahim (2022) examines the effects of Islamic financing on energy efficiency from an empirical perspective. It also delves into how Islamic finance may use various financial tools to help circular enterprises raise capital. According to the data, the nation's implementation of Islamic finance has seen a decline in energy efficiency. In addition, there is an opportunity for renewal, virtualization, exchange, optimization, sharing, and closing the loops to achieve circular economy development in Qatar's electricity and transportation sectors and the country's agriculture and water supply systems, according to the report. The paper also claims that Islamic finance can help circular businesses reach their full potential through caring contracts, equity financing models, and risk-sharing. To fully integrate renewable energy into a circular economy, the research suggests implementing the Community Green Waqf (CGW) funding model. This approach combines the efforts of community organizations, commercial companies, and charitable institutions to ensure the success and adoption of renewable energy projects in rural areas.

Belkhaoui (2023) conducts an experimental investigation into the ways in which conventional and Islamic banking might promote economic development in the MENA region. The study looks into the connections between Islamic Banking, the growth of conventional banks, and economic growth using a Panel Granger Causality Test, a Panel-Based Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), and a Panel Cointegration Technique. Islamic banking in MENA countries promotes economic growth and positively affects the evolution of conventional banking, according to the empirical results. Since the expansion of Islamic banking directly impacts GDP growth, it is classified as supply-following by them. Traditional banking, in contrast, is demand-following and plays a passive role; it reacts only to changes in the economy's trajectory over the long run.

Both the long-term and short-term relationships between Islamic banking and the growth of Nigeria's economy are examined by Tabash et al. (2022). They tested time series data from 2013 to 2020 using ARDL and ECM. According to the data, Nigeria's Islamic banking and GDP development exhibit a small but beneficial link.

Chowdhury et al. (2018) wants to examine the connection between EG and Islamic finance principles by focusing on two particular Islamic financing concepts- non-risk sharing and risk sharing. Using ARDL and Continuous Wavelet Transform Approaches, researchers have collected data for approximately 30 years (1984–2014). According to the results, risk-sharing instruments positively correlate with economic growth, whereas non-risk-sharing instruments correlate negatively.

Alam et al. (2022) use the concepts of participatory finance, often called Islamic finance, to analyze the problems hindering Türkiye's economic growth and provide remedies. Goals for Türkiye's economic development considering growth, per capita income, inflation, unemployment, and young unemployment were the subjects of a critical literature study. According to the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, Türkiye's banking system in 2019 saw declining asset quality, deleveraged lenders, market instability, decreased investor confidence, and weak governmental and private investment. Similarly, the traditional literature on finance demonstrates that strategic financial choices can improve these problems. Islamic financial literature, on the other hand, proved that interest-free financial systems are more robust and help the economy grow sustainably. While the amount of participation in Islamic finance makes its contributions small, the method of financing has enormous potential to benefit Türkiye's economy, as demonstrated in other nations. The current Turkish government has committed to participating in Islamic banking, with an expected asset level of 15% by 2025.

Impact of Malaysia's Capital Market on Economic Development From 1998 To 2018, Specifically the Influence of Sukuk and Other Market Subcomponents, is the topic of Tan et al.'s (2021) study. Findings suggest a correlation between capital market traits and GDP growth over the long run. One side of the coin is that bond market components, especially sukuk and conventional bonds, contribute positively but marginally to GDP growth. Conversely, studies show that improvements to stock markets, irrespective of the metric used to quantify economic growth, have substantial and beneficial effects in the

long run. According to the report, the stock market's components are the most critical factors influencing Malaysia's economic growth.

Caporale et al (2018) compare two groups of seven developing nations: one without Islamic banks and another with a hybrid system incorporating Islamic and conventional banking practices. They look at how Islamic banking has affected financial lending and GDP correlations. Unlike earlier research, it applies both time series and panel techniques to assess the conclusions' robustness. They also check for long- and short-term causation. In sum, the results show that the two groups of nations are quite different from one another, which is reflective of the unique characteristics of Islamic banks. The time series analysis shows a long-term causal relationship between loans and GDP in nations where Islamic banks are prevalent. The panel causality tests validate this; however, in this instance, there is also evidence of short-run causation in nations without Islamic banks.

Elmawazini et al. examine the impact of Islamic and commercial banks on the GDP growth of GCC nations from 2001 to 2009 and from 2010 to 2017 in their 2020 research. The authors used the Cross-Sectionally Correlated and Time-Wise Autoregressive (CCTA) model to enhance Pagano's (1993) theoretical endogenous growth model while creating Islamic and commercial financial markets. Before and after the financial crisis of 2008, the writers contend that Islamic banks were more helpful to economic growth than traditional banks. Despite being an important component, finance does not follow GDP growth. Given these results, it is reasonable to assume that Islamic financial ethics may contribute positively to GDP growth.

Lebdaoui & Wild (2016). analyzed the effect of Islamic banks on the economic growth of countries in Southeast Asia. Between 2000 and 2012, they gathered data in Southeast Asian nations using the ARDL and another model. According to the research, Islamic banking and economic growth have a long-term correlation, not a short-term one. The proportion of the Islamic financial sector affects GDP growth in Southeast Asian nations, and this effect is positively and substantially correlated with population rates.

Ehigiamusoe et al. (2021) examine the factors that mitigate the impact of financial development on GDP growth by drawing on theoretical and empirical data. Institutions, macroeconomic stability, and economic and financial development levels all have a moderating role in the relationship between finance and growth. Nations that are well-developed economically and financially have solid institutions and are relatively stable economically may see financial development boost economic growth. In contrast, nations that are less developed may have the opposite impact. They also show that when the amount of money in circulation is too high, it stunts rather than helps economic growth, suggesting that we have reached a tipping point in the evolution of financial markets. According to the findings, an ideal financial and economic development level, a more robust institutional framework, and a steady macroeconomic climate are necessary to foster economic growth. So, countries that want to boost their economy via the banking system should put these things in the correct order of importance.

A quarterly data set for Malaysia spanning 1998-2013 is used by Kassim (2016) to empirically assess the effect of Islamic financing on vital macroeconomic indicators' performance using the ARDL method. The findings indicate that Islamic finance is starting to significantly impact the actual economy by streamlining the process of combining and investing money. Constant effort is needed to encourage the expansion of Islamic finance because of its substantial contributions to the Malaysian economy. By enhancing the regulatory and legal environment to support the development of businesses, Malaysia is further establishing itself as a global leader in Islamic finance.

Çinar et al. (2022) use data from different areas of Türkiye to investigate the correlation between Islamic banking and GDP growth. This research shows that Islamic banking does not boost GDP growth anytime soon. According to a combination of positive and negative assessments for conventional and Islamic banking features, consumers in Türkiye see conventional loans as alternatives to Islamic banking loans rather than complementary services.

The final 25 reports examine the Impact of Islamic Finance on Economic Development across various regions and countries, utilizing varying research methodologies to assess the significance of the findings and make significant contributions to the existing literature. We first analyze and summarize the summing table of these 25 academic articles, identifying the author of each article, the published source, the variables and methodology employed, and, ultimately, the study's findings.

Table 2.2. Systematic Literature Review

No	Author/ Authors	Year of Publication	Journal /Universities	Analytical Approach	Findings
1	Ryanda Al Fathan; Tika Arundina	2019	International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management	(VAR) Model	Economic growth is unrelated to the expansion of Islamic financial institutions and stock markets. Growth in the Islamic sukuk market directly correlates to economic expansion. Furthermore, this study found that the growth of the sukuk market is directly related to the expansion of Islamic banking and the Islamic stock market. Additionally, it demonstrates that Islamic banking and stock growth are unrelated.
2	Daoud Ben Jedidia Khoutem	2014	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	Review	Islamic banks and Sukuk markets are positively correlated and crucial in boosting the country's economic development.
3	Edib Smolo; Ruslan Nagayev	2024	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	LSDVC	The research shows that when other proxies are employed, the financial industry's impact on economic growth decreases, and it is not even a significant component.
4	Hajer Zarrouk; Teheni El Ghak; Elias Abu Al Haija	2017	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	Bivariate Vector Autoregressive Model; Data Envelopment Analysis	Financial development could contribute to economic growth, but the real GDP could cause Islamic financial development. Furthermore, evidence from the study revealed no reverse effect between variables in the relationship mentioned above.
5	Ibrahim Musa Gani; Zakaria Bahari	2021	ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance	ARDL	There is no correlation between the Islamic banking index and GDP in the near term, but Islamic deposits and financing do help the

					country's actual economy in the long term. A weak causal association exists between GDP and Islamic bank funding in Malaysia, but a bidirectional causal relationship exists between Islamic bank deposits and Malaysian GDP.
6	Muhammad Bilal Zafar; Ahmad Jafar	2024	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	Review	Some research looked at intellectual capital, while others looked at human capital regarding Islamic finance. Accounting is the backbone of most common approaches to measuring human capital. However, transparency and survey methodologies have also found some use. Several studies have examined the correlation between human capital and financial performance. However, the variables influencing human capital and its link to corporate governance have received less attention.
7	Mohammed Ayoub Ledhem; Mohammed Mekidiche	2021	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	A One-Step System GMM Dynamic Panel Model	Islamic finance has a key and contributing role towards GDP in Asian countries.
8	Mohammed Ayoub Ledhem; Mohammed Mekidiche	2022	ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance	Quantile Regression with the Markov Chain Marginal Bootstrap Resampling Technique	Islamic financing is helping Türkiye's economy flourish, which is in line with the goals of the New Turkish Economy Program (2019–2021). The expansion of Islamic finance inside Türkiye's banking system and beyond is one of the primary goals of this initiative, which is designed to stimulate economic development.
9	Mahmoud Khalid Almsafir; Ayman Abdalmajeed Alsmadi	2014	Procedia- Social and Behavioural Sciences	ARDL	The effect of macroeconomic variables on Murabaha is acceptable compared to the interest rate, which means Murabaha quickly made the equilibrium compared to the interest rate.

					Policymakers should pay attention to alternate conventional finance with Islamic finance.
10	Mohamed Ghroubi	2023	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	Seemingly Unrelated Regression Method	<p>The study applies the regression model to 3 different equations of the study where in each equation, the dependent variable changes to determine the coefficient of the independent variable.</p> <p>CPTA, LOANG, ZROA, INF, TRADEOP, and REV2011 have positive and significant correlations with GDPCG, while LTA, SIZE, BRMMONEY, SUBP2008 and COV2019 have negative and significant effects.</p> <p>GDPCG, ZROA, SIZE, SUBP2008 and REV 2011 have positive and significant effects on CPTA while LOANG, LTA, FTD, INF and BRMMONEY have a negative and significant effect on CPTA.</p> <p>GDPCG, TRADEOP, REV2011, SUBP2008 and COV19 have positive and significant roles on LOANG, while CPTA, FTD, CTI, INF and BRMMONEY have negative and significant effects on LOANG.</p>
11	Early Ridho Kismawadi	2021	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	VECM Approach	Islamic banking promotes economic growth in Bangladesh, Malaysia, Qatar, Bahrain, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and UAE. The study finds that Islamic banks have a direct and long-term effect on economic growth.
12	Ari Pratiwi	2016	Humanomics	Tawhidi String Relation	According to the study, Islamic banking has nothing to do with Indonesia's economic policy objectives. Islamic banking's financing

					mechanisms, such as Musharakah and Murabaha contracts, benefit micro, small, and medium-sized businesses, which boosts their financial performance index.
13	Adeeb Seman Hattar	2016	Walden University	Yin's method	The study advances business practices by disseminating the finest strategic approaches used by the executives of a prosperous American bank to pinpoint changes in operational efficiency that occurred during the financial crisis.
14	Abdul-Jalil Ibrahim	2022	Hamad Bin Khalifa University	Fixed Effect Approach	The empirical results suggest that the nations being studied have energy inefficiency due to the growth of the Islamic finance system. The paper also shows how the Qatari economy's water supply system, agricultural, transportation, and electrical sectors all have opportunities for circular economy development via virtualization, exchange, optimization, sharing, and looping closure. The research also shows that Islamic finance can use equity-like financing and risk-sharing financing to encourage circular businesses, which aligns with the overall goal of Maqasid. The research suggests using the Community Green Waqf funding model to fully integrate renewable energy into a circular economy. This approach combines the efforts of community organizations, commercial companies, and charitable organizations to enhance the feasibility and adoption of renewable energy projects in rural areas.
15	Samir Belkhaoui	2023	Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research	Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)	The empirical findings demonstrate that Islamic banking in (MENA) not only contributes to economic growth but also has a favorable and notable impact on conventional banking growth. As a result, they categorize Islamic banking as

					supply-following because of its active role in promoting economic growth. In contrast, conventional banking plays a passive role (demand-following), responding only to long-term economic growth.
16	Mosab I. Tabash; Fatima Muhammad Abdulkarim; Mustapha Ishaq Akinlaso; Raj S. Dhankar	2022	African Journal of Economic and Management Studies	ARDL	The findings indicate that Islamic banking positively impacts Nigeria's economy in both the short and long term; nevertheless, this impact is insignificant.
17	Mohammad Ashraful Ferdous Chowdhury; Chowdhury Shahed Akbar; Mohammad Shoyeb	2018	Managerial Finance	ARDL; A Continuous Wavelet Transform Approach.	The results show a favorable correlation between risk-sharing tools and economic growth in countries. On the other hand, non-risk-sharing instruments have a negative correlation with the country's GDP.
18	Kausar Alam; Hafij Ullah	2022	Journal of Nusantara Studies	Critical Literature Review Analysis	This research asserts that conventional banks contribute more significantly to Türkiye's growth than Islamic banks. Furthermore, the study's findings indicate that the Islamic banking system differs from traditional banks in size, share, number, and instruments.
19	Yan-Ling Tan; Roslina Mohamad Shafi	2021	ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance	ARDL model	The results indicate a long-term equilibrium relationship between capital market features and GDP growth. Both sukuk and conventional bonds comprise the bond market and contribute positively to economic growth insignificantly. Research indicates that long-term stock market development substantially benefits economic growth, regardless of the measure employed. According to the research, stock market subcomponents impact Malaysia's economic development the most.

20	MohamadHusam Helmi	2018	The International Journal of Finance and Economics (IJFE)	Cointegration and Causality Analysis	According to cointegration and causality analysis, weak evidence of short-term causality in both directions is found in countries with Islamic banks. However, there is strong proof that real credit and real GDP are causally related over the long term. On the other hand, there is evidence of a long-term causal link in countries without Islamic banks, where real GDP affects real credit instead of vice versa. The unique characteristics of Islamic banks reasonably accounted for the disparities between the two groups of countries. These banks specifically provide loans for projects directly linked to actual economic activities and refrain from engaging in speculative transactions. As a result, this approach enhances the distribution of resources in the economy and stimulates long-term economic growth.
21	Khaled Elmawazini; Khiyar Abdullah Khiyar ; Asiye Aydilek	2020	International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management	Cross-Sectionally Correlated and Timewise Autoregressive (CCTA) Model; Endogenous Growth Model	According to the authors, Islamic banks contributed more to economic development than conventional banks before and after the financial crisis. Although financial markets do not always track GDP growth, the authors find them critical to economic expansion. Results also suggest that following Islamic finance's ethical guidelines may have a beneficial effect on GDP growth.
22	Hind Lebdaoui; Joerg Wild	2016	International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management	ARDL model; Pooled Mean Group (PMG); Mean Group (MG); Dynamic Fixed Effect	There is a favorable correlation between the presence of Islamic banks in the selected region and long-term economic development. However, this does not hold in the short run. Islamic banking's contributions to the financial sector and economic growth are positively and statistically significantly correlated with the percentage of the population that identifies as Muslim in a particular

				(DFE); Two-Stage Least Squares (2SLS)	country. This correlation holds for Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore, the Philippines, Thailand, Bangladesh, and Brunei.
23	Kizito Uyi Ehigiamusoe; MohamadShaharudin Samsurijan	2021	International Journal of Finance & Economics	Theoretical and Practical Literature Analysis	Financial development positively influences economic growth when financial and economic development, institutional quality, and macroeconomic stability are strong. Conversely, financial development may have a reverse effect when these characteristics are poor. Additionally, they demonstrate that an excessive amount of finance hurts economic growth. This implies a certain level of financial development that, if not exceeded, hinders growth rather than promoting it. Stable macroeconomic conditions, better institutional quality, and optimum financial and economic growth are all aspects of the economy that this study might affect. Therefore, nations hoping to encourage economic development via the banking sector should give these factors enough weight.
24	Salina Kassim	2016	Global Finance Journal	ARDL	The results indicate that Islamic finance is increasingly contributing to the real economy by effectively aggregating and directing funds for investment objectives.
25	İbrahim Tuğrul Çınar; Yusuf Ünsal	2022		Generalized Method of Moments (GMM)	The study's results suggest no short-term correlation between economic development and Islamic banking. The loans that Islamic banking offers its consumers are not complementary to those of commercial banks; instead, they serve as substitutes.

PART THREE

ISLAMIC FINANCE AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A COMPARATIVE INVESTIGATION OF THE LATEST INSIGHTS AND TRENDS FROM LEADING ISLAMIC FINANCE COUNTRIES, WITH A FOCUS ON TÜRKIYE

The third section of the research contains the significance of the study, limitations of the research, data set of research, methodology, and analysis of panel data. The third part of the study mainly focuses on the connection between Islamic finance (Islamic banking, Sukuk, Takaful, Islamic mutual funds, and Islamic financial institutions) and economic development (GDP, GDP adjusted by power purchasing parity, and Human Development Index) in leading Islamic finance countries. The development of Islamic banking is measured by the profitability of Islamic banking, and the development of the Islamic capital market is measured by Sukuk, while Takaful is the total value of general and family takaful operating in the country. Economic development is measured by real gross domestic product, human development index, and foreign direct investment outflows. Collected data is a balanced panel, spanning from 2015-2021, counteracting from (Türkiye, Kuwait, Qatar, UAE, Oman, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Nigeria). Three different (Ordinary Least Squire, Least Squire Dummy Variables, and Random Effect) models were employed to respond to 9 questions and test 13 hypotheses.

3.1. Significance and Objective of The Study

The Islamic financial sector has seen remarkable growth in recent years, with average annual growth rates of over 15 per cent. The Middle East and other Muslim nations, as well as investors worldwide, have driven this explosive development in the demand for shariah-compliant products, making the spread of Islamic finance a worldwide phenomenon. The research's originality is applying multiple regression (Ordinary Least Square Regression, the Least Square Dummy Variable, and the Random Effect) models in the context of different countries to find valid results and compare them to one another. This research is mainly about the structure of Islamic finance and how it behaves in economic development in different leading countries of Islamic finance. Three different models with distinguished variables are used to find

new and valid results for the extension of Islamic finance. The result of the study first fills the theoretical gap in the literature. It will help empirically show the direction, strength and type of association between the outflow of foreign direct investment, human development index and gross domestic product per capita with Islamic banking (Profitability, Total Asset, and Total Financing), Islamic capital market(Sukuk), takaful (Islamic Insurance), multiplication of profitability and Sukuk(PSU), multiplication of political stability and government efficiency to the inflow of foreign direct investment (PFDIin and GEFDIin), multiplication of political stability to exchange rate, and inflation (PSTVEX and PSTVCPI) to extend any more the Islamic finance industry in Malaysia, Indonesia, Kuwait, Qatar, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, Oman, and Türkiye. Furthermore, Türkiye is compared to other mentioned countries for contributing Islamic banking towards the gross domestic product(GDP); results of the investigation indicate Türkiye has a greater contribution than any other countries of the research while keeping the other variables (Sukuk, Takaful, PSTVEX, PSTVCPI, PSTVFDIin, POP, TO, EXR, and CPI) constant.

3.2. Limitation of Research

Islamic finance is a broad concept that includes Islamic banking, Islamic capital markets, Islamic insurance, Islamic mutual funds, and other Islamic financial institutions. Panel data from 2015 to 2021 in Malaysia, Indonesia, Kuwait, Qatar, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, Oman, and Türkiye were analyzed by using a new and updated version of STATA18. The output variables (Outflow Foreign Direct Investment, New Human Development Index, and Gross Domestic Product) and explanatory variables (Islamic Banking, Sukuk, PSU, Takaful, Trade Openness, Exchange Rate, Consumer Price Index, Multiplication Form of Political Stability to Exchange Rate, Inflation, Inflow Foreign Direct Investment, Population, PSTVFDIin, and GEFDIin) are utilized for a conducting distinguish regression model to specify the direction, strength, and type of association between mentioned dependent and independent variables. Furthermore, we assumed Türkiye as the base variable for comparing Islamic banking to other countries to determine its contribution to the gross domestic product. The limitation of the study based on the above explanation is the time frame (2015-2021)

of the data set, even though the data from the recent 2 years (2022-2023) have not been analyzed due to non-availability. The data set shows variability across the year, affecting the result's validity. Furthermore, the study did not consider the contribution of Islamic mutual funds and other Islamic financial institutions toward gross domestic product. We compare Türkiye to different countries based on the contribution of Islamic banking on gross domestic product; other studies could compare other named countries based on the contribution of Sukuk and takaful on the gross domestic product, human development, outflow of foreign direct investment, and other factors of economic development (New Human Development Index)².

3.3. Data Set of The Research

Data from nine (Türkiye, Kuwait, Qatar, UAE, Oman, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Nigeria) leading Islamic finance industry countries is collected from different websites of central banks, commercial banks, Islamic banks, Islamic capital markets operating in the mentioned countries, and international reports of the IMF and World Bank. IFSB (Islamic Financial Service Board) and SESRIC (The Statistical, Economic, and Social Research and Training Centre for Islamic Countries (SESRIC)) are the websites of databases where the 7 years (2015-2021) of data were collected about Islamic banking, Sukuk, and Takaful. Economic Development Data (GDP, Real GDP, HDI, Foreign direct investment outflows) Were Gathered from different databases of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), Global Financial Development (GFD), the World Development Indicator (WDI), the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), and globaleconomy.com.

3.4. Research Methodology

This research conducted three different (Ordinary Least Square, Least Square Dummy Variables, and Random Effect) models to make a valid decision about the contribution of Islamic finance, especially Islamic banking, towards economic development, particularly foreign direct investment outflows. The random effect model shows the contribution of Takaful towards human development. In contrast, the least squares dummy variable model concludes the contribution of Islamic banking to

²NHDI includes three sub-indicators (income level index, health index, and education index)

real gross domestic product and compares this contribution based on Türkiye's country.

3.5. Panel Data

Longitudinal and cross-sectional time-series data are alternative names for panel data sets. They have two dimensions: temporal (T) and spatial (N). They include many time-series observations of different cross-sectional units, including people, companies, and countries (Baltagi, 2008, p. 33). Scientists may now examine the change processes in very brief time series data sets. According to Baltes and Nesselroade (1979), longitudinal data and procedures are a variety of techniques based on the observation and monitoring of an entity over time to understand its existence and development. These techniques have been used in several fields of inquiry. According to Frees (2004), these developments have occurred due to the availability of significant datasets for empirical researchers.

Lazarsfeld and Fiske (1938) and Frees (2004) coined the phrase panel data when they suggested interviewing a panel of consumers over time as part of their research on the link between radio advertising and product sales. Engel's 1857 budget surveys are recognized by Toon (2000) and Frees (2004) as one of the first uses of longitudinal data. Engel gathered information on the spending habits of the same group of participants throughout this study. The goal was to investigate how food expenses correlated with income. The latter part of the 20th century saw the development of panel data modelling and estimate approaches. Kuh (1959), Johnson (1960), Mundlak (1961), and Hoch (1962) are among the first to use fixed effect models, while Balestra and Nerlove (1966) and Wallace and Hussain (1969) employed random effect models (Neelu and Sylvain, 2012, p. 1; Hsiao, 2007, p. 1; Lazarsfeld and Fiske, 1938, p. 597; Eom et al, 2008, pp. 571-572).

Balgati (2008) and Hsiao (2001) describe the benefits of panel data in great detail. In this comparison with cross-sectional data analysis, they highlight many topics that readers need extensive econometrics understanding to find valuable. Increasing the amount of observations for the study is one of the benefits of utilizing panel data. This holds for the pooled OLS model. Compared to standard errors

determined from cross-sectional data analysis, those resulting from longitudinal observations have more minor standard errors. As a result, we should expect more accurate estimates and a greater likelihood of statistical significance due to the increased number of observations made possible by combining cross-sectional data. However, panel data's main selling point is that it lets scientists look at the cause-and-effect connection using before-and-after data. Analyzing causal relationships using cross-sectional data is still helpful for testing theoretical research models. Still, it is not always easy to tell which variables affect others without considering time, which is a crucial component of any causal relationship. Similarly, we may check whether the dependent variable's connection with the independent variables is stable. Unlike panel data, which allows us to investigate the dynamic fluctuations of the associations, cross-sectional analysis looks at the relationships at one moment in time. Panel data analysis is also motivated by the need to mitigate the missing variable bias, as highlighted by Wooldridge (2006). This is particularly true for error component models. By using a fixed effects model, we can effectively remove time-invariant unobserved mistakes unique to each observation. Consequently, we get estimate findings that are more statistically reliable (Wooldridge, 2006, pp. 6-7).

panel data analysis models often used in academic literature. As previously discussed, panel data include information about temporal and spatial dimensions. The temporal dimension refers to the specific time intervals during which measurements are taken, such as months, quarters, and years. On the other hand, the spatial dimension refers to the particular units or entities being observed, such as individuals, companies, and geographical regions. The panel data general regression model may be formulated as follows:

$$y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{it,1} + \beta_2 x_{it,2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{it,k} + v_{it}, \quad i=1, \dots, N; \quad t = 1, \dots, T; \quad k = 1, \dots, K \quad (3.1)$$

where

i is the unit of observation

t is the period of time

k indicates the kth explanatory variable

β_0 is the intercept

β_k is the coefficient of each explanatory variable

v_{it} is the error term.

The equation's so-called composite error term, v_{it} , can have two components: a cross-sectional unit-specific error, a_i , and an idiosyncratic error, u_{it} .

$$v_{it} = a_i + u_{it} \quad (3.2)$$

The cross-sectional unit-specific error, a_i , does not change over time, and the idiosyncratic error, u_{it} , varies over the cross-sectional units and time (Baltagi, 2008, pp. 11-12; Gujarati, 2022, p. 12; Wooldridge, 2006, pp. 6-7). The rationale for partitioning the error terms is that by excluding some items from the panel data, we may mitigate concerns over omitted variable bias stemming from unobserved unit-specific factors. Integrating equation 3.2 into equation 3.1 yields the following equation:

$$y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{it,1} + \beta_2 x_{it,2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{it,k} + a_i + u_{it} \quad (3.3)$$

Equation 3 is a model for error components. We do not have any data on the time-constant and unit-specific error a_i . Based on our handling of the error term, a_i , we classify the methods for estimating error component models. The pooled OLS model does not detect it because it is similar to other kinds of errors. The random effects model treats it as a random variable, while the fixed effects model uses it as an estimated coefficient.

3.5.1. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Model

A fundamental way to estimate Equation 3.1 is to aggregate the data and use Ordinary Least Squares (OLS). Estimating Equation 3.1 using pooled OLS necessitates the assumption that the composite error term v_{it} is uncorrelated with the explanatory variable (x_{itk}) (Gujarati, 2022, p. 99; Wooldridge, 2006, p. 11). This indicates that we can only aggregate the data and execute OLS regression models in

the absence of both cross-sectional and temporal effects. The pooled OLS formulation of Equation 3.1 is articulated as follows:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \cdots + \beta_k x_k + v \quad (3.4)$$

Subscripts i and t are removed from equation 4 by the preceding assumption. The pooled OLS algorithm imposes multiple restrictions. You may learn about the cross-sectional and temporal aspects using panel data. However, pooled OLS does not need to consider panel data information. Since it is not feasible to measure and include all unit-specific and time-invariant effects, a_i , into the model, the pooled OLS assumption is also not practical. Consequently, the hypotheses is often violated when OLS is used to examine panel data. Here, we see biased and inconsistent results from the pooled OLS estimator biased (Gujarati, 2022, p. 99; Wooldridge, 2006, p. 11). Despite these limitations, the public administration literature widely uses the pooled OLS model because it significantly increases the number of observations and, in many cases, secures more variations of the key independent variables. This results in significant estimates.

3.5.2. Fixed Effect Model

The fixed effects model accounts for missing factors that remain constant over time but vary between units. We refer to this as fixed effects, also known as unobserved heterogeneity in (a_i) . When estimating equation 3.1 using the fixed effects model, we assume that the explanatory variable (x_{itk}) is associated with the unobserved heterogeneity (a_i) . Importantly, we also assume that the explanatory variable (x_{itk}) is unrelated to the idiosyncratic error (u_{it}) . (Baltagi, 2008, p. 13; Wooldridge, 2006, p. 11).

Removing the unobserved impact $((a_i))$ makes it possible to reduce omitted variable biases and obtain more robust estimates. There are three ways to remove the unobserved impact (a_i) in panel data analysis: 1. The First-Difference method 2. Time-Demeaning method, and 3. Least Squares Dummy Variables (LSDV) method.

3.5.2.1. The First-Difference Method

A technique for eradicating unobserved heterogeneity (a_i) is to differentiate the data over two temporal intervals. The primary distinction is the transition from one temporal era to another. If y_t represents the value of y at time t , then the first difference of y at time t is equivalent to y_{t1} . Consequently, subtracting equation 3.6 at period 2 from equation 3.5 at period 1 yields the following equation (E6 – E5).

$$y_{i1} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1,1} + \beta_2 x_{i1,2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{i1,k} + a_i + u_{i1} \quad (3.5)$$

$$y_{i2} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i2,1} + \beta_2 x_{i2,2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{i2,k} + a_i + u_{i2} \quad (3.6)$$

$$y_{i2} - y_{i1} = \beta_1(x_{i2,1} - x_{i1,1}) + \beta_2(x_{i2,2} - x_{i1,2}) \dots \beta_k(x_{i2,k} - x_{i1,k}) + (u_{i2} - u_{i1}), \text{ or } \Delta y_i = \beta_k \Delta x_{i,k} + \Delta u_i \quad (3.7)$$

where Δ represents the shift from time $t = 1$ to time $t = 2$. Equation 3.7 eliminates the unobserved heterogeneity (a_i). Here, we have a simple equation for differences-based cross-sectional regression. Hence, OLS is used to estimate the coefficients on β_k , supposing that Δu_i is uncorrelated with Δx_{it} .

3.5.2.2. The Time-Demeaning Method

The time-demeaning technique is an alternative to the first difference for removing the time-constant and unit-specific error (a_i). Converting the initial variables into departures from each variable's group mean is known as time-demeaning. In particular, we calculate the original variables' average values over time (t) and deduct those average values from the original variables' values. By averaging equation 3.8 across time in equation form, we obtain

$$y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{it,1} + \beta_2 x_{it,2} + \dots + \beta_k x_{it,k} + a_i + u_{it} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\bar{y}_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \bar{x}_{i1} + \beta_2 \bar{x}_{i2} + \dots + \beta_k \bar{x}_{ik} + a_i + \bar{u}_i \quad (3.9)$$

and then by subtracting equation 3.8 from equation 3.9.

$$y_{it} - \bar{y}_i = \beta_1(x_{it1} - \bar{x}_{i1}) + \beta_2(x_{it2} - \bar{x}_{i2}) + \dots + \beta_k(x_{itk} - \bar{x}_{ik}) + (u_i - \bar{u}_i) \quad (3.10)$$

where $(y_{it} - \bar{y}_i)$ is the time-demeaned values of y and the same for $(x_{it} - \bar{x}_{it})$ and $(u_i - \bar{u}_i)$. The important thing is that the time-constant heterogeneity (a_i) is now eliminated in equation 3.10 (Baltagi, 2008, p. 13; Wooldridge, 2006, p. 11).

We have removed the requirement that (a_i) and (x_{it}) be uncorrelated. Therefore, we can estimate equation 3.10 using OLS. It seems that the shift that devalues time is a hardship. It is unnecessary to do time-demean transformation manually. After the time-demeaning transformation, statistical software such as LIMDEP, SAS, and STATA automatically generates the fixed effects estimator. One drawback of this method is that the time-demean transformation converts all time-constant explanatory variables to zero values. Some examples of such factors include gender, ethnicity, and geography. A potential solution is to analyze the coefficients of the time-constant variables as they fluctuate over time by including the interaction term between these variables and time dummy variables (Wooldridge, 2006, p. 544).

3.5.2.3. Least Square Dummy Variable

The Least Squares Dummy Variables Method gives us a different way to look at the fixed effects model by treating the unobserved effect, a_i , as an unknown parameter that needs to be estimated for each cross-sectional unit (i). We can calculate the estimate for both each period (t) and each cross-sectional unit (i) by using a dummy variable to represent them (Baltagi, 2008, p. 13; Gujarati, 2022, pp. 33-34). Least squares dummy variable (LSDV) regression is our name for this method. A dummy variable might take on the values 1 or 0 for binary variables. Group and time effects are common subjects for this kind of regression research. Here is the conventional LSDV model:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + (\delta_1 D_1 + \dots + \delta_{i-1} D_{i-1}) + (\theta_1 T_1 + \dots + \theta_{t-1} T_{t-1}) + \beta_1 x_{it1} + \dots + \beta_k x_{itk} + u_{it} \quad (3.11)$$

Where:

D_i is a dummy variable for each cross-sectional unit except for one

T_t is a dummy variable for each time period except one.

The null hypothesis of LSDV is that all dummy parameters except one are zero: $H_0: D_1 = \dots = D_{t-1}$ (or $H_0: T_1 = \dots = T_{i-1}=0$).

To test the hypotheses, one uses the F-test. The rejection of the null hypothesis demonstrates that the fixed effect model outperforms the pooled OLS model. The LSDV's simplicity in estimating and interpreting makes it a popular choice (Baltagi, 2008, p. 33). With the same standard errors and other vital data, it produces an estimate that is comparable to the time-demean estimator.

Since each dummy variable eliminates one degree of freedom from the model, the LSDV performs best when the panel data contains more periods and fewer scenarios. However, the LSDV becomes troublesome when the panel data contains many cross-sectional units (Baltagi, 2008, p.14; Wooldridge, 2006, p. 5).

3.5.3. Random Effects Model:

Assumedly linked to the explanatory variables (x_{itj}). the Fixed Effects Model in panel data analysis removes unobserved heterogeneity (a_i), However, excluding it from the fixed effects model produces inefficient estimators since (a_i), is independent of all explanatory variables. Instead of considering unobserved heterogeneity (a_i), as a constant variable, the random effects or variance components model considers it a random factor. Thus, when randomly picking cross-sectional units from a large population, the random effects model is the proper choice (Baltagi, 2008, p. 35). Estimating the random effects model using generalized least squares (GLS) becomes possible when we know the group variance's structure. If the variance structure is unknown, the feasible generalized least squares (FGLS) technique is acceptable for estimating it. To find out whether there are random effects, Breusch and Pagan (1980) created the Lagrange multiplier (LM) test. In the one-way random group effect model, the null hypothesis states that the group variances are zero, denoted as $H_0: \sigma_u^2 = 0$. If we reject the null hypothesis, the random effect model outperforms pooled regression (Baltagi et al, 2012, pp. 39-40).

Conducting some tests for specifying which effects model is fit for the study:

- 1. Chow Test:** The Chow test determines the most appropriate model for the study between the common and fixed effect models. Using this test, we test the null hypothesis (CEM is more appropriate than FEM). The hypotheses in the Chow test can be written as follows:

H_0 : The common Effect Model is more appropriate than the Fixed Effect Model.

H_1 : The fixed Effect Model is more appropriate than the Common Effect Model.

If the P-value is less than 0.05, then we can reject the H_0 hypothesis. This means that the FEM is a better model than the CEM.

- 2. Lagrange Multiplier (Bruch-Pegan) Test:** To decide whether the model, CEM or REM, is superior, researchers employ the Lagrange multiplier (Bruch-Pegan) test. The LM test hypotheses may be expressed as follows:

H_0 : The Common Effect Model is more appropriate than the Random Effect Model.

H_1 : The Random Effect Model is more appropriate than the Common Effect Model.

If the P-value is less than 0.05, then we can reject the H_0 hypothesis. That means that the REM is a better model than the CEM.

- 3. Hausman Test:** Finally, we performed the Hausman test to determine which of the two models (FEM or REM) would provide the most accurate results. In the Hausman test, one possible hypothesis states as follows:

H_0 : The random Effect Model is more appropriate than the Fixed Effect Model.

H_1 : The fixed Effect Model is more appropriate than the Random Effect Model.

If the P-value < 0.05 , then we can reject the null hypothesis and conclude that FEM is a better model than REM. To select the best model from CEM, FEM, and REM, we will follow the diagram in Fig 3.1.

Fig 3.1. Diagram of Selecting Appropriate Models of Effects

When one of these three models is accepted for the study, the fitting or fixing of the model will be tested through a series of tests named below:

A Heteroskedasticity White test should be conducted to check the model's heteroscedasticity. If, the P-value of the conducted test, is less than <0.005 ; the null hypothesis will be accepted; otherwise, the alternative hypothesis will be replaced. The null and alternate hypotheses of the Heteroskedasticity White test as stated below:

H_0 = : The residuals are homoscedastic

H_A = : The residuals are not homoscedastic

To test the cross-section's dependency, the Breusch-Pagan LM test of independence could be performed to describe whether the study model depends on the cross-section of the data. The null and alternate hypotheses of the Breusch-Pagan LM test of independence as stated below:

H_0 = : There is no dependency between cross-sections/individuals

H_A = : There is a dependency between cross-sections/individuals

If, the P-value of the conducted test, is less than <0.005 ; the null hypothesis will be accepted; otherwise, the alternative hypothesis will be replaced.

For the normality of the model's residuals, the Jarque-Bera normality test and for serial correlation, the Wooldridge autocorrelation test might be conducted to decide whether the model is stabilized for the study.

Wooldridge test for autocorrelation hypotheses

H_0 =: There is no autocorrelation between residuals

H_A = : There is autocorrelation between residuals

Jarque-Bera normality test hypotheses

H_0 = : Residuals are normally distributed

H_A = : Residuals are not normally distributed

If , the P-value of the conducted test, is less than <0.005 ; the null hypothesis will be accepted; otherwise, the alternative hypothesis will be replaced.

If the above 4 main tests suggest a problem in the model, especially indicating that the coefficients of the independent variable are inconsistent in predicting the response variable. Because of the instability of the model mentioned, the model coefficient should be standardized through a robust standard error regression model to finalize the research results (Humta & Şahin, 2023, p. 41).

3.6. Research Models

Three different econometric models were conducted based on originality and valid results for assessing the relationship between Islamic finance and economic development. Each model is explained below:

3.6.1. Effect Models of Islamic Banks on Foreign Direct Investment Outflows

This model's primary concern is to examine the impact of Islamic banks on economic development (foreign direct investment outflows) by incorporating the role of Sukuk, Takaful and PSU within the FDI-Out function. The benchmark functional form of foreign direct investment outflows of the equation are as follows:

$$FDI_{out_t} = f(PROF_t, SUKUK_t, TAKAFUL_t, PSU_t) \quad (3.12)$$

The empirical equation is stated thus:

$$FDI_{out_t} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PROF_t + \beta_2 SUKUK_t + \beta_3 TAKAFUL_t + \beta_4 PSU_t + \mu_i \quad (3.13)$$

We use foreign direct investment outflows as an indicator of economic development, while profitability, sukuk, takaful, and PSU are used to measure Islamic finance. In equation 3.13, FDI_{out_t} is the outflows of foreign direct investment, PROF represents the profitability of Islamic banks, SUKUK is the Islamic bonds, TAKAFUL is the Islamic insurance, and PSU is the multiplication form of (PROF * SUKUK), respectively, while μ_i is a well-behaved error term assumed to have zero mean and constant covariance.

3.6.1.1. Model Variables

Every econometric model has one dependent and more than one independent and control variable. Each variable of the model is explained as follows:

Table 3.1. Description of the Variables Used in the Model

Dependent and independent variables of the model	Code	Description
Foreign direct investment outflows (Dependent Variable)	FDI_{out_t}	Foreign direct investment is outflowing from one country to another based on any reason, especially for profit
Probability	PROF	An indicator of bank performance reflects how banks are run, given the environment in which they operate.
Sukuk	SUKUK	The name sukuk originates from Sakk, which refers to bonds or securities structured according to Sharia principles, which prohibit Islamic issuers and investors from participating in traditional securities transactions. Sukuk, also referred to as Islamic bonds or investment certificates, function as securitized leases (Ijarah) and encompass a variety of Islamic finance instruments, including Murabaha, Musharakah, and Mudarabah.
Takaful	TAKAFUL	Takaful is an Arabic term derived from the root word kafala. It means a joint guarantee. In the

		context of insurance, takaful is a Shariah-compliant insurance. When members of a group first decide to establish a mutual fund and contribute money to it, they make a commitment to one another known as takaful. After that, they jointly guarantee or protect one another from specific losses and harm. If any group member experiences any specified loss or damage, they would be eligible for compensation, often in the form of monetary or benefit provisions from the mutual fund.
Profitability* Sukuk	PSU	Multiplication form of profitability and Sukuk.

3.6.1.2. Models Questions and Hypotheses

Each model of the study has three questions consistent with four hypotheses to accept or reject after conducting the analysis. The constructed questions followed by the hypotheses as follows:

1. Is there any relationship between foreign direct investment's outflow and Islamic banks' profitability?

H₁= A positive association exists between foreign direct investment's outflow and Islamic banks' profitability.

2. Is there any linkage between sukuk and takaful on the outflow of foreign direct investment?

H₂= Sukuk has a positive relationship with the outflows of foreign direct investment.

H₃= Takaful has a negative relationship with the outflows of foreign direct investment.

3. Does an Islamic bank's profitability with a moderating effect on sukuk have a positive relationship with outflows of foreign direct investment?

H₄= There is a positive relationship between sukuk and foreign direct investment outflows through the moderating effect of Islamic bank's profitability.

3.6.1.3. Models Analysis with Findings

Table 3.2 illustrates descriptive statistics to determine the characteristics of variables utilized in model 1 of the study. Summary statistics suggest that the variation

of outflows of foreign direct investment (M=5655.28; SD=6514.422) is greater than the variation of Takaful (M=3342.488; SD=5038.094) and lesser in the variation of Sukuk (M=9698.501; SD=11348.25). The variable most varied in the mentioned model (1) from the means of data is PSU (Profitability* Sukuk). In Appendix Table 2, we observed that the highest value of Islamic banks' profitability in 2021 reached 2.5 from 0.67 in 2015, with a standard deviation of 0.429. This indicates the high growth of the Islamic finance industry in recent years, especially in Islamic banking. Based on the Pearson coefficient of skewness, the data is positively skewed because the value skewness looks positive for all variables. The kurtosis value >0 means the data's peak (including all variables) is very high from the asymmetrical distribution curve named leptokurtic.

Table 3.2. Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	p1	p99	Skew.	Kurt.
FDI-Out	63	5655.280	6514.422	-12200	23859.910	-12200	23859.910	0.900	4.344
PROF	63	1.626000	0.429000	0.6700	2.5000000	0.6700	2.5000000	0.304	2.754
SUKUK	63	9698.501	11348.25	3.4700	39603.449	3.4700	39603.449	1.146	3.227
TAKAFUL	63	3342.488	5038.094	-22.730	16861.881	-22.730	16861.881	1.551	3.883
PSU	63	14464.77	16234.538	4.4070	59870.656	4.4070	59870.656	1.064	3.090

Source: Developed by author

Table 3.3 explains the weak and negative relationship between foreign direct investment outflows and Islamic banks' profitability. Sukuk has a weak and positive relationship with outflows of foreign direct investment. A strong and positive relationship exists between Takaful and foreign direct investment outflows, but PSU has a moderating positive relationship.

Table 3.3. Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) FDI-Out	1.000				
(2) PROF	-0.139	1.000			
(3) SUKUK	0.370	-0.273	1.000		
(4) TAKAFL	0.788	-0.062	0.266	1.000	

(5) PSU	0.426	-0.141	0.968	0.297	1.000
---------	-------	--------	-------	-------	-------

Source: Developed by author

By increasing the profitability of Islamic banks by 1 unit, the outflow of foreign direct investment (FDI-Out) will decrease by about 2741.25 units. By increasing 1 unit, Sukuk will reduce the outflow of foreign direct investment by 0.47300 units. A change in 1 unit of Takaful or PSU (Profitability* Sukuk) will lead to changes of 0.9070 and 0.397 FDI-Out, respectively. These relationships are significant at different levels of signification, and keep in mind that for each relationship between the variables, other variables will remain constant. F value =0.000 indicates the fitness or goodness of the model for the study we utilized. The coefficient of determination (R^2) shows 69% of independent variables estimating the output variable (Y); the remaining variable that changes, about 31 % of the response variable, did not take place in the model of the study (see Table 3.4).

Table 3.4. Regression Analysis

FDI-Out	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
PROF	-2741.25	1335.447	-2.050	0.045	-5414.437	-68.063	**
SUKUK	-0.47300	0.201000	-2.350	0.022	-0.875000	-0.0700	**
TAKAFUL	0.90700	0.099000	9.160	0.000	0.709000	1.1050	***
PSU	0.39700	0.138000	2.880	0.006	0.121000	0.6730	***
Constant	5921.713	2345.603	2.520	0.014	1226.479	10616.9	**
Mean dependent var		5655.280	SD dependent var			6514.422	
R-squared		0.695000	Number of obs			63	
F-test		33.03700	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		1219.479	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			1230.194	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: Developed by author

3.6.1.4. Panel Data Line Plots

The panel data line plot indicates a comparative graph of the countries based on foreign direct investment outflows. Indonesia has a high trend of foreign direct investment outflows, while UAE has a low trend throughout the year (2015-2021). The trends of other countries included in the study are shown in Figure 3.2.

Fig 3.2. Panel Data Line Plots

Source: Developed by author

Fig 3.3 below indicates the countries with different trending lines of foreign direct investment outflows, the profitability of Islamic banks, Sukuk, Takaful, and the multiplication form of (Profitability* Sukuk). In some countries, such as Nigeria and Oman, the lines are near to coincident; in contrast, in Saudi Arabia, the trends of the mentioned variables are different throughout the period (2015-2021).

The scatterplot matrix from left to right shows the correlation between the dependent variable (FDI-Out) and the independent variables (PROF, Sukuk, Takaful, and PSU). In contrast, the matrix from left to right shows the correlation between independent variables.

The Normal Probability Plot visually flags meaningful divergences from normality within information sets. If the data plot is near a straight line, the data is normally distributed. In contrast, if the data plot is away from approximately straight lines in terms of ups and downs, it is suggested that data not be normally distributed. In summing up, the closer the points hug the line, the stronger the evidence for normality. For each variable of model 1, the standard probability plot is visualized

below Fig 3.5. The evidence shows the partly normal distribution of the data set for each model variable.

Fig 3.3. Panel Data Line Plots

Source: Developed by author

Fig 3.4. Scatter Plot Matri

Source: Developed by author

Fig 3.5. Normal Probability Plot

Source: Developed by author

The residuals tend to be low, whereas fitted values grow forward. The spread of the residuals is constant at every response level, which could be a sign of the goodness of the model considered for the research (Fig 3.5; f).

3.6.1.5. Questions and Hypotheses of Research

After data analysis through Stata 18, the responses towards research questions and acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses concluded as follows:

Table 3.5. Questions and Hypotheses of Research

No	Questions	Hypotheses	P-Value	Remarks
1	Is there any relationship between foreign direct investment's outflow and Islamic banks' profitability?	H_1 = A positive association exists between foreign direct investment's outflow and Islamic banks' profitability.	0.045	Rejected
2	Is there any linkage between sukuk and takaful on the outflow of foreign direct investment?	H_2 = Sukuk has a positive relationship with the outflows of foreign direct investment. H_3 = Takaful has a negative relationship with the outflows of foreign direct investment	0.022 0.000	Rejected Rejected
3	Does an Islamic bank's profitability with a moderating effect on sukuk have a positive relationship with outflows of foreign direct investment?	H_4 = There is a positive relationship between sukuk and foreign direct investment outflows, moderated by Islamic banks' profitability.	0.06	Accepted

Source: Developed by author

3.6.2. Random Effect Model of Takaful on Human Development

This model's primary concern is to examine the impact of TAKAFUL on economic development (Human Development) by incorporating the role of PSU, TO, PFDIn and GFDIn within the HDI_Value function. The benchmark functional form of human development of the equation is as follows:

$$HDI_{Value_t} = f(TAKAFUL_t, PSU_t, TO_t, PFDIn_t + GFDIn_t) \quad (3.14)$$

The empirical equation is stated thus:

$$HDI_{Value_t} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 TAKAFUL + \alpha_2 PSU + \alpha_3 TO + \alpha_4 PFDIn + \alpha_4 GFDIn + \varepsilon_i \quad (3.15)$$

We use the human development index (HDI) as an indicator of economic development, while TAKAFUL, PSU, TO, PFDI_{in}, and GFDI_{in} are used to measure Islamic finance. In equation 3.15. HDI_{value_t} is the human development index value, takaful represents Islamic insurance, PSU is the multiplication form of (Profitability*Sukuk), TO is the Trade Openness, PFDI_{in} is the multiplication form of (Political Stability*Foreign Direct Investment Inflows), and GFDI_{in} is the multiplication form of (Government Effectiveness*Foreign Direct Investment Inflows) respectively, while ε_t is a well-behaved error term assumed to have zero mean and constant covariance.

3.6.2.1. Models Variables

Every econometric model has one output and more than one explanatory and control variable. Each variable of the model is described as follows:

Table 3.6. Description of the Variables Used in The Model

Dependent and independent variables of the model	Code	Description
Human development index value (Dependent Variable)	HDI_{value_t}	The Human Development Index (HDI) is a summary measure of average achievement in key dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, being knowledgeable and having a decent standard of living. HDI is the geometric mean of normalized indices for each of the three dimensions.
Takaful	TAKAFUL	Takaful is an Arabic term derived from the root word kafala. It means a joint guarantee. In the context of insurance, takaful is a Shariah-compliant insurance. When members of a group first decide to establish a mutual fund and contribute money to it, they make a commitment to one another known as takaful. After that, they jointly guarantee or protect one another from specific losses and harm. If any group member experiences any specified loss or damage, they would be eligible for compensation, often in the form of monetary or benefit provisions from the mutual fund.
Portability* Sukuk	PSU	Multiplication form of profitability and Sukuk
Trade Openness	TO	Increased trade openness is a suitable stand-in for trade liberalization and is sometimes defined as a growth in the size of the nation's traded sector relative to total output. Indeed, enhanced trade openness often signifies the efficacy of trade liberalization applications.
Political Stability* Foreign Direct Investment Inflows	PFDI _{in}	Multiplication form of political stability and inflow of foreign direct investment.

Government effectiveness* Foreign Direct Investment Inflows	GFDI _{in}	Multiplication form of government effectiveness and inflow of foreign direct investment.
---	--------------------	---

3.6.2.2. Models Questions and Hypotheses

Each model of the study has three questions consistent with six hypotheses to accept or reject after conducting the analysis. The constructed questions followed by the hypotheses as follows:

4. Does government effectiveness, moderating the inflow of foreign direct investment, have a positive relationship with human development?

H_5 = A positive relationship exists between human development and foreign direct investment inflows through the moderating effect of government effectiveness.

5. Does an Islamic bank's profitability with a moderating effect on sukuk have a positive relationship with human development?

H_6 = There is a negative relationship between sukuk and human development through the moderating effect of Islamic banks' profitability

6. Is there a significant effect of the inflow of foreign direct investment on human development through the moderating effect of political stability?

H_7 = Positive and significant effects exist between the inflow of foreign direct investment and human development, with political stability as a moderate factor.

3.6.2.3. Models Analysis with Findings

Table 3.7 illustrates descriptive statistics to determine the characteristics of variables utilized in model 2 of the study. Summary statistics suggest that the variation of Human Development ($M=0.795$; $SD=0.107$) is less than the variation of Takaful ($M=3342.488$; $SD=5038.094$); PSU ($M=14464.771$; $SD=16234.538$); GFDI_{in} ($M=3335.515$; $SD=7064.816$) and exception from the variation of PFDI_{in} ($M=-2721.501$; $SD=7956.367$). In Appendix Table 6, we observed that the highest value of Takful in 2021 reached 16861.881 from -22.73 in 2015, with a standard deviation of 5038.094. This indicates the high growth of the Islamic finance industry in recent years relative to traditional measurement parameters, especially in Takaful.

Table 3.8's correlation matrix explains human development's weak and positive relationship with Takaful, PSU, and PFDlin. Trade openness and GFDlin have positive and moderate relationships with human development.

Table 3.7. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
HDI Value	63	0.795000	0.107000	0.520000	0.9200000
TAKAFUL	63	3342.488	5038.094	-22.7300	16861.881
PSU	63	14464.77	16234.53	4.40700	59870.656
TO	63	84.96800	43.80200	20.7200	190.57000
PFDlin	63	-2721.501	7956.367	-28274.2	13433.627
GFDlin	63	3355.515	7064.816	-4992.43	28933.967

Table 3.8. Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) HDI Value	1.000					
(2) TAKAFUL	0.397	1.000				
(3) PSU	0.373	0.297	1.000			
(4) TO	0.664	0.537	0.364	1.000		
(5) PFDlin	0.287	0.450	0.181	0.715	1.000	
(6) GFDlin	0.426	0.738	0.352	0.759	0.497	1.000

Table 3.9. OLS Regression

HDI Value	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
TAKAFUL	6.72e-06	2.73e-06	2.46	0.017	1.24e-06	0.000012	**
PSU	7.60e-07	6.07e-07	1.25	0.216	-4.56e-07	1.98e-06	
TO	0.002830	0.00040	6.91	0.000	0.002010	0.003650	***
PFDlin	-6.14e-06	1.68e-06	-3.65	0.001	-9.51e-06	-2.77e-06	***
GFDlin	-7.59e-06	2.51e-06	-3.02	0.004	-0.000126	-2.56e-06	***
Constant	0.529724	0.03549	14.92	0.000	0.458641	0.600806	***
Mean dependent var		0.795	SD dependent var			0.107	
R-squared		0.595	Number of obs			63	
F-test		16.739	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		-148.893	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			-136.034	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Table 3.10. Fixed Effect Regression

HDI Value	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
TAKAFUL	6.71e-06	2.03e-06	3.30	0.002	2.63e-06	0.0000108	***
PSU	3.99e-07	1.35e-07	2.96	0.005	1.28e-07	6.70e-07	***
TO	0.000198	0.000196	1.02	0.314	-0.00019	0.0005945	
PFDlin	3.36e-07	3.58e-07	0.94	0.353	-3.84e-07	1.06e-06	
GFDlin	5.47e-07	3.77e-07	1.45	0.153	-2.11e-07	1.30e-06	
Constant	0.748811	0.020622	36.31	0.000	0.707370	0.7902535	***
Mean dependent var		0.795	SD dependent var			0.107	
R-squared		0.493	Number of obs			63	
F-test		9.516	Prob > F			0.000	
Akaike crit. (AIC)		-445.704	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			-432.845	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Table 3.11. Random Effect Regression

HDI Value	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
TAKAFUL	6.88e-06	1.94e-06	3.54	0.000	3.07e-06	3.07e-07	***
PSU	4.08e-07	1.37e-07	2.99	0.003	1.40e-07	6.76e-07	***
TO	0.000262	0.000189	1.39	0.165	-0.0001084	0.000634	
PFDlin	2.91e-07	3.58e-07	0.81	0.417	-4.11e-07	9.92e-07	
GFDlin	5.16e-07	3.78e-07	1.37	0.172	-2.25e-07	1.26e-06	
Constant	0.742747	0.352929	21.05	0.000	0.6735748	0.811920	***
Mean dependent var		0.795	SD dependent var			0.107	
Overall r-squared		0.283	Number of obs			63	
Chi-square		49.629	Prob > chi2			0.000	
R-squared within		0.492	R-squared between			0.282	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: Developed by author

The table's model selection criteria show that the study's appropriate model is a random effect model (See Table 3.12). Some diagnostic tests are employed to specify the model's existing problem and then to robust the model for valid results. The model has serial correlation and heteroscedasticity problems (See Table 3.13). To resolve the problem, the model has been robust.

Table 3.12. Model Selection

Test Name	Null Hypotheses	P- value	Result
Chow Test	H0: CEM is more appropriate than FEM	0.000	Rejected
Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier Test	H0: CEM is more appropriate than REM	0.000	Rejected
Hausman Test	H0: REM is more appropriate than FEM	0.256	Accepted

Table 3.13. Diagnostics Tests or Specification of The Selected Model

Test Name	Null Hypotheses	Prob	Remarks
Heteroscedasticity Test	H0: The variance is constant	0.000	Rejected
Breusch-Pagan Lagrange Multiplier Test of Independence	H0: Cross sections are independent	0.320	Accepted
Pesaran CD Test	H: Cross sections are independent	0.341	Accepted
Wooldridge Serial Correlation Test	H0: No serial correlation	0.003	Rejected
Jarque-Bera Normality Test	H0: There are normal distributions	3.000	Accepted

Table 3.14. Robust Random Effect Model

HDI Value	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
TAKAFUL	6.88e-06	1.39e-06	4.96	0.000	4.16e-06	9.60e-06	***
PSU	4.08e-07	1.95e-08	13.81	0.000	3.50e-07	4.66e-07	***
TO	0.0002628	0.0003068	0.86	0.392	-0.0003384	0.0008641	
PFDlin	2.91e-07	3.41e-07	0.85	0.394	-3.77e-07	9.58e-07	
GFDlin	5.16e-07	2.54e-07	2.03	0.042	1.87e-08	1.01e-06	**
Constant	0.7427476	0.0516573	14.38	0.000	0.6415011	0.8439940	***
Mean dependent var		0.795	SD dependent var			0.107	
Overall r-squared		0.283	Number of obs			63	
Chi-square		294.565	Prob > chi2			0.000	
R-squared within		0.492	R-squared between			0.282	

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: Developed by author

The panel data line plot indicates a comparative graph of the countries based on human development index value. The United Arab Emirates has a high trend of human development index value, while Nigeria has a low trend throughout the year (2015-2021). The trends of other countries included in the study are shown in Figure 3.6 (Developed by author, 2024).

Fig 3.7 below indicates the countries with different trending lines of human development index value, Takaful, PSU, TO, PFDlin, and GFDlin. In some countries, such as Kuwait and Oman, the lines are nearly too coincident; in contrast, in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) and Saudi Arabia, the trends of the mentioned variables are different throughout the period (2015-2021).

Fig 3.6. Panel Data Line Plot

Fig 3.7. Panel Data Line Plot

Source: Developed by author

The scatterplot matrix from left to right shows the correlation between the dependent variable (HDI-Value) and the independent variables (Takaful, PSU, TO, PFDIn, and GFDIn). In contrast, the matrix plot from left to right shows the correlation between independent variables (Developed by author, 2024).

Fig 3.8. Scatter Plot Matrix

Fig 3.9. Normal Probability Plot

Source: Developed by author

3.6.2.4. Remarks on Hypotheses of The Model

After data analysis through Stata 18, the responses towards research questions and acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses concluded as follows:

Table 3.15. Remarks on Hypotheses of The Model

NO	Questions	Hypotheses	P	Remarks
4	Does government effectiveness, moderating the inflow of foreign direct investment, have a positive relationship with human development?	H_5 = A positive relationship exists between human development and foreign direct investment inflows through the moderating effect of government effectiveness.	0.042	Accepted

5	Does an Islamic bank's profitability with a moderating effect on sukuk have a positive relationship with human development?	$H_6 =$ There is a negative relationship between sukuk and human development through the moderating effect of Islamic banks' profitability.	0.000	Rejected
6	Is there a significant effect of the inflow of foreign direct investment on human development through the moderating effect of political	$H_7 =$ positive and significant effects exist between the inflow of foreign direct investment and human development, with political stability acting as a moderate factor.	0.850	Rejected

Source: Developed by author

3.6.3. Least Square Dummy Variable Model

This model's primary concern is to examine the impact of the profitability of Islamic banks on GDP (gross domestic product per capita) by incorporating the role of SUKUK, TAKAFUL, PSTVEX, PSTVCPI, PSTVFDIn, POP, TO, EXR, and CPI within the Log GDPci function. The benchmark functional form of gross domestic product of the equation is as follows:

$$\text{Log GDPci}_t = f(\text{PROF}_t, \text{SUKUK}_t, \text{TAKAFUL}_t, \text{PSTVEX}_t + \text{PSTVCPI}_t + \text{PSTVFDIn}_t + \text{POP}_t + \text{TO}_t + \text{EXR}_t + \text{CPI}_t) \quad (3.16)$$

The empirical equation is stated thus:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Log GDPci}_t = & \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 \text{PROF}_t + \gamma_2 \text{SUKUK}_t + \gamma_3 \text{TAKAFUL}_t + \gamma_4 \text{PSTVEX}_t + \\ & \gamma_5 \text{PSTVCPI}_t + \gamma_6 \text{PSTVFDIn}_t + \gamma_7 \text{POP}_t + \gamma_8 \text{TO}_t + \gamma_9 \text{EXR}_t + \gamma_{10} \text{CPI}_t + \gamma_{11} \text{SA}_t + \\ & \gamma_{12} \text{INDO}_t + \gamma_{13} \text{KU}_t + \gamma_{14} \text{NI}_t + \gamma_{15} \text{OM}_t + \gamma_{16} \text{QA}_t + \gamma_{17} \text{UAE}_t + \gamma_{18} \text{MA}_t + \\ & \omega_i \end{aligned} \quad (3.17)$$

We use the real gross domestic product per capita (Real GDPpc) index to indicate economic development. In contrast, PROF, SUKUK, and TAKAFUL are used to measure Islamic finance. In equation (LogGDPci_t) is the log of gross domestic product per capita, PROF represents Islamic bank's profitability, SUKUK is the Islamic bonds, TAKAFUL is the Islamic insurance, PSTVEX is the multiplication form of (Political Stability*Exchange Rate), PSTVCPI is the multiplication form of (Political Stability*Inflation Rate), PSTVFDIn is the multiplication form of (Political Stability*Foreign Direct Investment Inflows), POP is the Total Population, TO is Trade Openness, EXR is the Exchange Rate, and CPI is the Consumer Price Index respectively, while ω_i is a well-behaved Error Term assumed to have zero mean and

constant covariance. SA, INDO, KU, NI, OM, QA, UAE, and MA stand from Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Kuwait, Nigeria, Oman, Qatar, United Arab Emirates, and Malaysia, used as dummy variables in the model to compare to Türkiye's the contribution of Islamic banking towards gross domestic product.

3.6.3.1. Models Variables

Every econometric model has one output and more than one explanatory and control variable. Each variable of the model is described as follows:

Table 3.16. Description of the Variables Used in The Model

Dependent and independent variables of the model	Code	Description
Gross Domestic Product Per Capita Income (DV)	LogGDP _{ci}	The total amount of final goods and services in the year inside the country's border in terms of money.
Islamic Banks Profitability	PROF	Bank profitability, an indicator of bank performance, reflects how banks persist, given the environment in which they function or operate.
Sukuk	SUKUK	The name sukuk originates from Sakk, which refers to bonds or securities structured according to Sharia principles, which prohibit Islamic issuers and investors from participating in traditional securities transactions. Sukuk, also referred to as Islamic bonds or investment certificates, function as securitized leases (Ijarah) and encompass a variety of Islamic finance instruments, including Murabaha, Musharakah, and Mudarabah.
Takaful	TAKAFUL	Takaful is derived from the root word kafala. It means a joint guarantee. In the context of insurance, takaful is a Shariah-compliant insurance. When members of a group first decide to establish a mutual fund and contribute money to it, they make a commitment to one another known as takaful. After that, they jointly guarantee or protect one another from specific losses and harm. If any group member experiences any specified loss or damage, they would be eligible for compensation, often in the form of monetary or benefit provisions from the mutual fund.
Political Stability Value* Exchange Rates	PSTVEX	Multiplication form of political stability and exchange rate.
Political Stability Value* Consumer Price Index	PSTVCPI	Multiplication form of political stability and inflation.
Political Stability Value* Foreign Direct Investment Inflows	PSTVFDlin	Multiplication form of political stability and inflow of foreign direct investment.

Population	POP	The population figure, or total population or simply population, of a given area is the total number of people in that area at a given time.
Trade Openness	TO	Increased trade openness is a suitable stand-in for trade liberalization and is sometimes defined as a growth in the size of the nation's trade sector relative to total output. Indeed, enhanced trade openness often signifies the efficacy of trade liberalization applications.
Exchange Rate	EXR	Exchange rates are defined as the price of one country's currency relative to another country's currency. This indicator is measured in terms of national currency per US dollar.
Consumer Price Index	CPI	Inflation is the rate of increase in prices over a given period.

3.6.3.2. Models Questions and Hypotheses

Each model of the study has three questions consistent with six hypotheses to accept or reject after conducting the analysis. The constructed questions followed by the hypotheses as follows:

7. Is there any linkage between banks' profitability and sukuk on the gross domestic product?

H_{07} = The profitability of Islamic banks has a negative relationship with the gross domestic product.

H_{A7} = Sukuk has a positive relationship with the gross domestic product.

8. Is there any connection between inflation and an exchange rate on gross domestic product with a moderating effect on political stability?

H_{08} = Inflation and gross domestic product have a positive relationship through the moderating effect of political stability.

H_{A8} = The exchange rate and gross domestic product have a negative relationship due to the moderating effect of political stability.

9. Does Türkiye contribute more to the gross domestic product through Islamic banks than other studied countries?

H_{09} = Türkiye contributes more to the gross domestic product through the profitability of Islamic banks than any other country in the study.

H_{A9} = Türkiye contributes more to the gross domestic product through the profitability of Islamic banks than any other country in the study except Malaysia.

3.6.3.3. Models Analysis with Findings

Table 3.17 illustrates descriptive statistics to determine the characteristics of variables utilized in the study's underlying model (3). Log transformation was performed to make the data pattern interpretable (Nawaz et al, 2013). Summary statistics suggest that the variation in GDP (Mean= 1.130×10^{12} ; Standard Deviation= 9.659×10^{11}) is greater than the variation in profitability of Islamic banks (M=1.626, SD=0.429); Sukuk (M=9698.501; SD=11348,25); Takaful (M=3342.488; SD=5038,094); PSTVEX (M=-841.475; SD=2217.739); PSTVCPI (M=-96.504; SD=264.719); PSTVFDlin (M=-2721.501; SD=7956.367); POP (M=70474404; SD=92033566); TO (M=84.968; SD=43.802); EXR (M=1586.131; SD=4403.303); and CPI (M= 187.521; SD=119.843). In Appendix Table 3, we observed that the highest value of Sukuk in 2021 reached 39603.449 from 3.47 in 2015, with a standard deviation of 11348.25. This indicates the high growth of the sukuk in recent years relative to traditional measurement parameters.

Table 3.17. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
LogGDPci	63	26.551000	0.845000	25.04200	27.805000
PROF	63	1.6260000	0.429000	0.670000	2.5000000
SUKUK	63	9698.5010	11348.25	3.470000	39603.449
TAKAFUL	63	3342.4880	5038.094	-22.73000	16861.881
PSTVEX	63	-841.47500	2217.739	-8552.900	3.6400000
PSTVCPI	63	-96.504000	264.7190	-755.6450	200.57200
PSTVFDlin	63	-2721.5010	7956.367	-28274.24	13433.627
POP	63	704744040	92033566	2414573	2.738e+08
TO	63	84.968000	43.80200	20.72000	190.57000
EXR	63	1586.1310	4403.303	0.300000	14481
CPI	63	187.52100	119.8430	92.01000	686.95000
DFSA	63	0.1110000	0.317000	0	1
DFINDO	63	0.1110000	0.317000	0	1
DFKU	63	0.1110000	0.317000	0	1
DFNI	63	0.1110000	0.317000	0	1
DFOM	63	0.1110000	0.317000	0	1
DFQA	63	0.1110000	0.317000	0	1
DFUAE	63	0.1110000	0.317000	0	1
DFMA	63	0.1110000	0.317000	0	1

Source: Developed by author

Table 3.18 Regression Analysis indicates A change in 1 unit profitability of Islamic banks, Sukuk, Takaful, PSTVEX (Political Stability*Exchange Rate), PSTVCPI (Political Stability*Consumer Price Index), and Population will cause a change in the Gross Domestic Product by 0.001, 65900, 0.000000449, 0.00000062, 0.00000769, and 1070000 units, respectively. Trade openness, exchange rate, and consumer price index have positive and insignificant relationships with gross domestic product. Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Kuwait, Nigeria, Oman, Qatar, UAE, and Malaysia have less contribution (-24%, -274%, -121%, -168%, -164%, -111%, -112%, and -88%) compared to Türkiye's Islamic banks regarding profitability to the gross domestic product, respectively. Without Saudi Arabia, all contributions of Islamic banks toward gross domestic product are significant due to p-values, as seen below in Table 3. The coefficient of determination, or $R^2 = 99$, means the independent variables estimate 99 percent of the output variable as (Y) in the model. The value of the R square shows the model's ability to employ and find comprehensive and valid results for the study. Overall, the $F = 0.000$ shows the significance of the model and is acceptable for the combined effect of the independent variable (PROF, SUKUK, TAKAFUL, PSTVEX, PSTVCPI, PSTVFDI_{in}, POP, TO, EXR, and CPI) on the dependent variable (GDP).

Table 3.18. Regression Analysis

LogGDPci	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
PROF	0.1368695	0.0380783	3.59	0.001	0.0601277	0.2136113	***
SUKUK	6.59e-06	2.49e-06	2.65	0.011	1.57e-06	0.0000116	**
TAKAFUL	0.0000449	0.0000189	2.37	0.022	6.75e-06	0.0000830	**
PSTVEX	0.0000622	0.0000365	1.70	0.095	-0.0000113	0.0001357	*
PSTVCPI	0.0007686	0.0003581	2.15	0.037	0.0000468	0.0014904	**
PSTVFDI _{in}	-0.0000107	4.78e-06	-2.23	0.031	-0.0000303	-1.04e-06	**
POP	1.07e-08	4.93e-09	2.16	0.036	7.32e-10	2.06e-08	**
TO	0.0022913	0.0021137	1.08	0.284	-0.0019686	0.0065513	
EXR	0.0000855	0.0001185	0.72	0.474	-0.0001534	0.0003244	
CPI	0.0002777	0.0003517	0.79	0.434	-0.0004311	0.0009864	
DFSA	-0.2477852	0.2204862	-1.12	0.267	-0.6921459	0.1965754	
DFINDO	-2.7449700	1.3400350	-2.05	0.047	-5.4456320	-0.0443072	**
DFKU	-1.2134050	0.2699088	-4.50	0.000	-1.7573700	-0.6694396	***
DFNI	-1.6855740	0.5947657	-2.83	0.007	-2.8842450	-0.4869021	***
DFOM	-1.6489970	0.2613168	-6.31	0.000	-2.1756460	-1.1223480	***
DFQA	-1.1154610	0.2709860	-4.12	0.000	-1.6615970	-0.5693242	***
DFUAE	-1.1203070	0.4460700	-2.51	0.016	-2.0193020	-0.2213119	**
DFMA	-0.8808808	0.2359728	-3.73	0.001	-1.3564530	-0.4053089	***
Constant	26.262580	0.3373541	77.85	0.000	25.582690	26.942470	***
Mean dependent var		26.551	SD dependent var			0.845	
R-squared		0.994	Number of obs			63	

F-test	434.076	Prob > F	0.000
Akaike crit. (AIC)	-134.159	Bayesian crit. (BIC)	-95.582

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source: Developed by author

The panel data line plot indicates a comparative graph of the countries based on gross domestic product (GDP). Indonesia has a high GDP, while Oman's trend has been low throughout the year (2015-2021). The trends of other countries included in the study are shown in Figure 3.10.

The correlation matrix of model 3 explores positive and moderate relationships between the gross domestic product (GDP) with Islamic bank's profitability, the population, and the exchange rate. Conversely, PSTVEX, PSTVCPI, PSTVFDIin, and TO have negative associations with GDP. CPI, Sukuk, and Takaful have positive and weak relationships with GDP. At the same time, PSTVEX, PSTVCPI, PSTVFDIin, and TO have negative links to GDP. Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Nigeria, and Malaysia have stronger relationships between GDP and Islamic bank profitability than Türkiye. In contrast, Kuwait, Oman, Qatar, and the UAE have a weaker relationship between gross domestic product and Islamic bank profitability compared to Türkiye. All countries are created through dummy variables, and relationships among them are negative due to multicollinearity.

Table 3.19. Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(13)	(14)	(15)	(16)	(17)	(18)	(19)	
(1)LogGDPci	1.000																			
(2) PROF	0.538	1.000																		
(3) SUKUK	0.119	-0.27	1.000																	
(4) TAKAFUL	0.298	-0.06	0.266	1.000																
(5) PSTVEX	-0.47	-0.47	0.243	0.173	1.000															
(6) PSTVCPI	-0.44	-0.36	0.306	0.341	-0.02	1.000														
(7) PSTVFDIin	-0.53	-0.44	0.251	0.450	0.314	0.683	1.000													
(8) POP	0.626	0.623	-0.34	-0.24	-0.79	-0.49	-0.48	1.000												
(9) TO	-0.35	-0.57	0.449	0.537	0.411	0.658	0.715	-0.68	1.000											
(10) EXR	0.471	0.437	-0.22	-0.16	-0.98	0.048	-0.29	0.774	-0.38	1.000										
(11) CPI	0.271	-0.04	-0.22	0.071	0.228	-0.68	-0.25	0.108	-0.02	-0.25	1.000									
(12) Saudi Arabia	0.339	0.221	0.202	0.450	0.135	0.050	-0.06	-0.13	-0.18	-0.12	-0.26	1.000								
(13) Indonesia	0.467	0.430	-0.21	-0.16	-0.98	0.063	-0.28	0.760	-0.37	0.999	-0.25	-0.1	1.000							
(14) Kuwait	-0.42	-0.38	-0.27	-0.23	0.135	0.151	0.123	-0.25	0.085	-0.12	0.007	-0.1	-0.12	1.000						
(15) Nigeria	0.103	0.345	-0.30	-0.14	0.037	-0.60	-0.09	0.496	-0.47	-0.10	0.288	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	1.000					
(16) Oman	-0.59	-0.15	-0.29	-0.22	0.135	0.220	0.200	-0.25	0.041	-0.12	-0.24	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	1.000				
(17) Qatar	-0.30	-0.04	0.205	-0.19	0.136	0.236	0.098	-0.26	0.052	-0.12	-0.26	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	1.000			
(18) UAE	0.059	-0.22	0.086	0.815	0.136	0.371	0.529	-0.23	0.727	-0.12	0.252	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	1.000		
(19) Malaysia	-0.03	-0.25	0.741	-0.09	0.135	0.157	0.188	-0.14	0.345	-0.12	-0.20	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	-0.12	1.000	

Source: Developed by author

Fig 3.10. Panel Data Line Plot

Source: Developed by author

Fig 3.11 below indicates the countries with different trending lines of Islamic banks' profitability, Sukuk, and Takaful. In some countries, such as Oman, the lines are nearly too coincident; in contrast, in Saudi Arabia, the trends of the mentioned variables are different throughout the period (2015-2021).

Fig 3.11. Panel Data Line Plot

Source: Developed by author

The scatterplot matrix from left to right shows the correlation between the dependent variable (Log GDP_{ci}) and the independent variables (PROF, Sukuk, Takaful, PSTVEX, PSTVCPI, and PSTVFD_{in}). In contrast, the matrix plot from left to right shows the correlation between independent variables.

The Normal Probability Plot visually flags meaningful divergences from normality within information sets. In summing up, the closer the points hug the line, the stronger the evidence for normality. For each variable of model 5, the normal probability plot is visualized below Fig 3.13. The evidence shows the partly normal distribution of the data set for each variable (Log GDP_{ci}, PROF, Sukuk, Takaful, PSTVEX, PSTVCPI, and PSTVFD_{in}) of the model.

The residuals tend to be low, whereas fitted values grow forward. The spread of the residuals is constant at every response level, which could be a sign of the goodness of the model considered for the research (See Fig 3.13, I).

Fig 3.12. Scatter Plot Matrix

Source: Developed by author

Fig 3.13. Normal Probability Plot

Source: Developed by author

Source: Developed by author

3.6.3.4. Remarks on Hypotheses of The Model

After data analysis through Stata 18, the responses towards research questions and acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses concluded as follows:

Table 3.20. Remarks on Hypotheses of The Model

No	Questions	Hypotheses	P- Value	Remarks
7	Is there any linkage between banks' profitability and sukuk on the gross domestic product?	H_{07} = The profitability of Islamic banks has a negative relationship with the gross domestic product.	0.095	Rejected
		H_{A7} = Sukuk has a positive relationship with the gross domestic product.	0.090	Accepted
8	Is there any connection between inflation and an exchange rate on gross domestic product with a moderating effect on political stability?	H_{08} = Inflation and gross domestic product have a positive relationship through the moderating effect of political stability.	0.007	Accepted
		H_{A8} = The exchange rate and gross domestic product have a negative relationship due to the moderating effect of political stability	0.05	Rejected
9	Does Türkiye contribute more to the gross domestic product through Islamic banks than other studied countries?	H_{09} = Türkiye contributes more to the gross domestic product through the profitability of Islamic banks than any other country in the study.	SA 0.2670 INDO 0.04 KU 0.000 NI 0.0070 OM 0.000	Accepted
		H_{A9} = Malaysia contributes more to the gross domestic product through the profitability of Islamic banks than any other country in the study except Türkiye.	QA 0.000 UAE 0.01 MA 0.001 0.001	Rejected

Source: Developed by author

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

Islamic finance has a vital role in economic growth, especially in those countries whose constitutions and other regulations contain and support Islamic rule and regulation. Islamic finance is a broad concept that includes different parts, such as Islamic banking, Islamic bonds, Islamic insurance, Islamic mutual funds, and other Islamic financial institutions. The objective is to rank countries based on Islamic finance using a scale measuring Islamic financial development indicator. Islamic financial development indicator has 5 (Financial Performance, Awareness, Knowledge, Sustainability, and Governance Indicators) sub-indicators. Based on the Islamic financial development indicator scores 2022, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Bahrain, and Kuwait ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th, respectively. A financial performance index is a weighted index of the Islamic capital market and Islamic financial institutions per country that generate Islamic financial services. Based on financial performance indicator, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Iran, Kuwait, and Bahrain ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th, respectively. The governance index is a weighted index of standards of good practice regarding regulations, corporate and sharia governance. Based on governance indicators, Malaysia, Oman, Bahrain, Pakistan, and Kuwait are in the 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th stages, respectively. The sustainability index is a weighted index of corporate social responsibility activities and ESG practices for all Islamic finance sectors and asset classes. In the Islamic finance development indicators sub-indicator (sustainability indicator), Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, South Africa, and Jordan ranked 1 to 5th, respectively. A knowledge indicator is a weighted index of education and research that is the main building block of any knowledge-based industry. Based on the knowledge indicator in 2022, Indonesia, Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, Pakistan, and Bahrain got 1st to 5th rank, correspondingly. The awareness indicator is a weighted index of Islamic finance market awareness that assesses events and news. Based on awareness indicators, Malaysia, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, UAE, and Bahrain got 1st to 5th rank among other countries, respectively.

Based on the results of the sub-indicator of financial performance, Sudan is first in Islamic banking, Saudi Arabia is first in Islamic insurance, Kuwait is first in other Islamic financial institutions, and Malaysia is first in Islamic bonds and mutual funds.

Some international organizations (AAOIFI, IFSB, IDB, SESRIC, IIRA, IRTI, IIFM, IILM, IIFA, and OIC) are working to develop Islamic finance worldwide, including law, supervision, training, education, and awareness.

Mudarabaha, Musharakaha, Muzare and Musakat, Takaful, Sukuk, Karz-i-Hasan, Vefa Sales, Teverruq, Murabaha, Ijare, Selam, and Istisna are the modes of Islamic finance that operate following Sharia law. In the first part of the dissertation, each mode of Islamic finance is explained in simple words with a comprehensive diagram.

Studying economic development is the most fascinating and complex subfield of political economy and economics. Economic development refers to programs, policies, or activities that seek to improve a community's economic well-being and quality of life. Some theories as (Adam Smith, Ricardian, Malthusian, and G.S. Mail theories, the Demographic transition theory of population, The optimum theory of population, Karl Marx, Schumpeter, Keynesian economic development theories, Rostow's stages of economic theory, Gerschenkrons great spurt theory, Nurkses theory of disguised unemployment as a saving potential, Lewis economic development model, FEI- Ranis model of economic development, Jorgenson Neo-Classical model of a dual economy, Haris- Todaro model of migration and unemployment, Leibensteins critical minimum effort theory, Nelsons low- level equilibrium trap, Big push theory, Balanced and Unbalanced growth theories, Dualism theory, Dependent theory of underdevelopment, Limit growth model, and Gunnar Myrdal theory of circular causation) were explained in 2nd part of the dissertation.

The traditional measurement scale of economic development was gross domestic product per capita (GDPpc), which was later changed to the gross domestic product per capita adjustment of purchasing power parity for more accurate measurements. Economic

development is measured by the Human Development Index, created by the United Nations Development Program (UNDP); in 2010, a letter was changed to the New Human Development Index.

Based on the human development index values in 2022, ARE (United Arab Emirate), QAT (Qatar), SAU (Saudi Arabia), TUR (Türkiye), QAT (Kuwait), OMN (Oman), MYS (Malaysia), IDN (Indonesia), and NGA (Nigeria) are ranked 17, 40, 40, 45, 49, 59, 63, 112, and 161, respectively. Compared to 2021, based on the HDI value, Türkiye comes through at a rank of 48 to 45.

The main characteristic of a dissertation related to other research is the applying different models by distinguished research methodologies. The results of the research accept and reject 13 hypotheses related to Islamic finance and economic development. Each model of the study is concluded as follows:

1. Ordinary Least Square Model (OLSM)

In this model, foreign direct investment outflows are considered as the response variable and a key factor of economic development. The regressors of the model are Islamic banks, sukuk, takaful, and multiplication forms of profitability and Sukuk (Profitability*Sukuk). The development of Islamic banks is measured by the profitability of Islamic banks and PSU, which explore the relationship between economic development and Islamic finance through the effect of Sukuk. To conclude the results of Model 1, descriptive analysis, correlation, and regression analysis were conducted, and some remarks are summarized below.

- A negative association exists between foreign direct investment outflows and the profitability of Islamic banks.
- Sukuk has a negative, and takaful has a positive relationship with foreign direct investment outflows.

- There is a positive relationship between sukuk and foreign direct investment outflows, moderated by Islamic banks' profitability.

2. Random Effect Model (REM)

This model explores the relationship between human development and takaful. Human development is measured by human development indicators that represent all economic development. Some variables (PSU, TO, PFDI_{in}, and GFDI_{in}) are considered control variables in the model used to conduct the statistical analysis and access remarks on the acceptance and rejection hypotheses as designed earlier. Cointegration of Sukuk and Islamic banks strengthens economic development compared to individuals. Government effectiveness and political stability help to flow foreign direct investment to the country and have a positive effect on developing or broadening the application of Islamic finance in economic circulation.

Regression analysis (OLS, FE, and RE) was conducted on model 2; after performing the (Chow test, Breusch- Pagan Lagrange Multiplier test, and Hausman test) tests the appropriate model was selected as a random effect.

Some diagnostic tests (Heteroscedasticity test, Breusch- Pagan Lagrange Multiplier test of independence, Pesaran test, Wooldridge serial correlation test, and Jarque- Bera normality test) were conducted to determine the existence problem of model 2 to solve for accurate and acceptable results. Once the problem of the model was determined, it was solved in a robust form, and the results were summarized for further implications for the policy and application.

- A positive relationship exists between human development and foreign direct investment inflows through the moderating effect of government effectiveness.
- There is a positive relationship between sukuk and human development through the moderating effect of Islamic banks' profitability.

- There is a negative and nonsignificant effect exists between the inflow of foreign direct investment and human development, with political stability acting as a moderating factor.

3. Ordinary Least Square Dummy Variable Model (OLSDV)

This model creates a relationship between gross domestic product per capita and Islamic banks in the context of the United Arab Emirates, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, Türkiye, Kuwait, Oman, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Nigeria. To obtain accurate results, Sukuk, Takaful, (Political Stability*Exchange Rate), (Political Stability*Consumer Price Index), (Political Stability*Foreign Direct Investment Inflows), Population, Trade Openness, Exchange Rate, and Consumer Price Index are considered control variables in the model. Türkiye is compared to other mentioned countries in terms of how much Islamic banks contribute toward GDPpc. The model is concluded after statistical analysis :

- A change in 1 unit profitability of Islamic banks, Sukuk, Takaful, PSTVEX (Political Stability*Exchange Rate), PSTVCPI (Political Stability*Consumer Price Index), and Population will cause a change in the Gross Domestic Product by 0.001, 65900, 0.000000449, 0.00000062, 0.00000769, and 1070000 units, respectively. Trade openness, exchange rate, and consumer price index have positive and insignificant relationships with gross domestic product. Saudi Arabia, Indonesia, Kuwait, Nigeria, Oman, Qatar, UAE, and Malaysia have less contribution (-24%, -274%, -121%, -168%, -164%, -111%, -112%, and -88%) compared to Türkiye's Islamic banks regarding profitability to the gross domestic product, respectively. Without Saudi Arabia, all contributions of Islamic banks toward gross domestic product are significant due to p-values, as seen in Table 3.18. The coefficient of determination, or $R^2 = 99$, means the independent variables estimate 99 per cent of the output variable as (Y) in the model. The value of the R square shows the model's ability to employ and find comprehensive and valid results for the study. Overall, the $F = 0.000$ shows the significance of the model

and is acceptable for the combined effect of the independent variable (PROF, SUKUK, TAKAFUL, PSTVEX, PSTVCPI, PSTVFDIin, POP, TO, EXR, and CPI) on the dependent variable (GDP).

- Sukuk has a positive relationship with the Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPpc).
- Inflation and gross domestic product have a positive relationship through the moderating effect of political stability.
- Türkiye contributes more to the gross domestic product through the profitability of Islamic banks than any other country in the study.

Most studies in previous literature reviews focus on the relationship between Islamic banking and economic growth and achieve positive or negative relationships based on using different proxies and distinguishing research methodologies. Based on the evidence, the development of the Sukuk, the positive relationship between Islamic banks and the sukuk market, financial sectors, financial development, Islamic banking index, Islamic finance, inflation, trade openness, ZROA, Islamic banking, and Islamic capital market have a positive association with the gross domestic product (GDP) (Fathan & Arundina, 2019; Khoutem, 2014; Smolo & Nagayev, 2024; Zarrouk et al, 2017; Gani & Bahari, 2021; Ayoub & Mekidiche, 2021; Ayoub & Mekidiche, 2022; Ghroubi, 2023; Kismawadi, 2021; Pratiei, 2016; Belkhaoui, 2023; Fatima et al, 2022; Helmi, 2018; Elmawazini, 2020; Lebadaoui, 2016; Ehigiamusoe & Samsurijan, 2021; Kassim, 2016; and Çınar & Ünsal, 2022). These results are the same as we found that sukuk, inflation, and trade openness have had a positive linkage with GDP for the last 7 years (2015-2012) in the mentioned countries.

Some studies have negative results, such as Islamic financial development causing energy inefficiency; Islamic banking has less impact on Türkiye's growth compared to traditional banking, and non-risk-sharing instruments of Islamic banks have a negative impact on GDP (Jalil Ibrahim, 2022; Chowdhury et al, 2018; Alam & Ullah, 2022).

This study used foreign direct investment outflows, human development, and GDP as dependent variables of the research models; other researchers could focus on other key factors of economic development (Poverty, advancement of technology, agriculture, industry, population, types of political regimes, sustainable development, culture, religion, domestic and foreign finance, equality, and... etc.) to create the association with Islamic finance.

We used such variables of Islamic finance as regressors of the model [Islamic Banking, Sukuk, Takaful, (Profitability*Sukuk), Trade Openness, Government Effectiveness, Political Stability, (Political Stability*Foreign Direct Investment Inflows), (Government Effectiveness*Foreign Direct Investment Inflows), (Political Stability*Exchange Rate), (Political Stability*Consumer Price Index), (Political Stability*Foreign Direct Investment Inflows), Population, Exchange Rate, and Consumer Price Index)]; Other researchers could focus on other key factors of Islamic finance [Islamic Mutual Funds, Other Islamic Financial Institutions, (Usage of Different Proxies Compared to This Research for Islamic Banking, Sukuk, and Takaful)], ... etc. to create an association with economic development. Differentiation of research method, period, region, and country is the other choice to investigate the association between Islamic finance and economic development for comparison, neither conducted individually for regions or countries.

REFERENCES

- (UNCTAD), U. T. a. D. (2023). UN List of Least Developed Countries. <https://unctad.org/topic/least-developed-countries/list>
- 1 MINUTE ECONOMICS. (2021, May 25). Technological Dualism [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o8jFnC3gLDI>
- 1 MINUTE ECONOMICS. (2021a, May 23). Social Dualism [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=W721xq2gVcA>
- 1 MINUTE ECONOMICS. (2021c, May 27). Financial Dualism [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=45rNiT_KBw
- 5 MINUTE ECONOMICS. (2021, January 31). Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth by Vidhi Kalra [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NLqtCF89rFU>
- 5 MINUTE ECONOMICS. (2021, January 31). Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth by Vidhi Kalra [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NLqtCF89rFU>
- 5 MINUTE ECONOMICS. (2022, February 13). The Keynesian Theory of Output, Income and Employment- Part 1 by Vidhi Kalra [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9rWpUGrT8oo>
- 5 MINUTE ECONOMICS. (2023, November 5). Schumpeter's Theory of Innovation by Vidhi Kalra Balana [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E4iyHtGpmLw>
- AAOIFI. (2023). History. Accounting and Audit Organization For Islamic Financial Institutions (AAOIFI). Retrieved 2/3/2024 from <https://aaoifi.com/our-history/?lang=en>
- ABASIMEL, N. A. (2023). Islamic Banking and Economics: Concepts and Instruments, Features, Advantages, Differences from Conventional Banks, and Contributions to Economic Growth. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 14(2), 1923-1950. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-022-00940-z>
- ABD. WAHAB, N., MOHD YUSOF, R., ZAINUDDIN, Z., SHAMSUDDIN, J. N., & MOHAMAD, S. F. N. (2023). Charting Future Growth For Islamic Finance Talents In Malaysia: A Bibliometric Analysis on The Islamic Finance Domains and Future Research Gaps. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 14(5), 812-837.

- ABDULLAH, A. (2017). A Comparison Between Malaysia And Indonesia in Islamic Banking Industry. *Research Journal of Business and Management*, 4(3), 276-286.
- ABDULLAH, A. K., & TERE BESSY, L. (2014). Sukuk and Bonds: A Comparison. *Islamic Finance Issues In Sukuk And Proposals For Reform*, The Islamic Foundation, Markfield, 69-95.
- ADA, A. A., & DALKİLİÇ, N. (2014). Efficiency Analysis in Islamic Banks: A Study For Malaysia And Türkiye. *BDDK Bankacılık ve Finansal Piyasalar Dergisi*, 8(1), 9-33.
- AHMED, H., & ELSAYED, A. H. (2019). Are Islamic and Conventional Capital Markets Decoupled? Evidence From Stock And Bonds/Sukuk Markets in Malaysia. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 74, 56-66.
- AHMED, K. (2011). Sukuk: Definition, Structure and Accounting Issues.
- AIMS. (2024). What is Islamic Capital Market? Academy for International Modern Studies(AIMS). Retrieved 2/28/2024 from <https://aims.education/7-basic-islamic-capital-market-instruments-products/>
- AJJA, S. R., FATHIA, M., & SUARNI, A. (2010). Tawarruq: Issue & Challenge. *Kuala Lumpur: IIUM*.
- AKHTER, W. (2010). Risk management in Takaful.
- AKİN, O., & OZSOY, S. M. (2021). Aggregate Liquidity Creation of Islamic Banks in Türkiye. *Marmara Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*, 43(1), 197-212.
- AKKIZIDIS, I., & KHAND ELWAL, S. K. (2008). Financial Risk Management For Islamic The Banking and Finance. Springer.
- AKRAM LALDIN, M. (2008). Islamic Financial System: The Malaysian Experience And The Way Forward. *Humanomics*, 24(3), 217-238.
- AL FATHAN, R., & ARUNDİNA, T. (2019). Finance-Growth Nexus: Islamic Finance Development In Indonesia. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 12(5), 698-711.
- AL RAHAHLEH, N., ISHAQ BHATTİ, M., & NAJUNA MİSMAN, F. (2019). Developments in Risk Management in Islamic Finance: A Review. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 12(1), 37. <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/12/1/37>

- AL ZAABI, O. S. (2010). Salam Contract in Islamic Law: A Survey. *Review of Islamic Economics*, 14(2), 91-122.
- ALAM, M. K., & ULLAH, M. H. (2022). Contributions of Islamic Finance in the Economic Development of Türkiye: A Review. *Journal of Nusantara Studies (JONUS)*, 7(2), 336-357.
- ALDOURY, N. (2020). Accounting in Contemporary Islamic Banks. *Uluslararası Finansal Ekonomi ve Bankacılık Uygulamaları Dergisi*, 1(1), 49-69.
- ALHARBİ, A. (2015). Development of the Islamic Banking System. 3, 12-25.
- ALHASSAN, M. D., NUOTERAH, L., ADAM, I. O., SEİNİ, A. B., BUKARİ, A., NAATU, S., & ISSAH, M. (2023). Examining The Linkages Between ICTS, Economic Development And The Sustainable Development Goals: Evidence-Based on The ICT4D Value Chain. *International Journal of Innovation Science*.
- ALI, K. M. M. (1989). Principles And Practices of Insurance Under Islamic Framework. *Insurance Journal*, 1.
- ALI, M. A. (2014). Evolution & Development of Islamic Banking—The Case of Pakistan. *European Journal of Islamic Finance*(1).
- ALI, M. A., & HUSSAIN, T. (2017). Significance of Musharaka in Islamic banking. *China-USA Business Review*, 16(1), 41-53.
- ALI, M. M., & HASSAN, R. (2016). Determinants of Shariah Non-Compliant Events in Islamic Banks In Malaysia: With Special Reference To Tawarruq-Based Financing. *Al-Shajarah: Journal of the International Institute of Islamic Thought and Civilization (ISTAC)*, 21(3).
- ALI, M. M., & HASSAN, R. (2020). Survey on Sharī‘ah Non-Compliant Events In Islamic Banks In The Practice of Tawarruq Financing In Malaysia. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 12(2), 151-169.
- ALI, S. N. (2017). Building Trust In Islamic Finance Products and Services. *Society and Business Review*, 12(3), 356-372.
- ALLENSENS. (2012, February 27). Dependency Theory [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JN6LIMY2ApQ>
- ALMSAFİR, M. K., & ALSMADİ, A. A. (2014). Murabahah Versus Interest Rate, The Equilibrium Relationship With Macroeconomic Variables in Jordanian Economy: An ARDL Approach. *Procedia-social and behavioral sciences*, 129, 349-357.

- ALMULHIM, T. (2019). Analysis Of Takaful Vs. Conventional Insurance Firms' Efficiency: Two-Stage DEA Of Saudi Arabia's Insurance Market. *Cogent Business & Management*, 6(1), 1633807.
- AL-SAYED, O. (2013). SUKUK RISK: Analysis and Management. *European Journal of Applied Social Sciences Research*, 1(3), 67-76.
- ANITA CHAND EL ECONOMICS CLASSES. (2021, September 16). #Theories of Balanced Growth and Unbalanced Growth# [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x5rVshiHO0A>
- ANITA CHAND EL ECONOMICS CLASSES. (2021b, October 16). Theories Of Dualism (UGC NET Economics, PGT Economics) [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KnOT1aDBQmw>
- ANSARI, Z. (2022). A Review Of 20 Years of Takaful Literature Using A Systematic Method. *Asian Journal of Economics and Banking*, 6(1), 2-25.
- APOSTOLIC, R., CHRISTOPHER, D., & PETER, W. (2009). Foundations Of Banking Risk. In: New Jersey: *John Wiley & Sons. Inc.*
- ASA'ARI, A. (2012) Bai'ul Wafa(Reviwe Penggunaan Dalil Mashlahah di Kalangan Hanafiyah). *Al-Qisthu*, 8, 1-17.
- AZIZ, F., ANJAM, M., FAHIM, S. M., & SALEEM, F. (2013). Mudarabah in Islamic Finance: A Critical Analysis of Interpretation & Implications. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 3(5), 1236-1243.
- AZIZ, M. R. A. (2012). Introduction To Islamic Institutions In Economics and Finance. *Universiti Sains Islam Malaysia*.
- BALLI, F., BILLAH, M., BALLI, H. O., & DE BRUIN, A. (2022). Spillovers Between Sukuks And Shariah-Compliant Equity Markets. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 72, 101725.
- BALTAGI, B. H., FENG, Q., & KAO, C. (2012). A Lagrange Multiplier Test for Cross-Sectional Dependence in A Fixed Effects Panel Data Model. *Journal of Econometrics*, 170(1), 164-177.
- BANK, W. (2024). The World Bank in Middle-Income Countries. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/mic/overview>
- BAYRAM, E., GÖZKONAN, Ü. H., YILDIZ, S. B., & EL KHAMLIHI, A. (2023). A Hybrid Approach To Financial Solvency: A Comparison of Conventional and Islamic Banking In Türkiye. *Kafkas Üniversitesi İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 14(28), 603-623.

- BELKHAOUI, S. (2023). Banking System And Economic Growth Linkages in MENA Region: Complementarity and Substitutability Between Islamic and Conventional Banking. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 14(2), 267-288.
- BEN JEDÏDIA KHOUTEM, D. (2014). Islamic Banks-Sukuk Markets Relationships and Economic Development: The Case of The Tunisian Post-Revolution Economy. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 5(1), 47-60.
- BILLAH, M. M., & BASODAN, Y. A. (2017). Islamic Insurance (Takaful) Models and Their Accounting Dichotomy. *Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance*, 34(1), 11-31.
- BOUBKER, O., DOUAYRI, K., & OUAJDOUNI, A. (2021). Factors Affecting Intention to Adopt Islamic Financing: Evidence From Morocco. *MethodsX*, 8, 101523. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8563690/>
- BOUKHATEM, J. (2022). How Does Financial Risk Affect Sukuk Market Development? Empirical Evidence From ARDL Approach. *Heliyon*, 8(5).
- BRUNECKIENĖ, J., RAPSĪKEVIČIUS, J., LUKAUSKAS, M., ZYKIENĖ, I., & JUCEVIČIUS, R. (2023). Smart Economic Development Patterns in Europe: Interaction With Competitiveness. *Competitiveness Review: An International Business Journal*, 33(2), 302-331.
- CALANDRA, D., MARSEGLIA, R., VACCARO, V., & CHMET, F. (2022). Mapping Islamic Finance and New Technologies: Research and Managerial Perspectives. *European Journal of Islamic Finance*, 9(1), 22-30.
- CAPORALE, G. M., & HELMI, M. H. (2018). Islamic Banking, Credit, and Economic Growth: Some Empirical Evidence. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 23(4), 456-477.
- CAREY, D., & FLYNN, A. (2005). Is bank finance the Achilles' heel of Irish SMEs? *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 29(9), 712-729. <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090590510629849>
- CHANAKYA GROUP OF ECONOMICS. (2018, June 9). #5 Balanced and Unbalanced Theory of Growth [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=paxH2zvDD-U>
- CHOWDHURY, M. A. F., AKBAR, C. S., & SHOYEB, M. (2018). Nexus Between Risk Sharing Vs Non-Risk Sharing Financing And Economic

Growth of Bangladesh: ARDL Bound Testing And Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT) Approach. *Managerial Finance*, 44(6), 739-758.

CIBAFI. (2023). Global Islamic Banker's Survey. G. C. F. I. B. a. F. Institutions.

CIHAK, M., & HESSE, H. (2010). Islamic Banks and Financial Stability: An Empirical Analysis. *IMF Working Papers*, 38, 95-113. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10693-010-0089-0>

COSTA, J. A. F., PINTO, A. P. V., DE AND RADE, J. R., & DE MEDEIROS, M. G. (2017). Clustering Of Regional HDI Data Using Self-Organizing Maps. 2017 IEEE Latin American Conference on Computational Intelligence (LA-CCI),

CSS WORLD. (2020, June 1). Dependency Theory of Imperialism [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T6Mb8SS8tYw>

CYPHER, J. M. (2014). The Process Of Economic Development. *Routledge*.

ÇINAR, I. T., & ÜNSAL, Y. (2022). Does Islamic Banking Stimulate Economic Growth: Evidence From Subnational Turkish Data. *Journal of Financial Politic & Economic Reviews/Finans Politik & Ekonomik Yorumlar*, 59(661).

ÇÜRÜK, S. A. (2013). İslami Finansin Türkiye'deki Gelişimi, Mevcut Sorunlar Ve Çözüm Önerileri [Doktora Tezi Selçuk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü].

DAR, A. H., & AKRAM, M. M. (2013). Islamic Economics. *Ilmi Kitab Khana*.

DAR, H. (2006). Sukuk An Introduction to the Underlying Principles and Structure. <https://www.sukuk.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/03/Sukuk-Structures.pdf>

DILBER, C. (2022). İslami Finans Ve Ekonomik Büyüme İlişkisi:Türkiye Ve Seçilmiş Ülkeler Üzerine Karşılaştırmalı Bir Analiz [Doktora Tezi Kırıkkale Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü].

DURMUŞ, G. (2023). The Place of Gratitude in an Islamic Bank's Organizational Communication Culture. *Erciyes İletişim Dergisi*, 10(1), 41-56.

E.Z. CLASSES. (2018, August 25). Nelson's Low-Level Equilibrium Trap [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hSdvUdcyweQ>

E.Z. CLASSES. (2018a, August 15). Theory of Big Push (HINDI) [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LmmYLV8xqv0>

- E.Z. CLASSES. (2018b, August 17). Theory of Unbalanced Growth (HINDI) [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LiML8OKAR9Q>
- ECOHOLICS - Largest Platform for Economics. (2022, August 25). Rostow's Stages of Economic Growth | Growth & Development | Ecoholics [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gFXfAJGJQFY>
- ECOHOLICS - Largest Platform for Economics. (2022b, October 29). Nelson's Theory of Low-Level Equilibrium Trap | R R Nelson | Growth & Development | Ecoholic [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_h5Tn88pYH0
- ECONOMICS_TIME. (2023, July 25). Ranis-Fei Model of Economic Development [UGC NET Economics | M.A. Economics | UPSC IES | [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IWuOuVqaaf0>
- ECONOSOPHIA. (2021, May 17). Jorgenson Model of Development of Dual Economy [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bxwvO0BhQ6I>
- EFFICACY. (2020, September 3). Jorgenson Neo Classical Dual Economy Model [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Wtd7wBWoo1E>
- EFFICACY. (2020a, August 12). Harris - Todaro Model of Migration and Unemployment [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ds4WrePDX5Q>
- EHİĞİAMUSOE, K. U., & SAMSURİJAN, M. S. (2021). What Matters For Finance-Growth Nexus? A Critical Survey Of Macroeconomic Stability, Institutions, Financial and Economic Development. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 26(4), 5302-5320.
- EKJYOT GUJRAL. (2021, May 1). Theory of Critical Minimum Effort [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yYYkI_v25xg
- EKOM ACADEMY. (2021, July 30). Unbalanced Growth Theory of Economic Development II PGT ECO II COMMERCE [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fhzbZpEU90Y>
- EL SHAZLY, M. R., & TRIPATHY, P. (2013). Sukuk Structures, Profiles and Risks. *Paper of Columbia College*, 1-18 .
- ELDAIA, M., HANEFAH, M., & MARZUKI, A. (2023). Moderating Role of Shariah Committee Quality on Relationship Between Board of Directors Effectiveness And The Performance of Malaysian Takaful. *Competitiveness Review: An International Business Journal*, 33(1), 62-84.

- ELMAWAZINI, K., KHIYAR, K. A., & AYDILEK, A. (2020). Types of Banking Institutions and Economic Growth. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 13(4), 553-578.
- EOM, T. H., LEE, S. H., & XU, H. (2008). 32Introduction to Panel Data Analysis: Concepts and Practices.
- ERRICO, L., & SUNDARARAJAN, V. (2002). Islamic Financial Institutions and Products in The Global Financial System: Key Issues in Risk Management and Challenges Ahead.
- FADUN, O. S. (2015). Takaful (Islamic Insurance) Practices: Challenges and Prospects in Nigeria. 1, 12-28.
- FAROOQ, M., & AHMED, M. M. M. (2013). Musharakah Financing: Experience of Pakistani Banks. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 21(2), 181-189.
- FAUZI, P. N. F. N. M., RASHID, K. A., SARKAWI, A. A., HASAN, S. F., ARIPI, S., & ARIFFIN, M. A. (2016). Takaful: A Review on Performance, Issues and Challenges In Malaysia. *Journal of Scientific Research and Development*, 3(4), 71-76.
- FIANTO, B. A., GAN, C., WIDIASTUTI, T., & SUKMANA, R. (2020). Customer Loyalty to Islamic Banks: Evidence from Indonesia. *Cogent Business & Management*, 7(1), 1859849.
- FRANCISCUS, R., PRADHANA, W., HALIM, J. K., PERMAI, S. D., ARIFIN, Y., PRAMUDYA, F. S., & JABAR, B. A. (2022). The Assessment of Human Development Index in West Java Province of Indonesia Using Regression and R Programming Technology. 2022 IEEE Creative Communication and Innovative Technology (ICCI),
- GANI, I. M., & BAHARI, Z. (2021). Islamic Banking's Contribution To The Malaysian Real Economy. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 13(1), 6-25.
- GERMÁN, C.-M., DIANA, V.-B., IGOR, Á.-S., & SANTIAGO, O.-M. (2021). Impact of Human Capital and Technology in Human Development Index in Latin American. 2021 16th Iberian Conference on Information Systems and Technologies (CISTI),
- GHROUBI, M. (2023). Linkages Between Capital, Bank Financing and Economic Growth: The Case Of Islamic and Conventional Banks From A Panel of Muslim Countries. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*.

- GRASSA, R., & GAZDAR, K. (2014). Law and Islamic Finance: How Legal Origins Affect Islamic Finance Development? *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 14(3), 158-166.
- GUBAREV, M., & SIROTİN, V. (2017). The Level And Quality of Life İn Russia And The United States Of America: A Comparative Analysis. 2017 Tenth International Conference Management of Large-Scale System Development (MLSD),
- GUIZANI, M., & AJMI, A. N. (2021). Financial Conditions, Financial Constraints and Investment-Cash Flow Sensitivity: Evidence From Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 37(4), 763-784.
- GUJARATI, D. N. (2021). Essentials of Econometrics. *Sage Publications*.
- HABIB, S. F. (2018). Fundamentals of Islamic Finance and Banking. John Wiley & Sons.
- HAIDER, J., & AZHAR, M. (2011). Islamic Capital Market: Sukuk and its Risk Management in the Current Scenario. In.
- HALIS, M., & ELTAWIL, A. E. A. (2017). Risk Management in Islamic Banks: Findings From Libya. *Ekonomik ve Sosyal Arařtırmalar Dergisi*, 13(2), 97-118.
- HANIF, M., & IQBAL, A. (2014). An Evaluation of Takaful Insurance: Case of Pakistan. *Journal of Islamic Economics, Banking and Finance*, 13(1).
- HARON, S., & NURSOFIZA WAN AZMI, W. (2009). Islamic Finance and Banking System: Philosophies, Principles and Practices. (*No Title*).
- HASMAWATI, A., & MOHAMAD, A. (2019). Potential Application of Istisna's Financing in Malaysia. *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets*, 11(2), 211-226.
- HASSAN, H. A., ABBAS, S. K., & ZAINAB, F. (2018). Anatomy of Takaful. *Global Scientific Journals*, 6(3), 143-155.
- HASSAN, M. K., ALİYU, S., HUDA, M., & RASHİD, M. (2019). A Survey On Islamic Finance And Accounting Standards. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 19, S1-S13.
- HATTAR, A. S. (2016). Winning Banking Strategies To Identify Efficiency Changes During A Financial Crisis. Walden University.
- HEAVILY INDEBTED POOR COUNTRIES (HIPC) INITIATIVE. (2024). World Bank. Retrieved 15/5/2024 from <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/debt/brief/hipc>

- HIJAZI, S., FAWAZ, R., KALAKECH, M., KALAKECH, A., & HAMAD, D. (2018). Top Development Indicators For Middle Eastern Countries. 2018 Sixth International Conference on Digital Information, Networking, and Wireless Communications (DINWC),
- HRYHORUK, P., KHRUSHCH, N., & GRYGORUK, S. (2019). An Approach To Design A Composite Index of Economic Development and Identifying The Bounds of its Levels. 2019 9th International Conference on Advanced Computer Information Technologies (ACIT),
- HUANG, T. (2020). Scientific Understanding of The Fundamentals of China's Economic Development. *China Political Economy*, 3(2), 279-287.
- HUMAN DEVELOPMENT INDEX (HDI). (2024). United Nations Development Program. Retrieved 28/5/2024 from <https://hdr.undp.org/data-center/human-development-index#/indicies/HDI>
- HUMAN DEVELOPMENT REPORT. (2023-2024). U. N. D. P. (UNDP). <https://hdr.undp.org/system/files/documents/global-report-document/hdr2023-24reporten.pdf>
- HUMTA, H., & ŞAHIN, I. B. E. (2023). Foreign Direct Investment and Financial Development: Evidence from Selected Arab League Countries. *Review of Business and Economics Studies*, 11(4), 29-44.
- IBRAHIM, A.-J. (2022). The Role of Islamic Finance in the Growth of the Circular Economy. Hamad Bin Khalifa University (Qatar).
- IBRAHIM, M. H. (2015). Issues In Islamic Banking And Finance: Islamic Banks, Shari'ah-Compliant Investment and Sukuk. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 34, 185-191.
- IFSB- Journal of Islamic Economics, Banking and Finance, Islamic Financial Services Board (2009), Capital Adequacy Requirements for Sukuk, Securitizations and Real Estate Investment.
- IFSB. (2023). About IFSB. The Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB). Retrieved 1/20/2024 from <https://www.ifsb.org/establishment/>
- IIFA. (2022). International Islamic Fiqh Academy. International Islamic Fiqh Academy (IIFA). Retrieved 25/2/2024 from <https://iifa-aifi.org/en#>
- IIFM. (2022). ABOUT IIFM. Islamic Financial Services Industry (IFSI). Retrieved 29/2/2024 from <https://www.iifm.net/about-iifm/corporate-profile>

- IILM. (2021). Home/About the IILM. The International Islamic Liquidity Management Corporation Retrieved 1/10/2024 from <https://iilm.com/about-iilm/>
- IIRA. (2021). Corporate Profile. Islamic International Rating Agency (IIRA). Retrieved 18/2/2024 from <https://www.iirating.com/About.html>
- INDONESIA DATASETS. (2024). IMF. Retrieved 1/6/2024 from <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/IDN>
- IQBAL, M., AHMAD, A., & KHAN, T. (1998). Challenges Facing Islamic Banking (Vol. 1). Islamic Research and Training Institute Jeddah.
- IQBAL, N., HAIDER, N., AKHTAR, M. R., & KARIM, S. H. A. (2014). Musharaka Financing for Poverty Alleviation in Pakistan. *International Letters of Social and Humanistic Sciences*, 26, 71-81.
- IsDB. (2024). The Islamic Development Bank. The Islamic Development Bank. Retrieved 25/2/2024 from <https://www.isdb.org/publications/the-islamic-development-bank>
- IsDBI. (2024). About Us. Islamic Development Bank Institute (IsDBI). Retrieved 22/1/2024 from <https://isdbinstitute.org/about-us/>
- ISLAHI, A. A. (2018). History of Islamic Banking and Finance. Intellectual Discourse, suppl. Special Issue, 26, 403-429. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/history-islamic-banking-finance/docview/2138496865/se-2?accountid=16935>
- JATMIKO, W., EBRAHIM, M. S., & SMAOUI, H. (2023). Sukūk Development And Income Inequality. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 88, 101852.
- JHINGAN, M. L. (2011). The Economics of Development and Planning. Vrinda Publications Delhi .
- JORGENSON, D. W. (2018). Production and Welfare: Progress in Economic Measurement. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 56(3), 867-919.
- KAHF, M. (2007). 17 Islamic Banks and Economic Development. *Handbook of Islamic banking*, 277.
- KASSIM, S. (2016). Islamic Finance and Economic Growth: The Malaysian Experience. *Global Finance Journal*, 30, 66-76.
- KATO, T. (2022). Islamic and Capitalist Economies: Comparison Using Econophysics Models of Wealth Exchange and Redistribution. *PloS one*, 17(9), e0275113.

<https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article/file?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0275113&type=printable>

- KERR, P. (1993). Adam Smith's Theory of Growth and Technological Change Revisited. *Contributions to Political Economy*, 12(1), 1-27.
- KHAN, N., KCHOURI, B., YATOO, N. A., KRÄUSSL, Z., PATEL, A., & STATE, R. (2022). Tokenization of Sukuk: Ethereum Case Study. *Global Finance Journal*, 51, 100539.
- KHAN, T., & AHMED, H. (2001). Risk Management: An Analysis of Issues in Islamic Financial Industry (Occasional Paper).
- KHARE, R., & KUMAR, Y. (2016). Employment Creation and Human Development Index Analysis of Renewable Mix in Island Mode. 2016 IEEE 7th Power India International Conference (PIICON),
- KISMAWADI, E. R. (2023). Contribution of Islamic Banks and Macroeconomic Variables To Economic Growth in Developing Countries: Vector Error Correction Model Approach (VECM). *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*(ahead-of-print).
- KUMAR, A., & SHARMA, U. (2014). Traditional Vs. Modern Measures Of Economic Development: A Theoretical Analysis. *International Journal of Scientific Footprints*, 2(1), 94-101.
- KURNIAWANSYAH, D., & AGUSTIA, D. (2017). A Parallel Ba'i Al-Salam Financing Mechanism for Banana Farmers, Micro Enterprises, and Medium Enterprises. *Advanced Science Letters*, 23(9), 8530-8534.
- KUSUMA, K. A., & SILVA, A. C. (2014). Sukuk Markets: A Proposed Approach for Development. *World Bank Policy Research Working Paper*(7133).
- KUWAIT DATASETS. (2024). IMF. Retrieved 1/6/2024 from <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/KWT>
- LAJUNI, N., WONG, W. P. M., YACOB, Y., TING, H., & JAUSIN, A. (2017). Intention To Use Islamic Banking Products and its Determinants. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 7(1), 329-333.
- LAL, T. (2021). Impact of Financial Inclusion on Economic Development of Marginalized Communities Through The Mediation Of Social And Economic Empowerment. *International Journal of Social Economics*, 48(12), 1768-1793.
- LEARN OIKONOMIA. (2024, January 30). Financial Dualism in Economics | Development Economics | Learn Oikonomia [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gwY5a0MbW-E>

- LEARN TO COMPETE. (2022, May 12). #31 Neo-Classical Theory of Investment (Jorgenson's Theory of Investment) Explained by Hardev Thakur [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=428UUT4h3KU>
- LEBDAOUI, H., & WILD, J. (2016). Islamic Banking Presence and Economic Growth In Southeast Asia. *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 9(4), 551-569.
- LEDHEM, M. A. (2022). The Financial Stability of Islamic Banks and Sukuk Market Development: Is The Effect Complementary or Competitive? *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 22, S79-S91.
- LEDHEM, M. A., & MEKIDICHE, M. (2021). Islamic Finance and Economic Growth Nexus: An Empirical Evidence From Southeast Asia Using Dynamic Panel One-Step System GMM Analysis. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 12(8), 1165-1180.
- LEDHEM, M. A., & MEKIDICHE, M. (2022). Islamic Finance And Economic Growth: The Turkish Experiment. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 14(1), 4-19.
- LIFE ECONOMICS. (2023, August 29). Nurkse theory of disguised unemployment | Malayalam | Deepesh Manoharan | LIFE ECONOMICS [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=on62D81fCvY>
- LIST OF LANDLOCKED DEVELOPING COUNTRIES. (2023). UNCTAD. Retrieved 20/5/2024 from https://unctad.org/topic/land_locked-developing-countries/list-of-LLDCs
- LIU, C., LI, X., & XU, L. (2014). The Influence of Regional Intellectual Capital on Regional Economic Development: Evidence From Shandong Province. 2014 International Conference on Management of e-Commerce and e-Government,
- LONE, F. A., & QUADIR, A. (2017). Incentive Structure of Financing A Project: An Islamic Finance Approach. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 7(1), 87-91.
- MADNI, G. R. (2017). Dynamism of Islamic Financing on Economic Growth. *Turkish Journal of Islamic Economics*, 4(2), 51-70.
- MAHAJAN, S. K. (2013). Human Development Index—Measurements, Changes and Evolution. 2013 Nirma University International Conference on Engineering (NUiCONE),
- MAHAVIDYA ECONOMICS SCHOOL. (2020, August 6). Fei- Ranis Economics Growth Model | Surplus Labour Model Upsc Economics

Optional | Nta net | Pgt eco [Video]. YouTube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8ofl2gWwQXI>

MAHAVIDYA ECONOMICS SCHOOL. (2020, August 8). Minimum Critical Effects Part 1| Lebestein's Theory of Critical Minimum Effects | UPSC economics|net [Video]. YouTube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jjiiTfN-YEY>

MAHAVIDYA ECONOMICS SCHOOL. (2021, March 18). Gunard Myrdal Theory of Circular Causation Part 1 | Upsc Economics Optional | UGC net | Development [Video]. YouTube.
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y6v_V85J91w

MALAYSIA DATASETS. (2024). IMF. Retrieved 1/6/2024 from
<https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/MYS>

MALCOM, A., & BHANDARI, C. N. (2021). An Empirical Study on Microfinance and its Impact on Human Development Indicators Using The Instance Of Kerala's Kudumbashree Model. 2021 12th International Conference on Computing Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT),

MALEK, M. A., & RAO, G. V. (2022). Profitability of Islamic Banking—A Study of Select Islamic Banks from Asia. *International Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance Studies*, 8(1), 57-77.

MANAGEMENT CLASSES. (2022, March 12). Karl Marx's Theory of Economic Development in Hindi [Video]. YouTube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HjOLrJeYGqw>

MARIFA ACADEMY. (2015, January 13). Sukuk - Al Murabaha: Lesson - 5 [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6nydUy7OtzA>

MARIFA ACADEMY. (2015b, January 13). Types Of Sukuk-Sukuk Al Ijara: Lesson - 3 [Video]. YouTube.
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9psR_jfyJAI

MARIFA ACADEMY. (2015b, January 14). Sukuk Al Modaraba: Lesson - 4 [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fiBh21otM2M>

MARIFA ACADEMY. (2021, August 10). Takaful Business Models Wakala Waqf Hybrid:Lesson4[Video].<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tdgnv5LPoJc&list=PLNAQg42Qalc1tpwXuHDjjVlm6ypDLqBF9&index=4>

MARIFA ACADEMY. (2021, August 10). Takaful Business Mudaraba: Lesson - 5 [Video].<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xCbTNMeTXRY&list=PLNAQg42Qalc1tpwXuHDjjVlm6ypDLqBF9&index=5>

- MATSAWALI, M. S., ABDULLAH, M. F., YEO, C. P., ABIDIN, S. Y., ZAINI, M. M., ALI, H. M., ALANI, F., & YAACOB, H. (2012). A Study on Takaful and Conventional Insurance Preferences: The Case of Brunei. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 3(22).
- MAYSAMI, R. C., & GOLRIZ, H. (1997). Pragmatic Interest-Free Banking: Metamorphosis of The Iranian Financial System. *Journal of International Banking Law*, 12, 92-98.
- MAYSAMI, R. C., & KWON, W. J. (1999). An Analysis of Islamic Takaful Insurance. *Journal of Insurance Regulation*, 18(1).
- MCMILLEN, M. J. (2007). Shari'ah-Compliant Project Finance: An Overview, Including Structures. *Journal of Islamic Economics, Banking and Finance*, 3(1), 1-45.
- METREAU, N. H. C. V. R. E. (2023). World Bank Group Country Classifications by Income Level For FY24 (July 1, 2023- June 30, 2024). *World Bank Blogs*. Retrieved 30/5/2024 from <https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/opendata/new-world-bank-group-country-classifications-income-level-fy24>
- MINI SETHI. (2021b, July 16). Lewis Model of Economic Development [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-9dcV0ncDp4>
- MINI SETHI. (2021b, July 8). Theory of Unbalanced Growth [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=brZNc3-xPhc>
- MINI SETHI. (2021c, July 11). Balanced Growth Theory of Ragnar Nurkse [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-wEYCGCsYr0>
- MINI SETHI. (2021c, July 22). Theory of Big Push [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8kl8aEY-GQE>
- MINI SETHI. (2021c, September 6). FEI - RANIS Model of Economic Development [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=T1_rHj4qLz8
- MINI SETHI. (2021d, October 8). Harris Todaro Model [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zg5n_WwqCaw
- MINI SETHI. (2021e, November 28). Nelson's Low-Level Equilibrium Trap [Video]. YOUTUBE. [HTTPS://WWW.YOUTUBE.COM/WATCH?V=ZYZ35MOGLBI](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZYZ35MOGLBI)
- MINI SETHI. (2021i, December 5). Gunnar Myrdal Theory of Circular Causation [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WRYAkh-QKnM>

- MINI SETHI. (2022, November 5). Keynesian Theory of Income & Employment [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lfcnQGVCR0U>
- MINI SETHI. (2023, July 2). Theories of Population - Malthusian, Demographic Transition, Optimum Population Theory [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=opJLFIFHpvw>
- MIGDAD, A. M. (2021). Scope Of CSR in Islamic Economics and Finance. *Islamic Economics Journal*, 7(2), 186-203.
- MOHAMED, S., & AHMED, T. (2022). *ICD – Refinitiv Islamic Finance Development Report 2022*. A. L. B. Islamic Finance Refinitiv. https://Icd-Ps.Org/Uploads/Files/Icd%20refinitiv%20ifdi-Report-20221669878247_1582.Pdf
- MOHAMMED, M. M., KHAN, N., & AHMAD, T. (2022). Opportunity for Islamic Finance in Blockchain Solutions for Climate Change: A Case Study of DCarbonX Model. *Bait Al-Mashura Journal*(18).
- MOHIELDIN, M., HUSSEIN, K., & ROSTOM, A. (2019). On Financial Development and Economic Growth in Egypt. *Journal of Humanities and Applied Social Sciences*, 1(2), 70-86.
- MSEDDI, S. (2023). International Issuance Of Sukuk and Companies' Systematic Risk: An Empirical Study. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 23 (3), 550–579. In.
- MUNEEZA, A., & MUSTAPHA, Z. (2020). The Potential of Fintech In Enhancing The Use Of Salam Contract In Islamic Banking. *International Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance (IJIEF)*, 3(2), 305-334.
- NANAEVA, Z. K. (2010). How Risky Sukuk Are: Comparative Analysis of Risks Associated with Sukuk and Conventional Bonds the British University in Dubai (BUiD)].
- NASUCHA, M. N., AHMED, R., & BARRE, G. M. (2019). Examining the Viability of Istisna for Project Financing: An Economic Perspective. *International Journal of Management and Applied Research*, 6(4), 259-270.
- NAWAZ, H. (2019). An Investigation into Factors That Determine the Growth Rate in The Islamic Banking and Finance. *Future Business Journal*, 5(1), 1.
- NAZAROV, I. I., & DHIRAJ, N. S. (2019). A Conceptual Understanding and Significance of Takaful (Islamic Insurance): History, Concept, Models and Products. *International Journal for Innovation Education and Research*, 7(4), 280-298.

- NIGERIA DATASETS. (2024). IMF. Retrieved 1/6/2024 from <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/NGA>
- NOMAN, M., UR RAHMAN, M., HAQQNI, H. F.-E.-H., BUSHRA, S., REHMAN, A. A., GHANI, M. U., & ULLAH, I. (2022). An Analytical Study of Ijarah as A Model of Finance in Islam. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(11), 3161-3171.
- OBAIDULLAH, M. (2007). 13 Securitization in Islam. *Handbook of Islamic banking*, 191.
- OCHOA, M., & NONNECKE, B. (2019). Increasing Human Development In Rural Mexico Through Policies For Internet Access. 2019 IEEE Global Humanitarian Technology Conference (GHTC),
- OIC. (2024). History. Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) Retrieved 2/3/2024 from <https://new.oic-oci.org/SitePages/CommonPage.aspx?Item=1>
- OKUMUS, H. S., & ARTAR, O. K. (2012). Islamic Banks And Financial Stability In The GCC: An Empirical Analysis. *Istanbul Ticaret Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 11(21), 147-164.
- OLDFIELD, G., & SANTOMERO, A. (1970). The Place of Risk Management in Financial Institutions. *Sloan Management Review*, 39.
- OMAN DATASETS. (2024). IMF. Retrieved 1/6/2024 from <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/OMN>
- PALDI, C. (2014). Understanding Riba and Gharar in Islamic Finance. *Journal of Islamic Banking and Finance*, 2(1), 249-259.
- PASHA, A. T., & HUSSAIN, M. M. (2013). Takaful Business Models: A Review, A Comparison. *Business Management Dynamics*, 3(4), 24.
- POAN, R., MERIZKA, V. E., & KOMALASARI, F. (2022). The Importance of Trust Factor In The Intentions To Purchase Islamic Insurance (Takaful) In Indonesia. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 13(12), 2630-2648.
- PRATIWI, A. (2016). Islamic Banking Contribution In Sustainable Socioeconomic Development In Indonesia: An Epistemological Approach. *Humanomics*, 32 (2), 98–120. In: H-12-2015-0085.
- PRISMA 2020 STATEMENT. (2024). New Preferred Reporting Items For Systematic Reviews And Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) <https://www.prisma-statement.org/prisma-2020-flow-diagram>
- QATAR DATASETS. (2024). IMF. Retrieved 1/6/2024 from <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/QAT>

- RAFINDADI, A. A., ISAH, A. B., & USMAN, O. (2023). Economic Development And Energy Consumption in Saudi Arabian Economy: Do Globalization, Financial Development And Capital Accumulation Matter? *International Journal of Energy Sector Management*.
- RAHMAN, M. H. (2018). Mudarabah And Its Applications in Islamic Finance: An Analysis. *Asian Journal of Research in Banking and Finance*, 8(6), 33-46.
- RAZAK, S. S., SAITI, B., & DINÇ, Y. (2019). The Contracts, Structures and Pricing Mechanisms of Sukuk: A Critical Assessment. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 19, S21-S33.
- RISE AND SHINE. (2021, July 9). The Ricardian Theory of Economic Development: Growth and Development - UGC NET/JRF Economics [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KjUtjxC44l8>
- RISE AND SHINE. (2021b, July 31). Mill's Theory of Economic Development: Growth and Development - UGC NET/JRF ECONOMICS [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bopYG7WGozk>
- RISE AND SHINE. (2022, March 2). Schumpeter Theory of Economic Development: Growth and Development - UGC NET/JRF ECONOMICS [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y4zsu_4dHHk
- ROBERT INKLAAR. (2020, April 24). Lewis Model (part 1) [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=df-4hqwPxnE>
- ROBERT INKLAAR. (2020a, April 24). Harris-Todaro Model [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KlSDIWlWLq8>
- ROBERT INKLAAR. (2020b, May 12). Lewis Model (part 2, extended) [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PVfspdpgp4Go>
- SA'AD, A. A., NAPIAH, M. D. M., & BT IBRAHIM, U. (2016). The Structural Development of Istisna Sukuk From A Shariah Perspective. *Islam & Civilisational Renewal*, 7.(2)
- SAIDU, O. S. (2020). Towards A Pristine Islamic Finance: Precondition. Share: *Jurnal Ekonomi dan Keuangan Islam*, 9(2), 164-183.
- SAMAAJ SAMJHEIN. (2022, May 20). Dependency Theory - Development Studies [URDU/HINDI] [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dFzg60LD20>
- SAMUELSON, P. A. (1975). The Optimum Growth Rate For Population. *International Economic Review*, 531-538.

- SANTILLÁN LUNA, I., CEJA PIZANO, J., & PINEDA DOMÍNGUEZ, D. (2024). Practical Strategies for The Economic Development of Mexico: Nearshoring Trend. *Mercados y negocios*, 25(52), 109-130.
- SAUDI ARABIA DATASETS. (2024). IMF. Retrieved 1/6/2024 from <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/SAU>
- SAUNDERS, A., & CORNETT, M. M. (2006). Financial Institutions Management: A Risk Management Approach. *McGraw-Hill/Irwin*. <https://books.google.com.tr/books?id=6a9pAAAACAAJ>
- SESRIC. (2024). About SESRIC. Statistical, Economic and Social Research and Training Centre for Islamic Countries (SESRIC). <https://www.sesric.org/sesric-about.php>
- SHEENU ECONOMICS CLASSES. (2021, May 7). Leibenstein's Critical Minimum Effort Thesis | Meaning | Need | Key Elements | Part-1 [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Cn2AggdPB1c>
- SHETH, S., & BETTENCOURT, L. M. (2020). The Community Human Development Index (CHDI): Localizing Sustainable Development Goals Across Scales. 2020 IEEE Conference on Technologies for Sustainability (SusTech),
- SHOIMAH, S. N., SUSANTI, D. O., & TEKTONA, R. I. (2021). The Characteristics of Murabahah Akad With Ba'i Al-Wafa' System.
- SHUKOR, S. A. (2020). Trust In Takaful Agents: Antecedents and Consequences. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 11(6), 1161-1174.
- SISWANTORO, S. (2022). Can The Integration Between Islamic Social Finance and Islamic Commercial Finance Tackle Poverty in Indonesia? *Jurnal Ekonomi & Keuangan Islam*, 236-249.
- SMAOUI, H., & GHOUMA, H. (2020). Sukuk Market Development and Islamic Banks' Capital Ratios. *Research in International Business and Finance*, 51, 101064.
- SMOLO, E., & NAGAYEV, R. (2024). Finance–Growth Nexus: Evidence From Systemically Important Islamic Finance Countries. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 15(4), 684-700.
- SSD EDUCATIONAL CLASSES. (2020, March 31). Karl Marx's Theory of Economic Development [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OMI_m3b7z2w

- STEHLÍKOVÁ, B., TAUŠOVÁ, M., & ČULKOVÁ, K. (2024). Impact of the COVID-19 Pandemic on the Economic Development of the Mining and Construction Industry: Case Study in Slovakia. *Economies*, 12(5), 119.
- STJOHNSPIPECASTS. (2021, February 11). Gerschenkron, Industrialisation and Economic Backwardness [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=w8Hx8TELKvI>
- SUSILAWATI, I., MADANI, L., SUTRISNO, S., NASIM, A., & NINGSIH, C. (2023). The Role of Sharia Supervisory Board in Implementing Public Trust on Sharia Banks. *Islamic Research*, 6(1), 15-19.
- ŞİMŞEK, M., & PEKKIRBIZLI, H. K. (2021). Islamic Insurance and Takaful Insurance Models. *BALAGH-Journal of Islamic and Humanities Studies*, 2(1), 2-16.
- TABASH, M. I., ABDULKARİM, F. M., AKİNLASO, M. I., & DHANKAR, R. S. (2022). Islamic Banking And Economic Growth: Fresh Insights From Nigeria Using Autoregressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) Approach. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 13(4), 582-597.
- TAN, Y.-L., & MOHAMAD SHAFİ, R. (2021). Capital Market And Economic Growth İn Malaysia: The Role of Şukūk and other Sub-Components. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 13(1), 102-117.
- TESTPREP (AP, GATE, NET . . .). (2019, December 21). Theory of Big Push: by Rosenstein Rodan; A Theory of Balanced Growth (Economics) [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BaC9nMS43w8>
- THEGEOECOLOGIST. (2021, August 10). Malthusian Theory of Population| Malthusian Theory UPSC [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RF8zUN3g9_A
- THEGEOECOLOGIST. (2021b, August 12). Demographic Transition Theory |Notestein |Geography optional [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pui3XjIC2II>
- THEGEOECOLOGIST. (2021c, November 10). Limits To Growth- Economic Geography -Geoecologist-UPSC [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WmpkFRBhQSQ>
- TODARO, M. P., & SMITH, S. C. (2020). *Economic Development*. Pearson UK.
- TOHIRİN, A., & ISMAİL, M. A. (2016). Financial Constraints and Islamic Finance: Lesson Learned From External Financing Perspective. *Economic Journal of Emerging Markets*, 8(2), 98.

- TRIPTI SANGWAN. (2020, July 7). Schumpeter Theory of Economic Development | Economic Growth and Development| Creative Destruction| [Video]. YouTube.
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M_Ms-F7jLcA
- TÜRKIYE DATASETS. (2024). IMF. Retrieved 1/6/2024 from <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/TUR>
- UCAK, A. (2015). Adam Smith: The Inspirer of Modern Growth Theories. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 195, 663-672.
- UGCNET ECONOMICS. (2020, August 21). John Stuart Mill's Theory of Development [Video]. YouTube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZAcDK2i83A4>
- UN LIST OF LEAST DEVELOPED COUNTRIES. (2023). UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD). Retrieved 26/5/2024 from <https://unctad.org/topic/least-developed-countries/list>
- UNITED ARAB EMIRATE DATASETS. (2024). IMF. Retrieved 1/6/2024 from <https://www.imf.org/external/datamapper/profile/ARE>
- UPSC 360. (2020, October 28). Limits To Growth Model | Economic Geography | Geography Optional | UPSC IAS [Video]. YouTube.
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YzG6_y9MD3I
- VICARY ABDULLAH, D., & KEON, C. (2010). Islamic Finance: Why It Makes Sense. In: *Marshall Cavendish Business*.
- VİSİON ECONOMİCS. (2020, August 3). Myrdal's Theory of Circular Causation/ Spread And Backwash Effect/Theory of Inequalities/ [Video]. YouTube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AZCMTOfaw8>
- WIDIASTUTI, T., ROBANI, A., SUKMANINGRUM, P. S., MAWARDI, I., NINGSIH, S., HERIANINGRUM, S., & AL-MUSTOFA, M. U. (2022). Integrating Sustainable Islamic Social Finance: An Analytical Network Process Using the Benefit Opportunity Cost Risk (ANP BOCR) Framework: The Case of Indonesia. *PloS one*, 17(5), e0269039.
- WOOLDRIDGE, J. M. (2006). Cluster-Sample Methods in Applied Econometrics: An Extended Analysis. *Michigan State University Mimeo*.
- YANPAR, A. (2014). İslami Finans - İlkeler, Araçlar ve Kurumlar; *Scala Yayıncılık*
- YAS, M. (2023). Legal And Regulatory Issues of Islamic Finance In Türkiye: A Qualitative Discussion. *Journal of Central Banking Law and Institutions*, 2(3), 401-434.

- YASSER KHAN. (2022, November 22). NuRksE Theory on Disguised Unemployment | NurKsE Theory | Disguised Unemployment | Economics | CUET [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ro8gx4innng>
- YASSER KHAN. (2023, July 4). Social Dualism | Dualism | Economics | Development Economics | CUET UGC UPSC | Technical Dualism [Video]. YouTube. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QSWWPICBU_M
- YASUKAWA, M. (1952). General Concept of Optimum Population. *Archives of the Population Association of Japan*, 1, A113-A119.
- YOUTUBE. (2015, September 15). Adam Smith's Theory of Growth. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6g-Ga32klWI>
- YUSUF, M. S., & ISA, M. Y. (2021). The Impact of Ijarah/Lease Financing On Malaysian Islamic Bank Performance. *International Journal of Islamic Business*, 6(1), 49-58.
- ZAFAR, M. B., & JAFAR, A. (2024). Human Capital and Islamic Banking: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*.
- ZAHIDMAHMOOD, H., ABBAS, K., & FATIMA, M. (2017). Islamic Microfinance and Household Welfare Nexus: An Empirical Investigation from Pakistan. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 7, 1-15.
- ZARROUK, H., BEN JEDÍDIA, K., & MOUALHÍ, M. (2016). Is Islamic Bank Profitability Driven By Same Forces As Conventional Banks? *International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management*, 9(1), 46-66.
- ZARROUK, H., EL GHAK, T., & ABU AL HAÏJA, E. (2017). Financial Development, Islamic Finance and Economic Growth: Evidence of the UAE. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 8(1), 2-22.
- ZAWYA, T. R. (2015). State of the Global Islamic Economy: 2014–2015 Report. In.
- ZULKHIBRI, M. (2015). A Synthesis of Theoretical and Empirical Research on Sukuk. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 15(4), 237-248.